

Mental Health Services for SME Workplaces: Options for Scotland

Submitted by

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Abstract

Optimum service options based on mental health standards have not been explored for small and medium enterprises in Scotland. Research has shown that the focus of regulatory agencies on workplace mental health has moved from inspection and enforcement to achieving compliance with public regulation and sociocultural influence. SMEs have constraints in meeting mental health standards through professional and costly options that larger organisations frequently use. The need for professionals to reach workforces and implement mental health standards in SMEs is driving innovation. The range of low cost or free mental health service options is identified on a spectrum from information technology-based Apps, through government-brokered services to citizen-driven social innovation and self-help based options.

This study aims to establish, through comparative analysis, how innovations may provide low cost or free mental health services options to SMEs. Building on existing work on mental health standards it asks: Which innovations – a technology-based solution, government-brokered option or self-directed social citizen networks – are most likely to be most effective in reaching SME workforces? This research's significance lies in detecting the most advantageous approach to effective mental health services in SMEs.

At the core of the research design and academic contribution and impact, the study explores how service options consisting of nine organisations may help achieve mental health standards. A qualitative method using multiple case study design was selected to increase the findings' validity and reliability. The researcher performed one in-depth interview, explored secondary data of policy documentation of service, and examined themes associated with mental health six standards. The multiple case study approach helped create a series of factors to form a consistent service provision narrative. Cross-case synthesis analytical method was selected to detect results where each case was handled as a distinct study, and then findings were linked across the individual cases.

The findings from the study indicate that service options advantageous to reach six standards are available to support employees' mental health at the SME workplace. AI-based or government-based mental health service options fulfil different supporting workplace benchmarks to establish mental health six standards. But no one type of option is capable of effectively fulfilling all six standards at the workplace.

Based on the results, it is recommended that integrated service approaches to employee wellbeing are considered to achieve mental health standards at SME workplaces. This study indicates that a combination and blend of low-cost, easy access approaches is appropriate for SMEs to achieve all mental health six standards. The research provided a perspective on the drive to offer technological or AI-based support to SMEs to create low-cost scalable interventions in the workplaces with the assistance of government-brokered and citizen-driven options.

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CIPD	The Chartered Institute of Personnel Development
EAP	Employee Assistance Programmes
EASY	Early Access to Support for You
FSB	Federations of Small Business
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
HWL	Healthy Working Lives
MHF	Mental Health Foundation
MHFA	Mental Health First Aid
MHW	Mental Health at Work
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NICE	The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
OH	Occupational Health
RTW	Return To Work
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
VOX	Voices of Experience
WAP	Wellness Action Plan
WHSS	Working Health Services Scotland

Chapter 1:

Introduction

The liability of mental health conditions on wellbeing and productivity has long been undervalued. At present, occupational health (OH) regulators in the United Kingdom (UK) are seeking to engage employers and employees in initiatives rather than inspect and enforce standards. Quality research is therefore required to explore low-cost mental health service options for small and medium enterprises (SMEs). This introductory chapter explains the research project, designed to explore how to meet service standards for mental health services in workplaces. It is comprised of seven sections, covering the context, gap and rationale of the research; aim and objective of the research; research questions; a brief description of the methodology; significance of the research; a short description of the structure of the thesis and a summary of the chapter.

1.1 Context, Gap and Rationale for the Research

In the SME context for OH in the UK, regulators have moved towards creating a more significant role for strategic coordination, encouragement and promotional activities (Wadsworth & Walters 2018). This also applies to mental health services in the workplace. The aim is to increase reach and 'buy-in' from owners and managers of SMEs and their employees by providing advice and guidance. The regulatory agencies' focus has moved from inspection and enforcement to achieving compliance with public regulation and sociocultural influence. The context in which this is occurring is the recent goal of OH regulators in the UK to engage employers and employees in initiatives rather than simply enforce regulations. This research considers innovation in mental health service provisions in Scotland for SMEs. It aims to explore how innovation might help meet standards set for mental health services in workplaces.

SMEs are a driver of innovation, but it is difficult to reach and engage with the sector. Professional and costly options frequently used by larger organisations include professional OH and Employee Assistance Programmes (EAPs), professionally delivered training in mental

health literacy workshops, or stress management. Frequently, SMEs must rely on other agents who offer and provide low or no-cost mental health services.

Low cost or free services such as general practitioners (GPs) do not have the specific expertise or the time to provide occupational mental health assistance, as reflected in the statements of Fitness for Work (Shiels et al., 2013). With low occupational health literacy among SME employers, concerns have been raised over workplace mental health. In addition, the implications of mental health for service delivery resourcing and partnerships vary significantly. The literature on workplace mental health has identified both the potential and challenges surrounding the ability of service options to give people in SMEs the opportunity to access low-cost, scalable interventions in their workplaces. At the core of the research design and academic contribution and impact of this study is a focus on how such options may help achieve the standards (see Figure 1) as set out in the current government policy (Stevenson & Farmer, 2017).

Figure 1: Six Standards for Mental Health in SME workplaces (Stevenson & Farmer, 2017)

SMEs rely on low cost or free mental health services because they do not have sufficient resources. To ensure appropriate wellbeing support for SMEs, it is therefore necessary to explore and compare the rationales and effectiveness of a range of methods for delivering mental health services. This study addresses this aim with reference to the six standards required for employers to commit to improving workplace mental health services (see Figure 1). The range of innovations is mapped on a spectrum, from highly technology-based, through to partnership innovations to social-citizen innovation. Options across this continuum currently exist for SMEs. There remains a gap in the literature regarding the actual assessment of the options available for mental health six standards involvements in the workplace. It is this gap this research seeks to fill. This study describes, analyses and compares examples of mental health service options within this spectrum in the context of Scotland.

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

The Government helps businesses to improve workplace health by developing frameworks and guidance. McEnhill & Steadman (2015) have explained what is included in the frameworks. The Public Health Responsibility Deal promotes the importance of employers participating in the public health agenda. The frameworks also include the Workplace Wellbeing Tool and this tool helps organisations calculate the cost to their business caused by ill-health. The Employer's Charter developed guidelines for employers on sickness absence and return to work process and helps employers understand their responsibilities. Six standards for workplace mental health, as outlined in Figure 1, represent the scope and focus for improving SMEs' use of such services.

The need for professionals to reach workforces and implement mental health standards in SMEs is driving innovation. These innovations need to be low cost or no cost to users. From the Scottish Government to OH professionals, there are set of stakeholders, innovators working with AI, and citizens with engagement in mental health who are actively pursuing such innovations. This research attempts to describe and compare these options by assessing examples of service provision in Scotland.

The aim of this research is to establish, through comparative analysis, how innovations may provide low cost or free mental health services options to SMEs. The implications for resourcing and partnerships vary considerably, from designing or purchasing chatbots to encouraging social-citizen networks. This research contributes to the research area of appropriate low-cost mental health interventions for SMEs and how innovations may help achieve standards (see -Figure 1) as set out in the current policy (Stevenson & Farmer, 2017).

1.3 Research Question

This research aims to establish, by comparative analysis, how innovations may provide low cost or free mental health service options to SMEs. Answering the following research questions will help achieve this aim:

1.3.1 Primary Research Question:

- Which innovations – a technology-based solution, government-brokered option or self-directed social citizen networks – are most likely to be most effective in reaching SME workforces?

1.3.2 Secondary Research Questions:

- What are the advantages and disadvantages of technology-based solutions, especially artificial intelligence (AI) and chatbots?
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of government-brokered, NHS based and non-NHS based options?
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of social-citizen innovations: self-directed networks managed by and involving users and voices of experience?

1.4 Overview of Research Design and Methodology

This study reviewed the appropriate and related literature and tried to use a combination of quantitative and qualitative methodology to pursue the research aim. The first reason for selecting this methodology was to enhance the research's rigour and validity by triangulating the data analysis from the research approaches used and minimising errors and biases (Yin 2003). The second reason was to ensure that the study pursued replication logic, validating or invalidating theory by presenting a broad range of evidence. The last reason was to provide a critical point of view (Yin 2003) in the exploration by gaining feedback from different levels of stakeholders in the selected mental health service organisations in Scotland.

1.4.1 Case studies

In this research, case studies are applied to help detect low cost or free innovative options for mental health services that are suitable for SMEs. Extensive data were collected on case organisations through desk research face-to-face interviews. The main motivation for choosing multiple case studies in this study was to help answer the research questions of the study. As such, it was necessary to interact with individuals from selected case organisations who provide mental health services to SMEs. Nine diversified case organisations were carefully chosen for this research, improving the quality of data accumulated and the overall research outcomes. Furthermore, the case study protocol provides standard general guidance and rules and improves the reliability of the study throughout the research.

1.4.2 Survey

Self-administered questionnaires were designed and sent out electronically to SMEs in Scotland. The questionnaire measures SME employees' opinions regarding the efficiency of AI administered mental health services. The questionnaire aimed to assess the first-hand experience of using chatbot. The construction of details was largely based on the literature review and the understandings obtained from secondary data.

Almost every area of life in the UK and worldwide has been affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. The education sector was no different. The pandemic has significantly impacted higher education, both in its teaching-learning and research missions. Conducting research requires face-to-face interaction with participants. But it was impossible to conduct interviews because of organisations' physical closures and a prolonged period of social distancing.

Because of time constraint, the researcher had to rely on secondary data analysis for this research even though secondary data analysis is unable to replace the dominant approaches used in academic research.

Figure 2: Research Design

1.5 Significance of the Research

Good mental health is an essential national asset; poor mental health is deeply correlated with worse physical wellbeing. The mental health and wellbeing of workers are directly influenced by the workplace environment, working conditions, intensification of the work, organisational culture, relationship with co-workers and, most importantly, the workplace's changing patterns (Hafeez et al., 2019). However, the big picture behind mental health is currently being ignored in OH. From the perspective of productivity, 91 million workdays are lost in the UK because of workers' mental health symptoms (Sime, 2019). SMEs' mental health is a neglected sector in OH research and practice, and it is difficult for SME staff to utilise the professional and

costly options often seen in corporate or large organisations. Instead, they must frequently rely on low-cost mental health service options.

A Mental Health Foundation report on the Scottish context (2018) identified the potential for but also issues with digital tools and products as a platform to give people in SMEs the opportunity to access low-cost scalable interventions in their workplaces. The potential lies in the adoption of an approach which avoids the stigma associated with disclosing mental health issues. The issues are concerned with the practical access, use and effectiveness of AI tools as anything other than a route to onward referral. The dependency on established human-to-human networks instead of innovation with technology has yet to be well evaluated. An assessment and comparison of the rationales and usefulness of a range of methods for delivering services regarding the six standards is therefore necessary.

The significance of this research lies in identifying the optimal approach to effective mental health services in SMEs. It is expected that a combination and blend of approaches is appropriate, one that works for SME workforces and stakeholders such as trade unions, industry groups and other professionals. This research offers a perspective on the drive to provide technologically appropriate mental health support to SMEs to create low-cost scalable interventions in the workplace and address sustainability issues, which are significant for private businesses, governments and self-help citizen engagement.

1.6 Organisation and Structure of the Thesis

Following the introductory chapter, Chapter 2 is the literature review, providing an overview of the mental health literature in SMEs and related subjects such as stigma, the disclosure of mental health issues, practical access to services and the effectiveness of different tools used by service providers. Chapter 3 explains and justifies the research philosophy and the research methodology, addressing the substantiated research gap. In defending these choices, this chapter discusses alternative research paradigms and methods. A discussion of ethical issues, as well as the methodological limitations, is also included. Chapter 4 is dedicated to the findings, whereby three main options of service delivery paradigms are explored through case narratives. Chapter 5 contains the discussion of the findings, assessing them in regard to the

six standards. Finally, chapter 6 summarises the research results, acknowledges the study's limitations and points to further research opportunities.

1.7 Summary of Introduction

This chapter briefly introduced all the essential areas of the thesis. It outlined the research subject, explained the rationale for the research and the gap it addressed, concluding that no specific research has as yet been conducted on how mental health service options may help SMEs achieve the six standards set out in the current policy. It also provided a synopsis of the research project's design and methodology. It further provided an explanation of the significance of the research and its structure.

Chapter 2:

Literature Review

This literature review discusses the research and concepts related to the purpose of this study and the research questions. It offers a foundation for how this study may contribute to identifying low-cost mental health service options for SMEs in Scotland. This literature begins with an overview of the importance of mental health in UK workplaces. It then discusses changes in the world of work and their influence on workplace mental health. The literature also includes the struggles of SMEs dealing with mental health at workplaces and the importance of employee mental health for productivity. This literature review is broad in scope because of a wide range of factors including cultural dimension, national initiatives, SMEs demand for easy access and less costly services. It explores the rationales and effectiveness of a range of options for delivering SME mental health services. The low-cost mental health service spectrum is discussed in reference to six standards which originate from government research. An additional purpose of the review is to provide a foundation for future studies on low-cost scalable interventions in the SME workplaces.

2.1 Occupational Health as a Whole in the UK

Access to healthcare facilities and ensuring health safety is the fundamental right of every human being in their workplace. However, these concepts were not given priority in the very beginning when the modern workplace concept was being developed during the industrialisation period. Workplace hazards were simply a part of any occupation, and the employer did not bear responsibility for them. During the Industrial Revolution, occupational health safety was not a big concern, though many incidents occurred on a regular basis, which caused physical and mental health problems (Health Management, 2015). Sir Robert Peel took the first step towards addressing this. He introduced the "Health and Morals of Apprentices Act 1802", commonly known as the Factory Act. The act explicitly applied to textile mills and factories that employed three apprentices or 20 factory workers (Health Management, 2015). This was the beginning of OH, and the priority was on physical health and safety. Therefore, mental health and wellbeing was not the key concern at the beginning of the development of health safety in UK workplaces.

Concerns regarding mental health and wellbeing began to gain importance and be included in OH during the shift from industrialisation to the service-oriented industry in the UK in the 1960s (Health Management, 2015). According to Ostry et al. (2002), from the beginning of the 1960s, deindustrialisation began to make significant changes to the UK workplace, whereby the service sector workforce had to deal with more mental pressures than the industry workforce. Health Management Ltd. (2015) reported that the UK service sector was contributing more than 76% to the UK GDP, highlighting the changing patterns of the employment and workforce of the UK in recent times. Realising these changing trends in the workplace, the World Health Organization (WHO) and International Labour Organization (ILO) defined OH as the promotion and maintenance of physical, mental and social wellbeing of professionals working in all occupations at the highest degree by preventing any health risk, controlling the risk and adapting the work to people (Burton, 2009). Importantly, both international organisations agreed on a common issue: the inclusion of mental health and wellbeing, which represents the first steps towards appreciating the importance of mental health in OH.

2.1.1 Mental wellbeing, an integral part of OH.

OH is referred to as the "health at work" in the UK, which implies all kinds of health and safety concerning workers and professionals in any workplace (Burton, 2009). The inclusion of mental health and wellbeing in OH first occurred during the 1950s and 1960s. The ILO and WHO played an important role during that period in ensuring that mental health and wellbeing at the workplace were officially recognised. In addition, significant changes in the nature of UK employment necessitated including mental health and wellbeing in occupational health (Health Management, 2015). The need for mental health is clear if the overall condition of mental health and wellbeing at work in the UK is examined. One in every seven workers in UK workplaces experiences a form of mental health problem, which is a 14.7% prevalence rate (Mental Health Foundation, 2020).

However, mental health problems are comparatively higher among female workers than male ones. It has been reported that 19.8% of female workers experience mental health problems compared to only 10.9% of male workers (Mental Health Foundation, 2020). It is easy to see the depth of this problem, which directly and indirectly impacts organisational performance,

affecting the economy, both locally and nationally. From this perspective, in the modern-day workplace, mental health and wellbeing have become part and parcel of OH.

In UK workplaces, mental health and wellbeing are the subjects of a specific focus as there is a specific legislative framework to ensure health and safety standards and the mental health and wellbeing of every employee. For example, the Health and Safety Executive (HSE) has developed a standard for employers of all sizes to ensure that every employee is taken care of regarding their mental health (HSE, 2019). The HSE standard forms a specific part in an organisation's health at work plan, whereby the mechanism is functional for monitoring all employee actions and outcomes. Crucially, the HSE standard is focused on the management of employees' mental health issues by their employers of any size, indicating the importance of mental health in OH.

From the perspective of law and regulations, it is clear that mental health is an integral part of OH. For example, the "Health and Safety at Work Act 1974" is the foundation law of OH in the UK. This law promotes both physical and mental health and employees' wellbeing, whereby every employee has the legal right to be treated well by their employers (Hart, 2020). At the same time, to ensure mental and physical health and wellbeing, employers are required to assess the overall health conditions under the "Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999" (Hart, 2020). If employers do not comply with the legislation and regulations, then they face different forms of penalties and legal consequences. From this perspective, mental health at the workplace and wellbeing is an integral part of overall health and wellbeing in OH.

2.2 How mental health Plays a Vital Role in Productivity

A workforce's productivity is directly connected to the health and wellbeing of its workforce, whereby both physical and mental health and wellbeing are essential. According to Harvard Health Publishing (2010), mental health problems are directly responsible for impacting businesses and employers as they result in increased absenteeism, error in production and service delivery, and lower productivity and profitability. Mental health problem in the workplace is a common issue in all countries. For example, Rajgopal (2010) found that reports from different parts of the world indicate that a good number of employees leave work permanently because of mental health problems. Rajgopal further highlighted that in the Netherlands, about 58% of workplace-related

disabilities are connected to the mental health of the workers and in the UK, tentatively 30%–40% of the sickness absences are caused by some form of mental ill-health. It is clear that an increased rate of mental health problems directly impacts productivity; however, it is also true that good mental health positively impacts productivity.

The WHO has estimated that because of mental health problems such as depression and anxiety, the global economy suffers a loss in productivity of US\$ 1 trillion/ year (WHO, 2019). Working is itself good for mental health and wellbeing, but a negative working environment harms mental health, causing depression, anxiety, harassment, bullying, increased work pressures and a poor workplace environment. The WHO has also emphasised the importance of ensuring OH through healthcare services and support for treating common mental disorders. A crucial finding is that for every US\$ 1 of mental health spending, the return of productivity from employees can be US\$ 4 (WHO, 2019).

The WHO has attempted to determine the link between mental health and the key reasons behind lower or poor organisations' productivity, as well as the key risk factors for mental health problems. Poor communication and management, the absence of proper health and safety policies, the low level of financial support for employees regarding their health, inflexible working hours, limited participation in an organisation's decision-making process, and unclear organisational objectives and tasks are the key risk factors in any organisation that can cause mental health problems for their employees (WHO, 2019).

From the UK perspective, mental health problems have a significant impact on organisations. It is estimated that the cost of mental health illness for UK employers was £26 billion in 2007, increasing almost twofold to £45 billion in 2016 (Deloitte, 2017). The increase of spending on mental health interventions by UK employers has a positive impact on their organisation or business, measured by productivity. Recent research has identified that employers who spend £1 on mental health interventions for their employees see a return of £5, as the employee absenteeism rate, presenteeism rate and staff turnover rate are reduced significantly (Deloitte, 2017).

The increased spending on mental health illness by UK employers also indicates that employees' mental health problems have increased recently. Deloitte (2017) focused on another aspect of UK employers' investment in mental health intervention to achieve a higher investment return. They found that if employers invest in early mental health interventions, it

is easier to achieve higher returns, indicating higher productivity. Along with higher returns and higher productivity, such investment effectively tackles complicated and advanced level mental health illnesses of employees, which is essential for ensuring quality OH.

The ultimate objective of ensuring mental health and wellbeing of workers is to obtain maximum performance from them. Indeed, due to UK employees' poor mental health, it was found that only 2 out of 5 employees can give peak performance working in their organisations (Deloitte, 2017). Mental Health Foundation (2018) reported that employers' productivity is being affected due to employees' mental health illnesses. This costs £2.4 billion each year, which represents a significant loss for employers. Sime (2019) reported a much higher scale of UK employers' loss due to ignoring their employees' mental health issues: a cost to the UK economy of approximately £70 billion each year. These figures indicate the extent to which mental health is being ignored in OH. From the perspective of productivity, 91 million workdays are lost in the UK because of workers' mental health symptoms (Sime, 2019).

An organisation's productivity is negatively impacted by the loss of working days resulting from absenteeism caused by either physical or mental illness. It is essential to understand whether the UK's changed workplace conditions result in a higher prevalence of mental health illness over physical health illness. In this regard, the Office for National Statistics (ONS) found that in 2018, approximately 141.4 million working days were lost due to injury or sickness, including physical and mental illness, which accounts for 4.4 working days per worker (ONS, 2019). The same report also found that mental health problems caused a loss of 17.5 million working days, or 12.4% of the entire estimated loss in the UK in 2018; such problems were the 4th most common reason for loss of working days in the UK as Figure 2.1 below demonstrates (ONS, 2019).

Figure 2.1: Percentage of working days lost due to sickness absence in the UK, 2018 (ONS, 2019)

Compared to this, the loss of working days due to minor illness was 38.5 million days the same year.

Figure 2.2: Total working days lost due to sickness absence in the UK from 1996 to 2018 (ONS, 2019)

Another critical factor is that, as Figure 2.2 shows, the rate of working days lost due to sickness absence has been decreasing for the last 23 years. However, the average absence per worker rate has increased; 4.1 working days in 1997 to 4.4 in 2018 (ONS, 2019). The reason for this is that the number of workers has increased in the last 15–20 years at a high rate whereby sickness, including mental health problems, has also increased significantly.

2.3 How Changes in the World of Work have an Influence on Workplace Mental Health

The workplace environment directly influences the mental health and wellbeing of workers, working conditions, intensification of the work, organisational culture, relationships with co-workers and, most importantly, the changing patterns of the workplace (Hafeez et al., 2019). The modern-day workplace environment is significantly different from the industrialisation era as work has become more service-oriented and technological revolution has made it more mental than physical. Hafeez et al. (2019) also noted that modern-day employers look for more skills, knowledge and experience. These are essential for decision-making at small to large scale in any job in any hierarchical position in the organisation. Consequently, modern-day workplace employees have to be mentally focused on achieving efficiency in job performance.

Health Management (2015) explained that during the era of industrialisation, the majority of the workforce were involved in physical labour or activities for which the use of the brain for critical thinking was low as the lower hierarchical employees followed the guidance and orders of more senior staff. However, deindustrialisation began from the 1970s onwards, when companies started to transform into service-oriented companies where physical skills and capabilities were less valued than mental skills, knowledge and experience. The UK's service sector now contributes 76% of GDP, meaning most jobs are now service-oriented (Health Management, 2015). Therefore, employees require professional skills, interpersonal skills, knowledge and experience to do their job efficiently.

The workplace has changed considerably in terms of the nature of employment and the way of working, and different factors are behind this change. Change in organisational structure, the involvement of technologies in the workplace, globalisation and the employment situation in a particular country or economy are the key factors that drive workplace changes. In modern-day business, different organisational structures are applied either to increase the productivity

of employees or to increase control over the organisation and its employees (Alvi, 2017). Whichever the reason, employees experience pressure and, in many cases, they are empowered to some extent with duties and responsibilities for making decisions and remain responsible for their own activities. Greater responsibilities come with greater mental pressures, leading to mental stress, depression and anxiety. Mental health issues are recognised as the number one cause of absence due to sickness in the UK workplace, but 95% of long-term sick leave arranged by employees mentions other reasons, indicating a reluctance to openly admit to mental health problems (Weston, 2017).

With regards to the main foundations of studies, the mental health of employees in various hierarchical roles could be embedded in unique procedures of challenges and identity development. According to Horton et al. (2014), the supervision of attachments and identities of staff is significant for an effective workplaces' growth. The authors suggest awareness about various administrative trials for staff in operational, mid-stage, and strategic roles by offering an extensive comprehension of hierarchical variations in identification. Kaplan and Mikes (2012) suggest that the company's identity may face challenges like weakening of reputation, lessening of company resources, and structural transformations, which could be anticipated to be particularly challenging to the personnel who deal with the strategic role. As opposed to this, they indicate that workers could be anticipated to be vulnerable to challenges to the operational level, like a transformation in the operational workgroup condition or a decline in the qualified role of this team in the company.

In both the Whitehall I and II research, job grade was a strong predictor of the health of employees (Fuhrer et al., 2002). Even if grade calculates the role in the hierarchy of job, it echoes beyond work experience. Living conditions, income, self-esteem, status, social background, and education are encountered by it. Fuhrer et al. (2002) also explain in their study that with the aim of arranging the most critical factor to establish health-based social grade, these factors are directly measured in the Whitehall II research. With the increase of job-related hierarchy, it is usual for demands to escalate, the intensity of control over work declines with a lower position. In the study conducted by Whitehall II, numerous reports are available for the theory that the control over jobs decreases with decreased employment roles (Marmot and Steptoe, 2008). This combination of inequality between control and demand predicts a range of poor health. Whitehall II's evidence states that lower back pain, heart disease, mental

deterioration, and sickness are seen in higher rates among individuals in work attributed to low control (Marmot and Steptoe, 2008).

In addition, the research discovered that satisfactory levels of job social assistance had a defensive impact on mental health and decreased the danger of invocations of lack of sickness (Marmot and Steptoe, 2008). A twofold escalated danger of poor common mental health was found due to less assistance from managers and vague or unreliable information (Vander et al., 2016). Likewise, mental health worsened due to the absence of assistance from peers. The Whitehall Research about work uncertainty began at the beginning of 1990. As such, other study groups internationally as well as in the United Kingdom have prompted study programmes regarding work uncertainty and its impact on wellbeing (Fuhrer et al., 2002). These researches conclude and endorse the results of Whitehall II research. Currently, significant evidence shows that work uncertainty escalates health issues, especially mental health issues and utilization of health services. Accordingly, together with job-associated anxiety, similar socio-economic aspects could also have a significant role in creating issues in the mental health of employees.

Globalisation is an integral part of modern-day workplaces as organisations are increasingly interested in cross-border operations to expand their business opportunities and secure a strong position home and abroad. Chopra (2009) stated that globalisation has opened the windows of opportunities for all kind of businesses, whereby one of the possibilities is access to the global labour market to get the most skilled and experienced individuals to achieve greater competitive advantage. However, as a result of these opportunities, employees have begun to experience new challenges linked to mental stress. For example, Chopra (2009) mentioned how globalisation has increased the job insecurity of local employees who feel less valued and less recognised in the workplace, especially employees of SMEs who experience this more often. Mental stress, depression, or anxiety can result from those experiences that negatively impact employees' mental health. However, Heal (2000) focused on another aspect of globalisation: organisations are now recruiting employees from different cultural backgrounds, meaning employees are concerned about losing their cultural identity. Heal also mentioned that the fear of losing cultural identity in a culturally diversified workplace can cause depression or stress, which has a negative effect on employees' mental health and wellbeing. In many cases, pressure from large cultural or ethnic groups in the workplace can result in fear and mental stress for employees from small cultural or ethnic groups.

In the UK, the employees that form black, Asian and minority ethnic (BAME) communities often report unfair and unequal treatment by their non-BAME employer and co-workers, making them too mentally weak to give their best performance in the workplace (Mental Health Foundation, 2019). Gopalkrishnan (2018) found that due to greater diversity in workplaces, employees from small cultural and ethnic groups experience discrimination, which can cause depression and stress. The Mental Health Foundation (2019) reported that the unemployment rate of BAME people is highest among other ethnic groups, with a rate of 26% for black people and 23% for Bangladeshis and Pakistanis. Employed BAME individuals are paid less than employees from other ethnic backgrounds with similar experiences and qualifications (Mental Health Foundation, 2019).

Occupation	All	Asian	Indian	Pakistani, Bangladeshi	Asian Other	Black	Mixed	White	White British	White Other	Other
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
Managers, Directors and Senior Officials	11	10	11	8	9	5	9	11	11	10	10
Professional	21	27	33	18	29	21	23	20	20	21	21
Associate Professional and Technical	15	12	14	10	11	12	19	15	15	13	12
Administrative and Secretarial	10	9	9	8	9	9	9	10	11	8	7
Skilled Trades	10	6	5	7	6	6	6	11	11	10	10
Caring, Leisure and Other Service	9	8	7	8	9	18	9	9	9	7	9
Sales and Customer Service	8	10	7	14	9	7	9	7	8	5	7
Process, Plant and Machine Operatives	6	9	5	15	5	7	5	6	6	10	8
Elementary	10	11	9	12	12	16	12	10	10	15	15

Figure 2.3: Percentage of employees from different ethnic backgrounds employed in different occupations (ONS, 2020)

It is important to note that, as Figure 2.3 shows, among the 11% of higher-level occupations (managers, directors and senior officials), a higher percentage of employees are employed from the White, White British and White Others ethnic groups. However, in lower hierarchical jobs such as caring, leisure and other services, and processes plant and machine operations, most of

the employees are from BAME groups. Because of this kind of socioeconomic discrimination reflected in workplaces, employees experience mental health problems, of which depression and mental stress are the most common.

The use of technology has also changed the workplace and has helped to significantly increase employees' operational efficiency. However, it is also true that the use of technology in everyday life is steadily increasing mental health problems. A study on employees from the US, UK, Singapore and UAE found that the majority of UK employees disagreed that the use of technology at their workplace improved their mental health. The authors discovered that technology erases the line between work and life (Business Matters, 2020). This is because technology makes employees more convenient to their workplace or employers, allowing them to access the workstation whenever they need to. The same study found that 74% of UK workers mentioned that due to the use of technology, the response to their work increased, leading to increased work pressure which made it extremely challenging to maintain a work-life balance (Business Matters, 2020).

In contrast, Accenture (2018) reported in their study that 65% of respondents stated that they feel positive about using technology to manage their mental health as it makes it convenient to manage their work more efficiently. Another survey of 2,000 UK employees also indicated similar opinions regarding technology at the workplace. The survey showed that most of the respondents mentioned that technology in different forms helps them manage their mental health and wellbeing, as 72% of respondents used online counselling services and 69% used meditation or relaxation apps. Online chatrooms or support groups were used by 67%, and 65% used online interactive GP services (Muller-Heyndyk, 2018). Technology at the workplace is essential for dealing with organisational operations in a competitive world, but it is also crucial to improve the personal awareness of employees with regards to managing their mental health and wellbeing by establishing control over technology usage.

2.4 How Workplace Mental health is Being Tackled in UK Workplaces.

Mental health problems are common health problems in the UK, specifically among workers. According to the Mental Health Foundation (2020), one in every four people in the UK experiences a form of mental health problem each year. The prevalence rate among UK workers is one in every six. Therefore, from the prevalence of mental health problems in the

general public and among the workers, it is clear that mental health is a key public health concern and has a significant socioeconomic impact. Consequently, there are interventions being used to tackle mental health problems at workplaces in the UK, where both healthcare and social care interventions are being applied.

There are signs of both positive progress but also negative signs regarding tackling mental health issues in UK workplaces. First, regarding the negative aspect, Deloitte (2017) reported that 72% of UK workplaces have no mental health policy, meaning that mental health problems are ignored, which is an indication of poor OH. Deloitte (2017) also reported that 56% of employers mentioned their unwillingness to employ any individual with any mental health issue including depression, anxiety and stress, even the individual is eligible for the job.

Due to this negative and less supportive attitude from employers, job seekers or even employees with any mental health issues attempt to hide them or not look for any support from their employers. Furthermore, Deloitte mentioned in the report that 92% of working people in the UK believe that admitting their mental health problems in their workplace can damage their career, which has a short and long-term impact on their social life (Deloitte, 2020). From this perspective, it is easy to understand that in most UK workplaces, employees' mental health issues are not tackled in a positive and supportive manner as the confidence of the majority of the employees in their employers is very low.

Turning to signs of positive progress, there have been some encouraging developments recently in UK workplaces. From the early 21st century, people's mental health and wellbeing, including that of workers, started to get attention at the government level. In 2007, the mental health charities Mind and Rethink Mental Illness founded the "Time to Change" programme to end the discrimination and stigma experienced by people with mental health problems in their workplaces. The programme was funded by the Department of Health, the Big Lottery Fund and Comic Relief (Deloitte, 2020).

In 2011, the UK Government began another initiative, the "Sickness Absence Review". The initiative's purpose was to motivate employers to manage their employees' mental health issues by announcing tax relief for employers who keep on their employees with mental sickness and take the initiative to speed their return to work (Deloitte, 2020). At the same time, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) developed a set of recommendations for employers to follow in making a workplace health programme. It was recommended that both

mental and physical health and wellbeing should be the priority of an organisation's senior management and that firms should ensure their employees' involvement in their health planning and wellbeing strategies. Importantly, there has been a legislative framework to promote and ensure the health and wellbeing of workers in UK workplaces since 1974 when the "Health and Safety at Work Act 1974" was introduced, but in most cases, it was physical not mental health and safety that was the priority in this legislation (British Safety Council, 2020).

In recent years, regulations and guidelines have prioritised mental health and wellbeing in UK workplaces. In 2005, the Department of Health (DH), HSE and Department for Work and Pensions (DWP) jointly devised a strategy whereby the role of employers, employees, government bodies and healthcare professionals are specified to improve the health and wellbeing of working adults. Following that strategy, the DH developed guidelines in 2006 for all kinds of employers, including large firms and SMEs, to reduce discrimination and promote mental health and wellbeing (Leka et al., 2016). In addition, two public health guidelines have been published by NICE regarding employees' mental health in the workplace. The guidelines are designed to tackle long-term mental sickness under the "Management of long-term sickness and incapacity at work" guideline and promote mental health and wellbeing under the "Promoting mental wellbeing at work" guideline (Leka et al., 2016). An important takeaway from all these procedures for tackling mental health problems in UK workplaces is that most responsibilities fall on the employers.

Large employers in the UK, including local and international employers, have addressed the importance of employees' mental health in the workplace, but SME employers have not yet done so because of a lack of awareness, resources and also a lack of information (Chowdhury and Dey, 2019). Chowdhury and Dey (2019) also mentioned that in SMEs, the staff must play multiple roles to reduce the cost of additional recruitment, but this leads to increased workload that ultimately causes psychological distress, work–life imbalance, depression and job stress burnout. In these cases, SME employers have no specific plan to deal with these mental health issues.

To tackle mental health problems in all kinds of workplaces, two approaches are generally followed: initiatives by employers and initiatives by employees. Mental Health Foundation (2020) explained that employers are now obliged to have specific mental health plans for

employees, and they also get professional training and support to identify symptoms of employees' mental health problems and be proactive with the necessary support according to government regulations. Employees are also encouraged to self-report their mental health issues to employers and encouraged to report those issues officially to get legal support.

2.5 How Cultural dimensions and National Initiatives are Important in Shaping the Management of Mental Health at Work

In the UK there are many private initiatives in the form of charities which provide mental health support to employees at workplaces, along with government initiatives whereby the initiatives are taken from the national level to get effective outcomes. According to Health Management, (2015), when dealing with mental health at work, the national initiative, including the development of policies, legislation and guidelines, is most important because it drives local initiatives. Mental health and wellbeing at the workplace and OH became a key concern in the UK from the beginning of the 1960s when national initiatives began to be taken by the UK Government (Health Management, 2015). In this regard, the Government plays the most crucial role as found by Deloitte (2019), who concluded that the Government has the power and capability to develop a legislative framework to include mental health and wellbeing as every individual's fundamental right.

A fundamental factor in how employer-managers and their employees perceive occupational health in small businesses is the impact of institutional pressure to obtain a social license to run the business (Scott, 2001). Institutions, in this regard, are the social structure that governs the link between organisation and society. Business owners and managers know that violations of these institutional rules, such as the unfair treatment of employees and ignoring workers' conditions, can have severe penalties. Beck and Walgenbach (2005) point out that small organisations deal with less institutional pressure than big firms. They also explain that the main justifications for this less institutional pressure involve the fact that SMEs are less visible to regulatory bodies than large companies and are less exposed to media and public attention (Wadsworth & Walters 2018). In their study, Wadsworth and Walters (2018) highlight the significance of regulatory factors that can increase institutional pressure on SME organisations' attitudes towards their workers' health. The regulatory pressure on both SME managers and their intermediaries develops the basis of many appropriate actions.

The impact of the poor mental health of SME employees has an overall effect on the UK economy; a cost of £35–£45 billion for employers due to the absenteeism and presenteeism caused by mental ill-health (Deloitte, 2020). This problem is common to all organisations. It occurs in both SMEs and large businesses throughout the UK, where local, community-based or individual initiatives are not effective to ensure good mental health and wellbeing in UK workplaces. Sinclair and O'Regan (2007) suggested that integrating national initiatives is the most effective way to set standards and guidelines for mental health services, for which public health organisations can play the most crucial role. Private organisations should take steps to support these government initiatives, such as Mental Health Foundation and Mental Health Care UK (MHC), which provide support through resources and information (Mental Health Foundation, 2013).

Charity organisations in the UK such as Mental Health Foundation work at the national level to create and increase employers' awareness regarding the importance of their employees' mental health and wellbeing. These charities also communicate information and training to employers and professionals regarding mental health and wellbeing legislation and guidance, which is again done at the national level to reach all employers operating business nationwide.

Culture has a direct and indirect influence on mental health and behaviour, and different responses to mental health problems are found different in different cultures (Gopalkrishnan, 2018). Gopalkrishnan (2018) further explained that cultural diversity might have an adverse impact on dealing with mental health problems in the workplace. Both negative and positive responses to such culture have been evidenced by employees with mental health problems. However, Hudson (2016) highlighted how organisational or workplace culture that directly impacts the management of mental health problems reported by employees or identified by colleagues' employers as should be avoided or criticised. Lack of positive and compassionate workplace culture often employees feel not welcomed to share their mental health problem with management. From this perspective, it is essential to develop a standard workplace with a positive and supportive workplace culture for dealing with employees' mental health issues, whereby the culturally diversified approach can be transformed into a standard workplace culture.

2.6 Standards for Mental Health Services in Workplaces

To ensure mental health services in workplaces, employers need to play a vital role, for which mental health standards can offer support. Different standards are followed in the UK, developed by different bodies, but there are common factors in all standards. Mind, a charity of mental health services in the UK, states that every employer regardless of their size and sector should follow the six standards accepted by the government under the label "Thriving at Work" and four enhanced standards to support the mental health of employees (Stevenson and Farmer, 2017). The six core standards are as follows:

- The first standard details that employers must consider several key aspects while developing a mental health plan for their employees at the workplace. The key aspects include senior leaders on board, raising awareness regarding mental health, involving employees, creating a culture of openness, promoting a healthy work–life balance, providing training and opportunities to learn regarding mental health and wellbeing, and offering a positive working relationship with employees.
- The second core standard states that the employer must develop awareness regarding mental health among employees by utilising information, tools and support, whereby the ultimate objective is to improve employees' mental health literacy.
- The third core standard states that employees struggling with mental health issues should be helped by encouraging them to have an open conversation that can be conducted during recruitment or at regular intervals throughout the employment.
- The fourth core standard supports the provision of good working conditions to every employee and ensuring a healthy work–life balance, which is the responsibility of every UK employer.
- The fifth core standard emphasises promoting the effective management of people, whereby it is the employer's responsibility to ensure a regular conversation with employees regarding their health and wellbeing. In this regard, employers should train up their line managers and supervisors regarding effective management practices.
- Finally, the sixth core standard emphasises the routine monitoring of employee mental health and wellbeing. Employers must develop this understanding by assessing available data, talking to each employee, and understanding their risk factors.

In addition to these core standards, every employer at their workplace should follow some enhanced standards:

- The first enhanced standard states that every employer should increase accountability and transparency to the regulatory bodies and employees through internal and external reporting, for which employers are encouraged to prepare an annual wellbeing report.
- The second enhanced mental health standard highlights a professional setting to demonstrate accountability by nominating an individual from the employees as a health and wellbeing representative at board or senior management level.
- The third standard states that workplace culture can be improved by supporting openness and the reporting and sharing of any mental health issue experienced by employees at the workplace. This culture can be practised in the recruitment process, whereby this standard helps to improve the positive responses of employers to employees' mental health problems.
- Finally, the fourth enhanced mental health standard states that every employer must ensure the provision of in-house mental health support and services. These services can be OH services purchased by the employer, NHS services or employee assistance programmes and can be fuelled by signposting to clinical support and digital support.

2.7 Why SMEs Struggle to Deal with Mental Health in the Workplace

In the UK, the number of SMEs is higher compared to any other business organisation. The ONS has reported that approximately 5.7 million SMEs in the UK account for 99% of the private sector business organisations employing more than 16 million employees (ONS, 2020). Furthermore, 16.6 million SMEs create 60% of the UK's private-sector jobs (ONS, 2020). A significant number of mental health problems at the UK workplace experienced by employees belong to the SME sector. A survey by the charity Business In The Community found SME employees experience work-related poor mental health issues and symptoms less frequently than large employers. Such experiences were reported by 59% of SME employees, whereas 62% of large organisations' employees reported similar problems (Business in the Community, 2019).

The report by Business In The Community highlighted that although the SMEs experience slightly fewer mental health problems than the large employers, SMEs are still lagging in terms of taking positive initiatives to address and ensure their employees' mental health and

wellbeing. The actual scenario becomes more apparent when the percentage of reporting of mental health issues to employers is assessed. Only 33% of SME employees report to their employers or management for help. However, 38% of large organisations' employees reported issues to their employer or management (Business in the Community, 2019). A further finding is that among SME employees who experienced any kind of mental health problems, 88% did not disclose their concern to their employers or line managers. These findings overall indicate that SMEs are ineffective in dealing with mental health issues in their workplace.

There are some key reasons behind the ineffectiveness or the failure to deal with mental health issues by SMEs. First, Business in the Community (2019) pointed out the lack of awareness of SME employers regarding the importance of their employees' mental health and wellbeing. Martin et al. (2009) supported this reasoning, finding that SME employers, especially small employers, do not bother to calculate the loss they face due to their employees' poor mental health. SME owners or managers are often preoccupied with the organisations' day-to-day activities, leaving them with little time for prolonged wellbeing discussion with employees and the implementation of mental health skills and training courses (Panagiotakopoulos, 2011).

Amongst SMEs, when acknowledging the particular problems concerning mental health, an essential factor to note is that SME is a blanket term for an extensive range of business and personal forms of employment. This includes freelancers, partnerships, entrepreneurs, family businesses, contractors, medium-sized organizations with 250 or less amount of staffs, small organizations with 50 or less amount of staffs, and micro organizations with 10 or less amount of staffs (Martin and LaMontagne, 2018). Even if different terms are available for SMEs globally, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) considers the number of staffs as the main standard (OECD, 2004). Among countries like Europe, Australia, the UK, and the USA, a common agreement prevails concerning the meaning of small organizations. Most are handled by their CEOs, who offer most of the functioning investment and are held accountable for the fundamental decision-making of the company (OECD, 2004).

According to the recommendations of professional epidemiologists, SMEs require unique attention since they have limited economic resources, small number of staff, limited competence and knowledge to execute interventions (Martin and LaMontagne, 2018). Martin et al. (2009) state that the policies that are frequently applied by the Human Resource Sector

of large companies like stress management training, mental health literacy seminars, and employee assistance programs are irregularly implemented by the SMEs. They also indicate that numerous SMEs do not have proper economic resources or budget for a committed Human Resource department and staff needs to deliver their work for several job roles. Supervisors and managers in SMEs also face an extra duty of describing and discussing the health welfare of staff, finishing assessments and wellness intervention techniques that are representative of managerial levels (Business in the Community (2019)). Therefore, sustaining mental health challenges at the expert level could be complex, especially with the HR department's work components extended throughout the organization.

According to Dessler (2008), the strategies and practices included in executing the human resource factor of administration are defined as HRM, or Human Resource Management, which impacts staff's performance, attitudes, and behaviours (De Cieri et al., 2008). Companies that acknowledge the significance of HR as a strength factor instead of as a service will be able to identify paths to establish a working atmosphere that is safe and understanding and would be able to justify the balance of life and work to their staffs. Companies with their own HR sector have demonstrated a significant amount of execution in communication, employee relations, training and development (Mansor et al., 2014). A major dissimilarity between large and small companies is the accessibility of resources.

In order to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of organizational functions, the company structure establishes a business hierarchy. Various small companies function in diverse methods, and there is no standardized answer concerning the company structure that each small company could select from (Lorette, 2019). Logically small companies usually maintain two uniform phases of company structure with a manager / CEO and employees. They may include a small HR team or forgo it all together (Lorette, 2019). They would have restricted resources and budgets due to small capital and modest incomes. This causes a situation where the Human Resource Department of small companies is unable to manage the expenses of aspects like developing a durable mental health strategy, relationship development, and staff training (Martin et al., 2009). These scenarios explain that administrative policies could have a significant role in preserving the health and welfare of staffs through the implementation of proper support and practical handling of major challenges that could be faced at various hierarchical levels.

HR experts could include comprehension of varying identity concerns into the support, training and development of staff at various levels (Kramar et al., 2017). Furthermore, these discoveries assist the HR group to collaborate with managerial workers to modify their distribution of rewards, duties, and tasks to employees at various hierarchical levels. According to the research conducted by Suter et al. (2021), managers who do not work with an expert team of HR could be dealing with challenges if they promote a mental health agenda with more proactive participation. In such organizations, if people were encouraged to discuss about mental health, and employees were motivated to talk about their struggles, managers may feel burdened with the amount of problems brought to them. In many cases, they would not know the right way to respond to issues outside of their expertise or concern (Suter et al., 2021). It could be the opposite in a few circumstances, where staff would not feel comfortable discussing their mental health problems with senior workers due to its hierarchical structure.

SME employers usually think about individual organisational aspects and ignore the collective impact of their employees' poor mental health on the overall economy. Martin et al. (2020) identified another reason for the unavailability of effective mental health support intervention in SMEs compared to large organisations in the UK: SME employers often believe that availing themselves of mental health interventions will incur additional costs for their organisation. In addition, the massive gap between employers and employees in SMEs in terms of reporting mental health issues is another reason why SMEs struggle to deal with mental health in the workplace.

Figure 2.4: The key reasons employees did not approach the OH or human resource management of their organisation (Business in the Community, 2019)

As shown in figure 2.4, most of the 1,645 employees mentioned their uncertainty regarding their employers' capacity to provide support for their mental health issues, and 27% of them feared the negative consequences on their career. Twenty per cent of the respondents were worried about the confidentiality of their mental health issues, and 17% were not interested in discussing those issues with anyone at their workplace. This indicates a lack of trust, communication, and a clear understanding between SME employers and employees, making it extremely challenging to deal with SMEs' mental health issues.

2.8 How the NHS and GPs are Tackling Mental Health

In the UK, people's mental health problems are managed by the NHS and GPs; there are some advantages and shortcomings to both of these service providers. The NHS has shown both a legislative and professional approach to handling mental health issues. In 1959, Parliament passed the "Mental Health Act", which provided a proper structure to the NHS for working in a more organised manner to ensure every individual's right to good mental health (NICE, 2020). Two decades later, the "Mental Health Act 1983" introduced the concept of the consent of an individual to their treatment with a mental health problem or illness. As part of the continuous improvement in this area, in 2002 the NHS developed a complete set of official mental health guidelines called the NICE mental health guideline. It became a standard followed by health and social care service providers and employers (NICE, 2020).

In recent years, the reliability of the NHS has increased significantly for individuals with mental health problems who attempt to access the NHS's mental healthcare services. However, the increased workload of the NHS has resulted in increased waiting times and mismanagement in referrals. Therefore, the NHS introduced the Improving Access to Psychological Therapies (IAPT) programme, the recent statistics of which reveal that, due to increased pressure, approximately 20% of those who made appointments did not receive treatment within six weeks after making their appointments (Fonagy & Clark, 2015). Despite these limitations, the NHS is still trying to provide quality mental health services and support to people. IAPT services have integrated multiple health care services and therapies, including one-to-one

therapy and digital therapies, to reach more service users with mental health problems. Now the IAPT is capable of treating 560,000 individuals every year (NICE, 2020).

The GPs network in the UK is also considered a route to access mental health services. However, the Mental Health Foundation (2019) highlighted that GPs were not skilled and sufficiently experienced to deal with mental health issues as they lack expertise in occupational mental health. This was the scenario 5 to 7 years ago, but this has changed in recent times as some new requirements have been added to the GP's job tasks such as the requirement to have an occupational medicine degree and some training experience to become a GP (Nicholson and Gratton, 2017). At the same time, GPs are now collaborating with NHS occupational therapists so that they can gain practical experience in dealing with mental health issues at workplaces.

According to Fonagy and Clark (2015), occupational therapists are the most skilled professionals in the health and social care sector. They share their experiences and skills with GPs across the UK so that the NHS's capability increases to handle the growing number of mental health issues at workplaces. The NHS is also implementing the NICE guidelines to promote workplace health programmes in every organisation, including SMEs and large organisations, so that employees with mental health symptoms and other issues can feel free to access mental health services.

The NHS has also increased the use of technology to improve mental health services, which can be an effective way to tackle mental health at workplaces. NICE has now evaluated five digital therapies dedicated to providing mental health service to employees, and two of those therapies have been recommended for treating employees' depression (NICE, 2020). Now employees can access digital treatments and other mental healthcare services using apps that make it more convenient.

2.9 Review of Workplace Mental Health Interventions

A multi-faceted support framework is needed to adequately address mental ill-health within and outside the work environment, as numerous factors are related to mental wellbeing. Organisations try to follow minimum health and safety standards to establish a legal framework in the workplace. But mental health promotion guidance development and intervention implementation in the workplace can be equally essential. More proof has recently built upon

organisational-level interventions that intend to create a healthy work environment and the right working conditions. The outcome from the evidence is mixed and examining intervention effectiveness from previous studies are challenging. Such interventions intend to prevent mental health issues but organisational restructuring and rapidly changing work environment often create difficulties in designing and implementing mental health interventions for the workplace.

2.9.1 Anti-stigma intervention

Most individuals undergoing mental health issues do not get assistance, and the stigma of mental health is believed to be the main hurdle to obtaining the right support. A review by Hanisch et al. (2016) demonstrates that anti-stigma interventions may be useful in altering workers' attitudes, understanding and actions towards individuals with mental issues in the workplace. Although public attempts have sent mixed outcomes, the advancement of customised strategies affecting the workplace may perhaps indicate a more promising route to tackling stigma (Szeto & Dobson, 2010). Therefore, although public anti-stigma forces aim for a larger part of the population, targeted interventions can be more beneficial and effective for working people (Hanisch et al., 2016). Involvement in anti-stigma intervention, in the capacity of employee development, could be made compulsory in a workplace setting, whereas public anti-stigma promotions require a population to participate voluntarily (Hanisch et al., 2016).

Some evidence suggests that there are positive influences of anti-stigma interventions on participants' general mental wellbeing (Quinn et al., 2011). The enhanced understanding of symptoms of mental health issues and support criteria may drive staff to look for assistance in advance. Some analysis found that mental health guidance improved participants' mental wellbeing by increasing knowledge and awareness about their own and others' mental health, enhancing self-perception and boosting coping skills (Hadlaczky et al., 2014). Besides generating a more sympathetic work atmosphere by reducing stigmatising discrimination, workplace anti-stigma interventions also lead to enhanced awareness and knowledge of mental health problems. Economic assessments of anti-stigma interventions are generally lacking, but initial evidence suggests a possible return on investment for organisations (Evans-lacko et al., 2013).

2.9.2 Stress prevention intervention

Workplace stress may cause a lot of harm to both employees and organisations. For employees, workplace stress has been associated with a range of damaging health outcomes including emotional burnout (Lee & Ashforth, 1996), psychological burden (Stansfeld & Candy, 2006), and musculoskeletal pain (Finestone et al., 2008). On the other hand, for organisations, work stress can lead to a decline in appropriate workplace behaviours, such as organisational commitment, as well as a rise in unwanted actions, such as long-term absence from work (Bakker et al., 2003) and staff turnover (Leong et al., 1996).

Ruotsalainen et al. (2015) found that there are mixed indications that relaxation interventions and cognitive behavioural therapy reduce anxiety and stress. Umanodan et al. (2014) suggested that a computer-based stress intervention programme was efficient at developing knowledge about stress management. Meanwhile, Lloyd et al. (2017) evaluated the influence of a stress management training intervention programme, finding declines in emotional exhaustion, psychological strain and depersonalisation. Their conclusions provide support for the persistent use of stress management training interventions to tackle health decline in employees. Although it is difficult to eradicate workplace stress, employers may attempt to reduce its effect through the establishment of stress management training.

2.9.3 Mindfulness and cognitive behavioural therapy intervention

To help employees overcome psychological distress, Mindfulness-based (Cullen, 2011) interventions have been recently introduced in workplaces. Brown & Ryan (2003) suggested that there can be different kinds of interventions, but they are all aimed to help the employees to be more mindful of their surroundings, increase awareness of their inner and outer worlds, to be more attentive about their thoughts, emotions and sensations. Grégoire and Lachance (2014) showed that there was a very positive change in the way employees approached the clients because of this mindfulness training. There was a significant increase in client satisfaction throughout the intervention, but this change's effect size was relatively small. Vonderlin et al. (2020) analysed the effects of mindfulness-based programmes and their findings indicated that with a decent effort, employees' productivity and job satisfaction improved and perceived stress and health issues reduced after finishing the programme.

A wide range of evidence supports that cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is successful in treating common psychological illness such as depression and anxiety (NICE, 2005). CBT is a psycho-social intervention that aims to improve the psychological health of participants. It concentrates on challenging and adjusting negative cognitive thoughts and behaviours, developing emotional control, and the enhancement of individual coping tactics that target solving ongoing issues. Reviews suggested that CBT may prove more beneficial in enhancing work-related outcomes when provided as return-to-work (RTW) intervention for staff on leave due to mental illness (Bruinvels et al., 2007). Studies have indicated that the occupational advantages are maybe even more significant if organisations adopt problem-focused therapy (PFT), a type of CBT that emphasises building practical problem-solving skills to facilitate change (Arends et al., 2012).

Gayed et al. (2019) suggested that CBT delivery modes, face-to-face as well as online, both help to improve managers' confidence in recognising mental health issues at the workplace and initiate conversations. But online delivery modes have low programme adherence and retention rates. Completion rate of CBT online delivery mode is quite similar to other internet-based interventions but because of low adherence rate overall effect of this programme was not as good as the face-to-face mode. At present, it appears that only when managers complete the online mental health training programme can improve their confidence level similar to in-person training. The retention rate of online training programmes can be improved by making them more engaging and interactive. Joyce et al. (2015) recommended that CBT can provide enhanced results for some specific work matters, such as an RTW programme or the development of employees' problem-solving skills.

2.9.4 Resilience and mental health training intervention

Robertson et al. (2015) argued that the evidence on resilience training programmes is unclear, although the influence on subjective wellbeing and mental health seemed to be one of the more prominent effects. The authors could not come to any conclusion about the most suitable format for this type of training. Meanwhile, Vanhove et al. (2015) found that coaching format training programmes supported by the classroom approach had the best results. Train-the-trainer and online training formats had the most underwhelming results. Martin et al. (2019) noticed some indication from studies that resilience training and face-to-face training may be more helpful than online training. Consequently, the authors suggested that attention be given to the potential

influencing role of interpersonal aspects in assisting the application of workplace wellbeing training interventions. Further investigation is required in this area, especially in light of the rapid increase of online interventions.

2.9.5 Gratitude and social connectedness interventions

Some researchers have chosen to emphasise social connectedness, given that feelings of interpersonal connectedness are fundamental to psychological inspiration and have been considered one of the core characteristics of wellbeing (Ryff & Singer, 1998). A large body of research has shown that thoughts of social association and related paradigms are crucial to mental health and wellbeing (Pinquart & Sörensen, 2000). Regardless of the recommended advantages of social connectedness, Kaplan et al. (2014) analysed the effectiveness of a social connectedness intervention action and found that the practice had no influence on any of the wellbeing outcomes measured in the study.

Furthermore, Sheldon and Lyubomirsky (2012) recommended that the greater the array of positive incidents experienced, the less likely people are to surrender to hedonistic adaptation. Therefore, different activities should decrease the likelihood of habituation and generate noticeable wellbeing improvements. Winslow et al. (2017) evaluated this idea by asking employees to swap between participating in the gratitude exercise and joining in behavioural strategies aimed at enhancing social ties at the workplace. They suspected that the social connectedness practice alone was not effective so far as it only covered a behavioural element. Therefore, there may be a need to implement an intervention that blends social connectedness with another practice that is more cognitive and reflective in nature, such as applying gratitude. In a more rigorous study, Winslow et al. (2017) found that neither intervention demonstrated a noticeable impact on affective wellbeing indicators.

2.9.6 MHFA intervention

Mental Health First Aid (MHFA) is a systematised educational programme established to tackle mental health issues in the general population by enhancing knowledge about mental health, improving behaviour and attitudes, and promoting supportive behaviours (Kitchener & Jorm, 2002). MHFA approaches are designed for the general public, using a similar instructional approach as in somatic first aid programmes. One of these approaches is a five-step action plan for mental health first aid. The action plan demonstrates how to help an

individual in mental health emergencies. The main goal of this course programme is to educate participants about common mental health conditions and available treatment options.

Hadlaczst et al. (2014) recommended that MHFA eventually boosts the mental health knowledge of the general population. It stimulates a series of cascading impacts, including progress in self-appreciation, and improved mental health-related literacy, therefore also reducing stigma. All these outcomes are believed to lead to enhanced coping skills and increased confidence to perform informed peer support. Significantly, outcomes suggest shifts in attitudes and knowledge and corrections in the attitude of those who complete the training. This is significant because although there is as yet inadequate evidence, MHFA appears to show a practical change in participants, who become more active in supporting those with mental health problems. Narayanasamy et al. (2018) argued that MHFA appears to be a helpful tool for increasing understanding and consciousness regarding mental health topics, but there is no evidence of whether it is the only or the most cost-effective means of achieving the outcome.

2.9.7 Factors influencing the success of intervention

More inclusive or multi characteristic interventions are likely to produce a more significant impact. Anger et al. (2015) suggested that interventions tended to report an impact on burnout if the interventions were more diverse, e.g. tackling organisational, material and working environment-related requirements simultaneously. The intervention user's engagement with and commitment to the process is an important factor. Müller et al. (2015) contended that when the participants are strongly committed to the intervention, they benefit more from the training. They also indicated that potential research should involve approaches that promote the managers' active engagement of reflection, motivation and behaviour change.

Stigma reduction interventions appear efficient in developing supportive behaviour, understandings and knowledge for employees with mental health issues (Martin et al., 2019). There is some suggestion that face-to-face resilience training intervention and coaching may have more impact than online training and courses. Vanhove et al. (2015) observed that training using face-to-face setups is better for training the trainer or online systems. Consequently, it is proposed that attention be given to the encouraging role of interactive factors while implementing wellbeing managers' training interventions for workplaces. The length of time of interventions on participants and their engagement is strongly associated with effects. The

intensity of the intervention's impact increases with the number of sessions (Theeboom et al., 2014). In this manner, an intervention programme that can be continuously conducted is necessary to support employees in the workplace.

Martin et al. (2019) examined recent systematic evidence reviews regarding effective workplace interventions and reported that system-wide multicomponent workplace approaches are impactful for the wellbeing of organisations. The Job Demands-Resources (JDR) model of Bakker and Demerouti involves harmful resource reduction and positive motivational mechanisms (Tetrick & Winslow 2015). It acknowledges several areas such as work and other non-work areas and several resources such as personal resources, job resources and family resources to identify employees' mental health. Another "integrated approach" to employee wellbeing claims that employee mental health interventions should protect the workplace from harm, create awareness, offer positive support and react to wellbeing issues as they are evidenced through work (LaMontagne et al., 2014).

In the literature on occupational health interventions, strong importance has been given to "business champions". Champions can take charge to organise project components, inspire employees, improve understanding and awareness, support adjustments to work practices, and reinforce the partnerships, associations and networks necessary to help modifications in organisational culture (Robinson et al., 2013). The six mental health standards for the workplace have all the components an organisation needs to champion workplace mental health. Interventions helpful to attain the six standards are also required to support employees in the workplace. Martin et al. (2019) argued that greater attention on industry partners and interdisciplinary study is essential to assist achievable, collaborative, multicomponent interventions.

2.9.8 Mental health interventions in SMEs

On the matter of necessary structures and resources, Cocker et al. (2012) explain that large organizations are likely to be more prepared when executing expensive mental health intervention programs. According to Dawkins et al. (2018), the use of expensive tools and services is comparatively restricted in SMEs. Only a few powerful researches are found on wellness interventions that focus on decreasing mental disorders, particularly among managers/owners and staff of SMEs (Martin et al., 2020). Researches show that intervention on mental wellbeing in SME workplace circumstances is obtainable and achievable, as they

are in larger organizations. However, major variations are found in the way these interventions must be designed and delivered to become accustomed to the particular SME setting (Hogg et al., 2021).

Significant variations could be found among large organizations and SMEs when it comes to the delivery of wellbeing interventions. McCoy et al. (2014) state that very few health campaign programmes are promoted in small organizations. Research revealed that financial aid and time were significant struggles in executing wellbeing programmes for small, medium or large organizations (Taylor et al., 2016). The authors also found that managers of small organizations were doubtful whether these wellness promotion movements fit the SME workplace environment. Since the intervention was obtained externally and not in the workplace in many cases, the researches concerning SME intervention assessment has the probability to reflect the realities of the challenges in executing such programmes in small organizations. (Saraf et al., 2019).

Yunus et al. (2018) discovered that the combination of technological aspects in larger organizations with the assistance of a counsellor decreased attrition. Meanwhile, the authors also identified that adherence and engagement was increased by influential technology like self-observation, collaboration through messaging and sharing mails, and a shorter intervention time frame (Yunus et al., 2018). In the attempt to enhance the rates of attrition, aspects like self-observation and collaboration with technology were suggested to be included in intervention concerning SMEs (Hogg et al., 2021).

Interventions like those that offered educational resources and those found in a group setting were easy to execute economically in a wide manner (Martin et al., 2020; Saraf et al., 2019; Schwatka et al., 2018). The inclusion of telephone assistance seemed to be advantageous (Martin et al., 2020; Schwatka et al., 2018). It may also be supported with the outcomes in small, medium, and large-sized organizations (Yunus et al., 2018) and could be a cost-effective solution to increase improvement, which demands further studies. Nevertheless, complete concentration on the effects of interventions on occupational outcomes was not found in the mental health intervention researches (Joyce et al., 2016). The reviews conducted by Martin et al. (2020) and Saraf et al. (2019) were the ones that comprised the expense of their interventions.

Moreover, the evaluation of economic effects related to direct or indirect expenses for individuals and organizations were not conducted by anyone. To comprehend the effect of face-to-face interventions, Hogg et al. (2021) suggest that these interventions have an adequate impact on presentism and absenteeism. In an SME setup, it can be difficult to manage cover for staff and face to face intervention can be a useful intervention approach to reduce absenteeism which also happens due to mental health issues.

The studies conducted by Martin et al. (2020) and Saraf et al. (2019) conclude that even if an advanced study is needed to decide the most successful strength, duration, and approach of projection, evidence states that signs of anxiety and depression in an SME environment could be reduced by CBT-related mediations. Future studies must concentrate on evaluating the impact of evidence-related CBT mental health interventions in the SME workplace. The results could be enhanced through studies on the cost-effective approach of projection, growing participation, and reducing attrition. To assist in determining the most economic interventions for SME organizations with fewer resources, a significant concentration on occupational and financial perspectives is needed

2.10 Suitable Options and Services for SMEs to deal with workplace mental health

Mental health care services must be available in SMEs so that employees' mental health and wellbeing can be ensured, whereby the understanding gap between employer and employees in this sector must be minimised. To make healthcare services available in SMEs, some effective options can be considered as suitable possibilities. Two key factors are emphasised most – the cost of the mental healthcare services and the process of accessing mental health services by an SME employee (Business in the Community, 2019).

2.10.1 Free/low-cost services:

In case of providing mental health services, the SME employers need to bear a cost, where that cost can be partial or fully paid for their employees. Research has recommended that low-cost mental health services are most suitable for an SME as it will encourage employers to take initiatives (Deloitte, 2017). However, Hall (2019) suggested that SMEs' mental health service should be free of cost, using technologies and collaboration with NHS and occupational therapists. Furthermore, Blake (2019) observed that SMEs in the UK have to spend more than £30 million each year due to their employees' mental health problems. Investment in

interventions for mental health services can compensate for the spending, thus generating more profits. As observed earlier, an investment of £1 on mental health interventions by the UK employers can generate a return of £4.20 (Deloitte, 2017). Therefore, SME employers, being the largest employers in the UK private sector, should be able to offer mental health services free of cost.

While searching for the cost of mental health services in workplaces, it is clear that the purchase values of these services are no less than the cost of any other specialised service. For an entry-level mental health workplace audit package, prices start at nearly £250 for a small organisation with up to 20 employees and a customised inspection package for a similar group starts at £400 (Brandly, 2019). It is understandable that if the same number of employees want to purchase an additional range of services, including direct supervision service, mental health first aid training service, policy and practice inscription service or awareness and mindfulness training services, the cost would be significantly higher.

Several studies have calculated the cost of workplace mental health intervention programmes. A study by Finners et al. (2017) suggests that operating Acceptance and Commitment Therapy, a branch within CBT that emphasises mindfulness and acceptance strategies, can cost approximately £210 per participant. The same study also suggests that operating a Workplace Dialogue Intervention that helps develop improvement in communication between employee and supervisor can cost nearly £260 per participant. A study by Boyd et al. (2007) suggests that the cost to the employer of individual Stress Management interventions to stimulate the mental health of staff varies from about £140 to £365 per participant. According to the UK Employee Assistance Professionals Association, the average cost of an EAP is approximately £15 per participant depending on what facilities are included (Mulchinock, 2019).

It is unquestionably cheaper for an SME organisation to train managers using awareness materials from the digital platform than specialist services when it comes to low-cost services. Research has recommended that low-cost mental health resources are most appropriate for SME mental health supervision (Deloitte, 2017). The costs of downloading awareness materials or guidance are very low or free. Most of the SME organisations that do not have specialist HR staff and are solely reliant on the managers can spend minimal expenses on training them with awareness materials or guidance. Costs of subscribing to an AI-based service like Woebot is also free, organisations only need to spend money on internet services.

Saraf et al. (2019) claim that most mental health interventions for SME workplaces focus on improving profits and sales at the firm level but overlook the question of human capital. SMEs can achieve a low-cost service experience by investing an insignificant amount of money and time to educate supervisors with awareness materials.

2.10.2 Easy access to mental health services:

The provision of easy access to mental health services by SME employers can be a better option to ensure mental health and wellbeing. In this regard, Mind (2011) highlighted how employers' key challenges are gaining their employees' trust so that they become proactive to report their mental health problems and access available health services. A community mental health survey found that mental health services must be convenient for those with any kind of mental health problems and that use of technology is the most useful factor to improve the convenience of the services (NICE, 2020). In this regard, it was recommended that a simple and free mobile app be developed to encourage employers to report and tackle their occupational health effectively, whereby the app must ensure confidentiality (NICE, 2020). This option can make the task easy for SME employers as this option is cost-effective and increases the accessibility of the available mental health services provided by employers and other healthcare professionals.

Mind (2013) emphasised collaboration with occupational therapists by employers to access specialist mental health services at the workplace. In this regard, Mind (2013) also mentioned that the NHS funded occupational therapy network can be most effective for workers to gain quick and free access to mental healthcare services.

2.11 Available Low Cost and Easy Access Options for SMEs

In OH as a whole in the UK, regulators have moved towards a more significant role for strategic coordination, stimulation and promotional activities (Wadsworth & Walters 2018). This applies to all aspects of wellbeing including mental health. In practice, this means using advice and guidance to increase reach and “buy-in” from owners and managers of SMEs and their employees. Regulatory agencies' focus has moved from inspection and enforcement to achieving compliance with public regulation and sociocultural influence. The spectrum of options that might underpin such compliance is outlined below.

Figure 2.5: Services Options Spectrum

Options across this spectrum exist, distinctively at each end and as hybrids in the centre. SMEs are a driver of innovation in a sector that is difficult to reach and engage with. Professional and costly options frequently used by larger organisations include professional OH and EAPs, or professionally delivered training in mental health literacy workshops or stress management. SMEs need low cost, easy access options that can ultimately motivate the sector to connect with mental health service development. An exploration and comparison of rationales and the effectiveness of a range of methods for delivering services are required. This can be done with reference to the six standards for employers to commit to improving workplace mental health cover.

2.11.1 Government-brokered mental health service organisations

Mental health services are provided to people with mental health problems throughout the UK through the NHS network, which is the only government-brokered mental health service providing organisation. The NHS hospitals, clinics and community healthcare service providing centres offer mental health services to people which can be accessed by employees, where direct referrals are used to access the services (Department of Health, 2000). The GPs

working under the NHS network play an important role in providing easy access to mental health services; they refer to specialised healthcare services such as counsellors, psychologists and occupational therapists to deal with mental health issues (Mental Health at Work, 2020). This mental healthcare service is a low-cost option from the UK Government. Under the NHS network, "Healthy Working Lives" is working in Scotland as a dedicated mental health service providing organisation; it offers information to employees regarding mental health, safety and wellbeing (Mental Health at Work, 2020). "Healthy Working Lives" is working collaboratively with the 14 local NHS boards in Scotland, and the services are free and confidential for employees working in all kind of workplaces (Mental Health at Work, 2020).

2.11.2 AI-related mental health service organisations

Due to the upsurge in smartphones and mobile Internet access, digital platforms based on the smartphone for mental health offer a distinctive prospect to increase the quality and convenience of psychological health self-care. According to Lee et al. (2018), a review directed by the World Health Organization showed that 15,000 apps related to mental health were utilised in 2015, of which 29% of apps address diagnosis, treatment, or assistance associated with mental health care. Ahmed et al. (2021) explain that the National Health Service in the United Kingdom is one of the public health associations that has identified that apps based on mental health are economic and accessible to analyse mental health treatment issues. However, while the amount of apps based on mental health seems prospective, only some are centred on evidence or have been meticulously tested.

In the UK, health and medical departments frequently utilise Artificial Intelligence. NHSX is one among those associations: deeply committed to AI while also maintaining collaboration with NHS. According to Joshi and Morley (2019), medical services in England mainly concentrate on youngsters and children in regards to challenges associated with psychological health. NHSX maintains the progressions in mental health services concerning prospective appointment planning with medical experts in charge and anticipating time and absence ratio, in accordance with which the major goal is to recognise the mental health care users' obstacles to develop optimal access to psychological health amenities (Joshi & Morley, 2019).

In the medical sector, NHSX's policy is to ensure that the services are digitised and linked to support integration (NHSX, 2021). According to the website, NHS plans to bring revolution in healthcare services through digital groundwork. NHS partners and numerous administrative units have partnered with NHSX to implement NHS Lab programmes based on Artificial Intelligence and provide financial aid to assist in projects that aim to utilise AI in identifying diseases and exploring numerous long-term disorders. A co-creative and collaborative environment are created by the AI Lab of NHS, which unites programs that focus on substantial restrictions to the enhancement and implementation of AI in healthcare systems (NHSX, 2021). Currently, the NHS website analyses and verifies 15 digital apps focusing on mental health (NHS UK, 2021). This demonstration reveals that the quality standards of NHS for accessibility, usability, safety, and healthcare effectiveness are met by these apps. Moreover, this gives the apps a strong empirical background.

Apps that profess to offer treatment in many forms should demonstrate proof for their procedures and remedial methodology, which has been excused in the past in numerous applications as a reason for inflicting harm to the clients (Ebert et al., 2015). A latest study showed that almost 293 mental health apps offered practical concepts concerning recovery and extensive healing mediation, particularly for depression and anxiety issues. Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT), Positive Psychology (POS), Mindfulness (MIND), and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) are the administrative methods included in similar researches (Ebert et al., 2015). Likewise, results show that CBT is the most significant concept for online mental health sessions since it has been a successful solution for reducing anxiety and stress levels for more than two decades (Jamie et al., 2020). Furthermore, researchers have revised chatbots for mental health disorders while pursuing standalone software programs. Moreover, chatbots were supported as a fundamental technology that could assist people with depression and anxiety issues.

A study conducted by Ahmed et al. (2021) in recent times revealed that chatbots have a favourable prospect in the conditions of depression and anxiety. Chatbots that highlight depression and anxiety hold the opportunity to enhance the aptitude of psychological health self-care by offering highly required economic aid to medical experts. The chatbot is a framework of AI built for various reasons, and managing mental health issues at the place of work is one of its major objectives. Chatbots are built to spread awareness of the significance of mental health among staff, inspire open discussion, and frequently observe staff mental

health (Withey, 2017). As such, Woebot is a chatbot driven by Artificial Intelligence, built particularly to offer mental assistance to individuals in their routine situations. To assist the staff in preventing work-associated depression and stress, the NHS encourages this AI in offices (Jesus, 2019).

The main outcome is that, over the next twenty years, modern technologies have the ability to transform mental healthcare systems (Forley and Woolard, 2018). Yet, they should be supplemented by organisational changes to be completely effective. As such, a more consistent self-recording of mental care and symptoms can be performed with smartphones. Forley and Woollard (2018) also suggest that connective with technology could offer helpful diagnostic and observational data and standalone self-help, a combination with conventional mental health mediations, or online peer assistance systems could be offered by digital therapies. These interventions are previously operational and are empirical. Furthermore, Ahmed et al. (2021) suggest that chatbots that utilise Natural Language Processing (NLP) and AI could include comparatively progressed computerised or partially computerised healing mechanisms in the future. It is evident that in the revolution of the psychological healthcare unit, technological progress alone with regulatory problems, political changes, organisational capability for transformation, system incentives, and the complexity of mental health settings will all be the deciding factor of development.

2.11.3 Self help or citizen-driven social innovation

In Scotland, Voices of Experience (VOX) is the only national mental health advocacy service-providing organisation which is run by the service users (Mental Health Foundation, 2020). From this perspective, VOX is a citizen-driven self-help organisation where service users with mental health problems help each other. It works as the representative voice of the people suffering from mental health problems (Mental Health Foundation, 2020). The main role of VOX is to represent the lived experiences of people with mental health problems and their demands so that the law and interventions related to mental health services can be shaped based on service users' demand and experiences (Mental Health Foundation, 2020).

2.12 How the Three Options Reflect Different Paradigms and Perspectives on Mental Health

There are significant theoretical and political aspects to the spectrum and the options associated with it. The practical context is service provision, for which there are essential theory and political aspects to the spectrum of options. The three options reflect the different paradigms and perspectives on mental health as a phenomenon.

2.12.1 Current state of government-brokered mental health service organisations

The Government facilitates businesses to improve workplace health by creating frameworks and guidance. McEnhill & Steadman (2015) have described what is involved in the frameworks. The Public Health Responsibility Deal promotes the significance of employers participating in the public health programme. The frameworks also include the Workplace Wellbeing Tool and this tool helps organisations calculate the cost to their business caused by ill-health. The Employer's Charter established guidelines for employers on sickness absence and return to work process and helps employers understand their responsibilities.

'Access to Work' is a government service (Department for Work and Pensions, 2020) intended to support employees with a constant health situation and disability, who are either about to begin a new job or already in employment. The service helps employees with physical and mental health problems financially and provides practical support. Access to Work Mental Health Support is confidential and free of cost service for employees delivered by Remploy (Department for Work and Pensions, 2020). Sinclair, Martin & Tyers (2012) suggests that small and micro-businesses underused the Remploy advice lines because of insufficient promotions, lack of awareness and scepticism on the advice provided.

The government-owned mental health service providing organisations focus on mental health and consider the physical health and wellbeing to ensure the overall health and wellbeing of people addressed in different research and studies. Mind (2013) stated that NHS mental health services are easier to access due to the broad coverage of the NHS network, which allows adequate mental health service interventions to be provided to meet mental health care needs. Deloitte (2020) further argued that a low-cost facility for people to access mental health services indicates that equality can be ensured among all social classes. From this perspective, SMEs can access NHS-funded mental health services for their employees as part of OH and wellbeing whereby the SME employers' difficulties in affording mental healthcare services are

mitigated. Another perspective addressed by McDaid (2017) concerns how the government provides mental health services that collaborate with healthcare professionals and other charity organisations to increase the capacity of the NHS and public health organisations to deal with mental health issues more effectively.

2.12.2 Current state of AI mental health management

The development and preference for AI and chatbots (Diamandis & Kotler 2020) can be seen as representing a paradigm of mental health as a biologically grounded phenomenon. This views mental health as a brain disease that can be fixed with solutions provided by science and professionals. Technologies, managed by large global organisations (Medical Futurist 2019), either pharmaceutical or information technology organisations, are the main agents shaping solutions. In effect, AI captures and replicates professional expertise without human (professional) mediation.

2.12.3 Current state of citizen-driven mental health service options

The paradigm and perspective of labelling people with defined mental health problems as different and deviant, and stigmatising them as themselves unhealthy and part of the problem. There is a long-standing movement to relabel mental health issues in less stigmatising ways. From this perspective, how people behave is less a sign of disease and more a form of reaction to troubling environments. Such behaviours may be alarming in a crisis but are not in themselves to be judged adversely or as signs of problems that need to be eradicated. Rather, “solutions” may be possible through refreshed positive relationships, compassion, care and love (Hunter, 2018). Options in this area include approaches involving close engagement with other people and healing communities among those with shared similar experiences (Icarus, 2019). Citizen-driven mental health organisations are created to support people with a healing attitude in groups.

2.13 How Low-Cost Options – Government-Brokered, AI-related and Citizen-Driven Social Innovation – can help SMEs to Achieve the Standards

Research shows that in terms of SMEs availing themselves of mental health services and interventions for their employees, low cost is the key consideration. According to Deloitte

(2017), SME employers' reluctance to adopt mental health service interventions is because of the cost and requirement of additional investment. Martin et al. (2020) also agreed that SMEs always look for cost-effective options, whereby the development of mental health intervention in workplaces is an additional investment.

2.13.1 Role of government-brokered mental health interventions in achieving mental health standards:

According to Goodrich et al. (2013), government healthcare organisations follow the standards of mental health services developed independently, which is compatible with the mental health legislation and regulations. From this perspective, it is easy for employers to use government service providers' mental health services such as the NHS. The NHS follows the guidelines of NICE, meaning that it automatically meets the standards of mental health services. Furthermore, Heal (2000) stated that when employers access mental health services provided by government-owned or managed service providers, they receive suggestions and recommendations to develop a healthy workplace considering both mental and physical health and wellbeing.

2.13.2 Role of AI-related mental health interventions in achieving mental health standards:

AI-related mental health interventions are developed following the needs of employers and employees and based on the workplace conditions, whereby the AI mental health interventions get approval from the authorities, who ensure compliance with existing mental health standards and legislation. Lovejoy et al. (2019) noted that AI-related mental health interventions are designed to provide preventive and treatment support to individuals with mental health problems. The availability of any AI mental health services or intervention can help an organisation meet the core standard of promoting and arranging adequate mental health support for employees in workplaces.

2.13.3 Role of citizen-driven mental health support in achieving mental health standards

Social support is essential for retaining good mental health. Generally, encouraging high quality social support can improve resilience to stress, reduce the effects of trauma-generated illnesses, create a shield against developing trauma-related disorders and decrease mortality and ill-health (Southwick, Vythilingam, and Charney, 2005). To reduce functional damage in

people with depression and enhance the likelihood of restoration, positive social support can play an essential role (Sayal et al., 2002).

The true nature of citizen-driven platform or social support group is to bring people to the same platform who have gone through or are going through the same kind of feelings and situations. Citizen-driven organisations allow individuals to reveal personal experiences and feelings, share coping approaches or first-hand knowledge regarding disorders or medications. There is a void between medical treatment and the need for emotional support and for a lot of people, a health-related support group can fill that void (Pomery et al., 2016). An individual may not get the much needed emotional support from his or her doctor. Sometimes friends and family are unable to understand the sufferer's struggle with mental health, but people with shared experience are able to relate and therefore may be of more help to fill the gap between their medical and emotional needs.

These social groups have the capability to enhance a sense of benevolence, empowerment and control by educating members about health, economic and social resources (Embuldeniya et al., 2013). Social support group members often have common feelings, similar experiences, everyday problems, worries, treatment decisions or medication side effects. Joining a help group may benefit members feel less judged and give them the power to talk and share their emotions openly and honestly. People with a common purpose and similar understanding can participate in a support group that allows them to be opened up about their feelings. One of the workplace mental health standards is to encourage open conversation about mental wellbeing. A social group's empathetic environment can help employees to be sufficiently confident to share their emotions with group members.

2.14 Summary of Literature Review

The literature review identified and examined an array of publications regarding workplace mental health services for SMEs. It began with the organisation's requirements which necessitate the development of mental health services for workplaces. This literature suggests that a lack of confidence, interaction and clear understanding between SME employers and employees makes it challenging to address SMEs' mental health issues. SME workplaces require low-cost options to support themselves with mental wellbeing. The current literature

on government programmes that support SMEs suggests that these programs are underused and not fully utilised by SMEs.

The research covered in the review concentrates on the changing world of work and how it influences the mental health conditions of the workplace. It provides a broad and solid foundation for this study. There is a selection of research in the areas of low-cost options, challenges and politics related to these options. It also supports the necessity for additional research that can provide a more current and focused assessment of the spectrum of low-cost mental health service options suitable for SMEs in reference to the six standards.

Chapter 3:

Methodology

Collecting data on a subject like the provision of mental health services presents several challenges. It involves careful consideration of the most appropriate, valid and reliable method of gathering data as well as the best analysis of the collected information to answer the research questions. Given this, a case study approach was essential, centred on describing and exploring the services provided by multiple agencies known to operate in the field in practice. Nine specific case organisations were identified as the service providers of SMEs. The standard procedures for the conduction of research were used to fulfil the needs of this research. The range of data sources included was open and diverse. These included accessing existing organisational case data sources on their services and their clients. A primary concern was choosing an appropriate interview technique for engaging with cases. Enabling access to case voices and compiling datasets was a major issue when providing answers to the research questions. While collecting, storing and analysing data, the University of West of Scotland's ethics procedure was strictly followed to ensure the acceptability of the research.

3.1 Research Questions

This research aims to establish, by comparative analysis, how innovations may provide low cost or free mental health services options to SMEs. The primary research question is as follows:

- Which innovations – a technology-based solution, government-brokered option or self-directed social citizen networks, are most likely to be most effective in reaching SME workforces?

3.2 Research Philosophy

Philosophy is generally adapted based on research, and the ideology of the research relies considerably upon various elements that have a significant part in research (Saunders et al., 2008). The methodology of research is strongly associated with the research ideology, which

could be called as the trust maintained by the researcher for the enhancement of the study. While performing this study, the researcher deliberated the ideological approach called interpretivism.

Interpretivism is a philosophical attitude that promotes the fact that people and their establishments are dissimilar to natural science because reality is created by producing meanings and human actions (Bell, Bayman & Harley, 2019). According to Saunders et al. (2016), an interpretivist attitude debates that public domains could not be calculated as similar to that of physical events since complexity requirements should also be considered and evaluated. An interpretivist study aims to establish unique and more affluent comprehensions and clarifications of people's realm. For instance, if this concept is interpreted for business management setup, this scenario would indicate exploring companies from the perspectives of diverse stakeholders.

Pragmatism, realism, and positivism are various research outlooks that are appropriate for the research ideology. In the realism and positivism ideology, the scholar continues to be impartial and dissociated from the outcomes. However, according to Bell, Bryman, and Harley (2018), in the interpretive methodology, the researcher's data analysis significantly impacts their outlook on the prospective contributions of the data. In an interpretive research ideology scenario, the researcher is considered and acknowledged as a tangible representation of the research development in which personal decision of the study is considered as a representation of the research; in consequence, the researcher's notions and individual ideology could not be detached from the research outcomes (Saunders et al., 2015).

Interpretive ideology relies on the attitude that a policy is essential that appreciates the dissimilarities between entities of natural sciences and common individuals and consequently necessitates the public researchers to understand the independent meaning of societal behaviours (Saunders et al., 2015). To carry out this scenario, researchers obtain access to the overall philosophy of individuals in order to understand their actions and social realm from their perspectives (Carson et al., 2001).

How data is gathered and why social actions occur is also focused on interpretivism. According to Bell, Bryman and Harley (2018), a usual tactic to gather data related to interpretivism utilizes an inductive approach with a basic model that permits researchers to shift from particular

reflection to extensive overview regarding philosophies. The data gathered from this basic model must generally follow a qualitative approach and interview is a universal practice used to gather such qualitative data.

This research was interested in how mental health service organizations manage and provide their mental health support to SMEs. The interpretivist stance was clear in the researchers' commitment to giving voice to service organizations' experiences in relation to SMEs mental health. Semi-structured interviews were planned to carry out with a purposive sample of nine mental health service organizations to know about their subjective experiences of providing six standards to SMEs. Unfortunately, because of the Covid-19 pandemic situation, the researcher could secure only one interview. The interviewee from See Me was asked to reflect on specific experiences in providing mental health services to SMEs. The researcher elicited the interviewee's organizational perspective in her own words and the analysis was undertaken to reflect the issues. Topics identified by research participants as being important in understanding the phenomenon of interest. This focus on the perspectives of research participant during data collection and analysis was the purpose of the interpretivist approach.

Because of the pandemic situation, most of the case-related data was gathered from secondary sources. In interpretivism ideology, another popular data gathering method is secondary data exploration. Four major outlooks to interpretivist study are discussed by Bryman (2008), where he considers hermeneutics as a significant outlook. In this outlook, the author's thoughts are expressed as text, and the interpreters or researchers should try to align themselves within the intellectual form or perception of the writer to restructure the envisioned meaning of the text. In this study, significance is placed in the comprehension and clarification of service associations' secondary data as well as the profound implications within each of them. Readers are encouraged by Higgs and Peterson (2005) to view hermeneutics as an inspiring and profoundly interpretive study outlook. Through this interpretive research approach researcher examined complex cases from multiple perspectives to produce rich theoretical and experiential interpretations of their service provisions

3.3 Research Approach (Inductive/Deductive)

The research approach is the process or method of how the research is conducted. This allows the development of the research in a more detailed and organised manner to develop the research objective as per requirements (Saunders et al., 2015). A researcher can either apply a

deductive or inductive style depending on how the analysis uses a theory (Saunders et al., 2015). The inductive approach is a method where the technical aspects of the research are developed first, and then the research objectives are developed based on the theoretical aspects of the research. This helps the development of the research in a more practical manner.

A deductive style is controlled and requires constructing a theory which is exposed to a careful examination. It is generally applied in natural disciplines where principles are employed to establish the foundation of rationalisations. Saunders et al. (2015) suggested that the deductive style lets the researcher predict the phenomenon and calculate its occurrence, thus allowing for the control of the study procedure. Therefore, in the deductive style of the research approach, the investigator has to anticipate the event's phenomena and its existence. The researcher assumes this from the collected data from different sources rather than live subjects. Researchers choose this style because of its capacity to clarify connecting relations among variables in a feasible way within the restrictions of the research (Babbie, 2015).

Turning to the inductive process of the research approach, this practice is based on more practical strategies and ensures results based on a pragmatic analysis (Gray, 2013). The inductive process allows the understanding of the research process in a more real-time setting and enables a development of the different aspects as per the requirements of the setting (Gill & Johnson, 2010). As Gray (2014) noted: "An inductive approach is more common in social sciences because it moves away from the cause-effect link towards the more accommodating social world interpretation from the human perspective". Moreover, deductive approaches are more inflexible in style and hence do not permit alternate justifications of the study phenomenon.

In this research, the study topic was more of a social issue than a theory-oriented subject. The research topic was based on incorporating the different mental health services in SMEs, which requires an inductive process of research. An inductive approach is generally associated with interpretive research that allowed the appropriate understanding and evaluation of the service organisations based on the needs of the research questions and objectives as per the views of the researcher. As the topic is more connected to analysing the different services of mental health care options in workplaces, a societal approach and more practical data collection for precise and appropriate results was required.

In the inductive approach, the researcher applies observations and thoughts to build a concept or illustrate an image of the phenomenon (Lodico et al., 2010). One of the weaknesses found in the inductive approach is the possibility of bias from the researcher's observations. To overcome this limitation, data cleaning, a close reading of data, creation of categories, overlapping codings, continuous revision and refinement of categories and cross-case study were performed throughout the process.

3.4 Research Strategy, Choices and Time Horizon

The research process is one of the most essential parts of organised research and it has multiple layers that ensure successful and established research (Saunders et al., 2015). Research processes are divided and segmented into three noteworthy sub-branches, ensuring a useful format for the research: the research strategy, choices of the research and the time horizon of the research. Completing these steps ensures the research objectives can be addressed.

The rationale of the study can either be exploratory, explanatory or descriptive. However, Saunders et al. (2009) explained that, just like the research questions, the research rationale can be both descriptive and explanatory. As Robson (2011) observed: "Exploratory studies deal with 'what is happening', seeking new insights, asking questions, and assessing the research phenomena in a new light". Explanatory studies concentrate on forming a causal relationship between variables and were not appropriate for this research because its objective is not to find connections among variables. Meanwhile, "descriptive studies are described as those that portray the precise profile of an event, person or situation" (Robson, 2011). This study style requires the researcher to have explicit knowledge of the study phenomenon and this style was also not applicable to this study.

In this study, exploratory studies were used to assess the provision of the mental health six standards for SMEs. The research also attempts to seek new knowledge regarding service organisations and service advantages and disadvantages and to assess the research phenomena from a new perspective.

3.4.1 Research strategy

The organised outline of the progress of the complete study method, which ensures the needs of research are met, is called a research strategy (Saunders et al., 2015). There are seven

segmented processes of research strategies which are applicable for the development of a research topic. These are archival research, experiment, grounded theory, case study, survey, action-research and ethnography. Starting with experiments, these are usually built for theory-based topics and are used in cases where the data is limited, new ideas have to be incorporated for the development of the subject, and results are expected for the phenomenon in different case scenarios (Bryman & Bell, 2015). In some cases, surveys can be considered a suitable method of collecting information from different sources in different ways to ensure a good research result (Zikmund et al., 2012). However, the issue with a survey process is that the practice limits the researcher to the questions, and thus other subsequent questions cannot be asked freely. Ethnography and grounded theory are also excluded as possible research strategies for this study because these approaches focus more on context.

Accordingly, this study employed a case study design. As Robson (2011) explained, “Case study is defined as a research strategy for undertaking empirical research of a specific phenomenon in its real-life context”. Yin (2013) further argued that case study strategies are best suited for either explanatory or exploratory studies. The exploratory research strategy was carefully chosen for this study because the research purpose is subjective in nature.

3.4.2 Research choices and Time horizon

Research choices are categorized as mixed-method, multi-method and mono-method (Saunders et al., 2009). Multi-methods are applied when the researcher blends two or more data collection techniques and assess from the same pattern, whereas mono-methods are utilized where research uses one data-collecting practice that resembles the assessment. These techniques can be either quantitative (e.g. experiment data and questionnaires) or qualitative (e.g. interviews and focus group) (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). Meanwhile, mixed-methods mainly involve the mixture of quantitative and qualitative data gathering systems (e.g. questionnaires and interviews) performed either in parallel or in sequence (Saunders et al., 2009).

At the beginning of this study, mixed-method was selected because the study required both primary data from the interviews of case organisations and surveys from SME employees to capture their attitudes regarding AI options. Unfortunately, the researcher only managed to conduct one interview with a case organisation due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Most of the data were collected using mono-method. In this case, secondary data from public sources were used to conduct this research. In this research, the interview and secondary data collection

strategies were cross-sectional because the respondent from the organisation See Me was questioned several times with follow-ups and secondary data were examined within a specific time period.

3.5 Research Design

In this research, a case study research design was used, which is generally qualitative in nature. Identifying qualitative research's characteristics and objectives is essential to justify the case study design (Baskarada, 2014). The qualitative approach seeks to know about an environment in its proper form rather than alter it (Merriam, 2009; Yin, 2009). This thesis aimed to assemble relative and actual understanding involving practices that service organisations provide for SMEs to support their mental wellbeing. Compared to a quantitative approach, the qualitative study delivers a more complete image of a context by collecting and covering in-depth explanatory data without generalisation (Merriam, 2009; Sutter, 2006). Researcher in this qualitative research responded to the question of "how" services were delivering in a specific context and did not attempt to generalise results for overall populations.

According to Yazan (2015), a case study is one of the approaches commonly utilised in qualitative research. A qualitative case study is a study approach that assists in the investigation of a scenario within a specific framework with the use of numerous data sources. Moreover, it commences the investigation through different perspectives to demonstrate various aspects of the scenario (Baxter & Jack, 2008). According to Beasley and Kaarbo (1999), a real-time scenario in a case study is discovered within its naturally transpiring setting while counting that the setting would establish a change. This study focused on investing quality time in gathering in-depth data from secondary sources to understand reality better. Moreover, due to the study's thorough and descriptive nature, qualitative findings could be obtained from case narratives.

Common constraint issues of qualitative case study research approaches (e.g. potential bias, difficulties in interpreting all the data) (Queirós et al., 2017) were solved through a close reading of data, the formation of codes, overlapping codings, continuous revision and refinement of categories and cross-case analysis. The purpose of case studies is to identify the procedures included in the co-generation of value. Hence, instead of theory testing, this is more similar to theory creation research. Neither hypothesis nor preposition was included in the commencing stage of this case. The first step in this case study protocol was designing the main question

and sub-questions. After designing questions, multiple low-cost/free mental health service organisations were identified to gather information about their service provisions.

Following the interpretive stance, the practical material focused on the experiences of participant, which helped in explaining the service options of the case organisation See Me. For other cases and See Me, researcher had to apply the hermeneutics interpretivist approach. Literature of mental health six standards was used while locating materials for research cases. The main tools to collect resource material were semi-structured interviews (see Appendix- I), augmented by interaction with the participant, documents including project reports, emails and the case organisation's official website. When locating and collecting materials, key words from six standards for SMEs were considered as leading clues. Interviewed materials and collected data from email, reports and websites were initially managed and stored in excel files (see Appendix-V).

In these studies, coding and theme creation is used since it is the most acknowledged and operated evaluation method for qualitative case study evidence, and text is used for its evaluation. As such, the logical process of interpretation began with the preliminary transcription of the interview's audio recording in this study. Secondary resources located from reports, articles and websites (see Appendix-IV) were collected and transcribed to understand thoroughly about service provisions of all the cases. Initial transcriptions of the interview and secondary data were then followed by cross-checking with note which were created at data location level. The point of cross-examining the written interviews and secondary sources with written observations was to identify if any information was misplaced while transcribing. Establishing communication with research contributors is a significant aspect for idea creation and concept analysis, and this practice also permits contributors to offer recommendations about futuristic enhancement and feedback that could fortify the outcomes of this research.

The process of cross-examination is followed by the coding of secondary observations and transcribed interview, which helps in the development of concepts. On grounds of similarities and variations, a few major codes from all the developed codes were modified into concepts, while less significant codes were incorporated into the major codes. Next, these concepts were combined in order to generate categories. The outcomes of secondary sources, documents, observation notes, interview transcriptions and these categories were construed and portioned together to gain an extensive outlook on the theme.

The objective of interpretation was to search for links between theories and generate a category that included numerous theories. The research prudently observed several patterns through which categories were established, reorganised, and confirmed, along with the assistance of literature reviews. Validity was attained via triangulation rather than via the influence of irrelevant information. This research was designed to understand the genuine facts about services provided by cases and case organisations' actual capacity to deliver six standards. To do so, proper research strategy and protocol were followed.

3.5.1 Case study design

Yin (2009) suggests that case studies are usually qualitative as they stress the significance of circumstance in deciding truths. Merriam (2009) described the case study as an “in-depth analysis of a bounded system”. A case could be an organisation, a single programme, a group of people, a person or a classroom. To be eligible as a case, a limited number of individuals or groups should engage within the procedure. The objective of the case study in this research was to investigate in-depth the significant aspects of mental health service organisations and their process of delivering services to SMEs.

A case study is usually chosen when exploring the present practice. Merriam (2009) argued that both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods can be included in a case study approach; however, participant observation and interviews are the most generally used practices in a case study. In this research, case organisations' interests were observed through secondary sources to recognise the status of provisions; thus, the case descriptions included current practices. Merriam (2009) also concluded that, like other qualitative research forms, a case study pursues knowledge and meaning of social phenomena. In this study, the researcher was the principal instrument of data compilation, and the sole purpose of the investigation was to collect data regarding mental health service provisions and options for SMEs.

There are key features connected to the development of the case study: particularistic, descriptive and heuristic (Merriam, 2009). Merriam (2009) clarified that a case study concentrates on a unique phenomenon, person, organisation or event by particularistic feature. The main objective is not to match general conditions but to achieve an intense knowledge of a unique situation. The descriptive feature means that a case study is an in-depth, rich narrative of the investigation approach. The result is generally considered explanatory, holistic and

innovative. Finally, the heuristic feature means that case studies “illuminate the readers’ understanding of the phenomenon under study” (Merriam, 2009). The heuristic feature can create revelation, enlightenment or validation regarding what has been previously identified about a concept.

Case studies can concentrate on single or multiple spots (Merriam, 2009; Yin, 2009). A single site study design is appropriate for cases that are representative or typical, extreme or unique, biographical, pilot or longitudinal. Single case studies lack generalisability and are often criticised for this. A multiple-site case study is described as a collective case study. A multiple-site case study involves gathering and examining data from multiple experiences. The cases within a multiple case study contribute to some common feature or are categorically bound together (Yin, 2009). Multiple site studies were preferable in this study because the data assembled were believed to be more stereotypical to the entire context; the research aimed to understand the phenomenon within a particular context of SME workplaces’ mental health.

3.5.2 Case study approaches

As Yin (2009) noted, “The research question can provide an important clue regarding the appropriate research method to be used”. Therefore, the approaches of this research investigation must be based on the study objective to assess the practices of service organisations regarding the mental health approaches of SMEs. In this case, the research objective was understanding the different mental health service options utilised by SMEs. Therefore, to understand and answer the research objective and research question, an in-depth evaluation of the cases was required. According to Yin (2009), this involves asking a “how” or “why” question about a contemporary set of events over which the investigator has little or no control. In this case, answers for “how” and “why” questions linked with mental health service options were required, and for that, a case study style was more appropriate than other study approaches. In addition, the research questions were exploratory as they sought to investigate service organisations’ role in managing mental health for SMEs. Moreover, the case study design emphasised the significance of context, and thus, the study recognised the inability to extract case organisations from their respective contexts.

3.5.3 Multiple-case studies

In a single case study, the researcher runs an in-depth examination on one case, whereas in multiple-case study design, more than one case analysis is done to understand the broader

aspects of a phenomenon. Criticism of case study approach is its dependency on a single case investigation, making it difficult to achieve a generalising outcome (Tellis, 1997). Yin (2009) suggested that multiple case study data are more captivating than data from single-case study designs because there is the likelihood of direct replication, resulting in compelling analytical outcomes. Therefore, in this research, the unique experiences of organisations were recognised. Thus, diversity regarding organisations' support, experiences, service principles, level of support training, etc. offered a broader synthesis of case organisations' experiences in SME contexts. In this way, using multiple cases increases both reliability and validity by providing a variety of experiences (Merriam, 2009; Yin, 2009). Multiple cases of organisations operating with unique client bases allowed comparisons among case organisations' experiences under various requirements. Furthermore, cross-case analysis was conducted to provide a synthesis of the understanding gathered from selected service organisations.

3.5.4 Sample and population

One of the most common sampling methods in qualitative research is nonprobability sampling. Nonprobability sampling does not depend on randomisation (Merriam, 2009). Both the research questions and the study's purpose mean that nonprobability sampling was the preferred option of this study. Cases were chosen for this research that involved low-cost or free mental health services being provided to SMEs. Honigmann (1982) recommended nonprobability sampling as "logical to solve qualitative problems, such as discovering what occurs, the implications of what occurs, and the relationships linking occurrences." This research intended to gather knowledge about the advantages and the disadvantages of different low-cost or free mental health service options in Scotland. Given this, the nonprobability sampling method was the most reasonable sampling method for selecting cases.

The study involved what Patton (2002) labels purposeful sampling, which is sampling "based on the assumption that the investigator wants to discover, understand, and gain insight and therefore must select a sample from which the most can be learned" (Merriam, 2009). The investigation demanded information-rich cases to study in-depth, which again pointed to purposeful sampling as the best type. Preissle and LeCompte (1991) recommended this practice as "criterion-based selection". They proposed creating a list of characteristics related to the purpose of the study. A list of characteristics was followed in this study to detect information-rich, low-cost mental health service organisations.

While filtering the nine sample cases for SME mental health in Scotland, a few criteria were thoroughly assessed, such as organisations that provide support and services for workplace mental well-being and organisations working towards bettering the mental well-being of the employed SME workforce in Scotland. Also, mental health service organizations from different spectrums, from AI-based to government-brokered to social innovation-based, were essential in selecting case organisations. The research literature found that organisations in different spectrums incorporate different characteristics in providing well-being services to SMEs. Therefore, only low cost or free service organisations in this spectrum were taken into account for this research.

3.5.5 Case geographic criteria

Scotland is undergoing a challenging period of transformation in general with other parts of the United Kingdom. Even before the Brexit decision, Scotland encountered substantial challenges. Research by the Fraser of Allander Institute (2016) recommends that withdrawal from the EU single market will only intensify a situation which was already worsening. Scotland's economy was expanding, and its labour market was vibrant – and, for a time, it was outperforming the rest of the UK. Now unemployment is rising, employment is falling and, most importantly, immobility is on the rise as more workers take back from the job market (Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development [CIPD], 2017)

Scotland's productivity performance is lower than the rest of the UK, which is low by international standards. As a CIPD report indicated, Scotland could pay itself nearly £4,000 per annum more if productivity reached the OECD average (CIPD, 2017). Productivity is, of course, the consequence of many different individual and organisational choices and actions. However, well-being and productivity are intertwined, as poor wellbeing leads to low productivity.

The brute arithmetic of sickness absence and lost production, the effect of presentism and stress, and the hidden pressure of worry and anxiety over personal finance issues are indirectly reducing job satisfaction, impacting the productivity and increasing costs to society. Looking after people at work pays real dividends. SMEs account for 99.3% of all private sector businesses in Scotland (The Scottish Government, 2018). SMEs dominate the Scottish business population, so how these organisations survive, regulate and adjust to mental health issues will have an immense impact on Scotland's future societal and economic prosperity. This study

therefore attempted to contribute to mental health best practices by analysing the right options in terms of cost and benefit for SMEs in Scotland.

3.5.6 Case selection criteria

Within the population of providing services for the mental health and wellbeing of SME staff, the following criteria were used to identify specific cases:

- Organisations providing support and services for mental wellbeing
- Organisations working towards the betterment of the mental wellbeing of the employed SME workforce
- Organisations who are government-brokered, citizen-driven social innovation or technology-based and who share resources to organisations and their leaders for SMEs' workplace mental health support.

3.6 Data Collection

Yin (2009) maintained that a researcher should follow three principles while accumulating case study research data. First, multiple sources of evidence should be used to allow the researcher to attain a wider range of performance or historical issues. In this study, tracing a network of data enhanced the study's authenticity and helped analyse multiple sources of data. Second, Yin (2009) indicated that a formal and presentable case study database should be created to improve its reliability. Data were collected in a systematic manner so that they could be easily presented to an external reader. Third, a chain of evidence should be maintained by the case study researcher to enhance the consistency of outcome

Data were collected about each case organisation. The practice of delivering services was investigated separately for each case. The original plan for data collection was to interview organisations to collect their experiences regarding service provision. An interview with one organisation was secured. Organisations were contacted through face to face meetings, email and voice calls. Mairead Rowan, a workplace officer from See Me, came forward to participate in the interview and represented See Me in this research. The rest of the information for cases were collected from secondary sources due to the COVID-19 pandemic. A formal and presentable case template was created with themes to organise data to understand what

organisations are doing to manage the six standards and their motivation behind their approach. In the initial case development stage, data were collected and kept under different subordinate themes to maintain a chain of evidence.

3.6.1 Documents

In the beginning, the aim was to collect primary data through interview technique. After gaining permission from the organisation to conduct the study at their respective site with informed consent, the case participant was contacted through email to arrange a face-to-face interview. Subsequently, relevant documents were solicited and gathered from each participant such as organisation details, working experience in fulfilling the six standards, level of involvement of SMEs, and the number of SMEs involved with the organisation for their mental health support.

Data collection involved face-to-face interviews with service organisations to gain insight into the organisations' experiences and level of involvement. In this case, the participant's documents were a good source for the researcher to understand the case organisation's different instances and occurrences in supporting the SMEs. Related documents and email communication with the organisation supplied a richer understanding of the context in which they work and their experiences with SMEs. Unfortunately, only one interview was able to be conducted due to the pandemic.

3.6.2 Interviews

According to Merriam (2009), interviews are the best technique to conduct rigorous case study research. At the primary data collection stage, the researcher used the interview method over the phone to collect primary data about the cases. Patton (2002) suggests that interview techniques are commonly applied to establish what "is in and on someone else's mind...We cannot observe feelings, thoughts and intentions and purpose while interviewing, then, is to allow us to enter into the other person's perspective". At the time of the face-to-face interviews, questions were asked to learn about organisations' perspective regarding mental health provisions for SMEs.

Roulston (2010) suggested approaches for conducting a "good interview". One such suggestion is to build guidelines and research objective-related open-ended questions, and ask the participant these at the start of the interview. Distraction and intrusion can make both the interviewer and interviewee uncomfortable, and to avoid this, Roulston advised selecting a

place with less interference. In a quiet environment, the researcher began interviewing the participant with easy background questions. The researcher intended to collect background information about the organisation and how they work to identify participants relationships with the case and the research.

When articulating interview questions, Roulston (2010) noted that a good question is “short, concise, and open-ended”. In the case of the current research, the interview questionnaire was short and precise and was shared previously with the participant. Merriam (2009) noted that a semi-structured interview can be suitable for describing experiences distinctively. Questions emerged from participants responses, and the participant was comfortable enough to answer these while communicating with the researcher.

3.6.3 Secondary data collection

Using secondary data which is public information and collected by others presents several issues for the research. While collecting secondary data, researchers should ensure that the source of data is authentic and that retrieved data from the sources are relevant to the research problem (Hox & Boeije, 2005). Hox and Boeije (2005) also advised that researchers should guarantee that data quality meets the research requirements and the methodological criteria are of good scientific practice. According to Walters (2009), subjective data collected and interpreted during qualitative research are often influenced by the social, cultural and political situation at the time of data collection. The researcher should be careful while analysing historic data. They should examine and compare the social, cultural and political differences in both time periods before coming to any conclusion.

The primary sources of information for cases were the official websites and other online public platforms. This case study research involved the collection of subjective data which were available mostly on organisations’ websites. Case organisations’ websites functioned as a virtual treasure house of information, providing detail regarding service offerings, industries served, geographic presence, organisational structure, service methods and innovations. Most importantly, data were collected, reanalysed and interpreted to explore the research question. Only information relevant to answer the research problem was collected from the case organisations’ public account.

3.7 Data Management

A data management strategy is essential to keep data classified and crucial for the researcher to easily retrieve the data at the time of report writing and analysis (Merriam, 2009). Each piece of data must be identified with the data source. Data should be managed in such a manner that the researcher can locate the case data and its source at any point of time of thesis writing. While managing the data, the initials of organisations were applied to detect cases. An electronic database was created to keep all the case study data file under one folder.

An Excel file and an electronic folder were used to manage data under the six standard mental health themes and to develop cases. Cross-case memos play an essential role in the case study research approach; these are the researcher's notes written while analysing data. A cross-case memo folder was also created to keep research analysis notes organised. Yin (2009) suggested that a comprehensive narrative account should be maintained for each case in the written report, and the researcher should include direct quotes to back data interpretation. In this study, the case study database and case development Excel sheet helped create such narratives to perform data analysis. In each case folder, subfolders were maintained and labelled under memos, interviews and documents to keep different data types separated from each other. The database was password-protected, virus protected and kept in a personal computer.

3.8 Data Analysis

According to Merriam (2009), data analysis is the process of making sense of the data. The research analysis process included the mixture, classifying, clarifying and interpreting of data gathered from emails, interviews and participants' documents. Data compilation and analysis are usually a coinciding activity in qualitative research (Merriam, 2009). Accordingly, data collection and data analysis activities were performed in parallel. In the consequent data collection phase, this process influenced the type of data collected. The data analysis procedure worked as a way of establishing the responses to the research questions.

Merriam (2009) stated that all qualitative data assessment is principally comparative and inductive. The appropriate study analysis derives heavily from the constant comparison of research data (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Glaser and Strauss applied the continuous comparative technique to build grounded theory. But Merriam (2009) insisted that the constant comparative

method is an assessment technique that is certainly recognized and commonly used in qualitative research, including case study approaches. In this study, the continuous comparison of data allowed researcher to generate and modify categories by constantly linking themes and patterns evolved from the data. The continual comparison of patterns and topics between and within cases ultimately guided researcher towards a richer interpretation of cases' service practices.

According to Merriam (2009), in the primary phase of data analysis, data needed to be broken into smaller segments so that every component can be compared with similar components. Eventually, to illustrate the research questions' answers, all significant units must be carried back together. The researcher divided a single interview or document into numerous parts. Sections of data were then contrasted to related data fragments in consequent documents and interviews.

Merriam (2009) identified categories as "conceptual elements' that 'cover' or span many specific examples of the category". In Particular, a category is a conceptual structure developed from the data capturing a persistent pattern that permeates the data. During the exploration procedure, initial categories turned into subcategories or combined into a more comprehensive category. Designing categories was inductive because the researcher began with data collection, divided data into sections, grouped parallel sections, and named the group. Merriam (2009) explains saturation occurs when "no new information, insights, or understandings [were] forthcoming". Categories formed in the course of data analysis met the standards recommended by Merriam (2009) :

- as responsive to the data as possible by illustrating the kind of the data involved,
- comprehensive enough to incorporate all applicable data,
- reactive to the research questions through the association of categories with the research purpose, and
- mutually exclusive in that an appropriate unit of data could be positioned in only one category.

All the options were evaluated with respect to the core standards for services. The analysis was conducted using a Likert scale (Figure 1) which emerges from collective responses to a set of items. Responses are scored along a scale (Likert, 1932) as "best for", "good for" and "not good for".

At the analysis stage, already transcribed, coded, categorised, and interpreted case research materials were compared to reveal cross-case patterns. This step helped in establishing a framework for the concept under study. The outcome of cross-case patterns of interpretation was presented in the form of Likert scale. At this step, the Likert scale was used comparatively across all the case studies. Before presenting cross-case results in the Likert scale, an extensive study was performed to acknowledge each standard's distinct characteristics from the six mental health standards. Interpreted data of case studies were taken into consideration and literature on six standards, SME mental health interventions, organisational setup of SMEs were used to move back and forth for conducting Likert scale analysis.

Cross case outcomes were calculated along the Likert scale as "best for", "good for" and "not good for". A case organisation scored "best for" when it qualified for most of the characteristics of a particular mental health standard. On the other hand, a case organisation scored "good for" when it qualified for not most but essential characteristics of a particular standard. And a case organisation scored "not good for" when it qualified for few or none of the characteristics of a mental health standard. The researcher aimed to avoid influencing the outcome by acknowledging that an environment can be controlled only by investigating it. Validity was attained via triangulation rather than via the influence of irrelevant information.

3.8.1 Cross-case synthesis

Yin (2009) recommended that there should be a determined and prearranged analytical strategy in researchers' minds before case study data is analysed; such strategy directs the researcher in constructing each case's story by producing analytical outcome, considering the data impartially and ruling out unsuitable explanations. Here, case descriptions were developed simultaneously, which presented a complete narrative account of each case. Contextual aspects were comprehensively illustrated in each case narrative as they were inseparably connected to the practices. Case organisations are all working towards supporting SMEs' mental health. The intention of all the organisations studied was to provide health and wellbeing support to working populations. Likewise, the rival explanations were examined during the course of the analysis procedure by constantly linking data alongside the themes and categories that emerged.

Yin (2009) listed five analytic techniques typically utilised in case study research once an analytic strategy is chosen: explanation building, pattern matching, logic models, timeseries

analysis and cross-case synthesis. The cross-case synthesis analytical technique was chosen here to detect results as an exploratory multiple-case study was performed to ensure a feasible analysis of service options. In this cross-case synthesis, each case is handled as an independent and distinct study, and the judgments and rulings are then aggregated across the separate cases (Yin, 2009).

All the case organisations were distinctive in their own way in providing mental health support and services. Thus, each distinctive case was investigated to establish responses to the study question. In other words, individual case analyses were used to compare answers to research questions or the categories, within and across each case. Finally, a Likert scale was used to demonstrate the allocation of the findings.

3.9 Limitations

In the qualitative case study, the researcher needs to gather thick, rich data through various sources, making the research process time consuming compared to quantitative research (Merriam, 2009; Yin, 2009). Similarly, it depends to a large extent on participants' support, commitment and cooperation across a large span of time. It was also difficult to establish, empirically, to what extent selected cases were similar or different to other such organisations all over Scotland. Furthermore, because the sample was small, distinctive and predominantly non-numerical, it was hard to determine the probability that data were representative of some larger population. Finally, in some cases, the complexity and difficulty in completing various forms and additional training was too high to gather complete results from an interview with one person from a single organisation. Because of the Covid 19 pandemic issue, the researcher had to rely on secondary data analysis for this research but combined analysis of primary and secondary data would have provided more precise outcomes.

3.10 Ethical Assurances

Respect for human dignity is the basic ethical concept for core research ethics. For ethical assurance, the researcher complied with several moral principles and values while conducting the interview. The University of West of Scotland's (2020) Ethics Committee suggests that any

research that involves human beings or any data or records of people should be conducted following these moral principles.

3.10.1 Autonomy, veracity and informed consent

One of the most important factors of autonomy is free and informed consent. Informed consent or approval has three components :

- The participant must be provided with thorough, precise and relevant information by the researcher. In this study, the researcher outlined the participant information sheet with honesty and care and explained all the relevant aspects of the research that the participant needed to know to make their decision to consent. There was no influence or compulsion involved, such as offering a reward or forcing to consent.
- It is crucial to make sure that tentative participants understand all the procedures and understand the research type before getting involved in the research. In this research, the potential interviewee was given enough time and information before deciding to participate in the research. Not taking informed consent in this manner would have breached the right to autonomy.
- An auditable record of consent is necessary to protect the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) rights of associated parties. UWS research ethics were followed to avoid the tendency to exaggerate the benefits and underestimate the risks.

3.10.2 Privacy and confidentiality

Privacy and confidentiality are fundamental human rights. In this research, only one participant was interviewed. The participant represented the government-brokered organisation See Me and their identity was not disclosed anywhere in this study. The researcher also explained to the interviewee how the collected data would be stored and secured, who would have access to the data and how long it would be stored. The secondary case-related data were collected from the public platform. The access, management and distribution of data were also safeguarded under the Data Protection Act 13 and the GDPR.

3.10.3 Benefits and harms

In the review of the process, the balance between benefits and risks was ensured. In this context, the risk was defined as potential harm, discomfort or stress generated by the research. Reasonable adjustments were made in terms of time and place to facilitate the interviewee. In

some circumstances, a comprehensive literature review was done to guarantee the research was unique and that the methods were accurate.

3.11 Summary of Methodology Chapter

This chapter described the research design and defended the reason for choosing the case study method. As the study aims to explore the experiences of organisations associated with mental health service and supporting SMEs mental health, it was appropriate to choose an interpretive, inductive, multiple-case study method to investigate these organisations' experiences with SMEs. As a data analysis strategy, cross-case synthesis was applied to compare the experiences of case organisations. In this participant-centred approach, the fundamental research ethics of UWS were considered during ethical assurance.

Chapter 4:

Findings

This chapter summarises the findings from the research into the case narratives. In total, nine cases, from AI platforms through to government-brokered services and citizen-driven options, were analysed for this study. All case organisations provide support and services for mental health to SMEs. In developing the cases, the method required in-depth interviews to be conducted, data to be collected from secondary sources, and themes identified related to mental health service standards. The case development process helped to create narratives of each of the cases in sections. In the case-building stage, most of the data were collected from secondary sources due to the pandemic. These data were collected under three main categories to classify SMEs' mental health services' current establishment. The case development stage results led the researcher to create narratives of each of the cases that helped produce an assessment of SME mental health provision.

Each of the nine cases was investigated to establish the workplace mental health service condition of these organisations. This chapter begins with an overview of the categories under which the cases were developed, including factors related to mental health standards and the service organisation's perspective of workplace mental health. Following the overview of the service organisations, the findings are presented and summarised using a case narrative process.

4.1 Overview of Themes

The study narrated the provision of nine cases engaged in mental health services for workplaces. All the cases for innovating were identified with reference to a spectrum of options and data were organised under the themes of the six standards. The research also aimed to explore experiences that the service organisation had with respect to themes emerging from The Mental Health Foundation recent report on the Scottish context (Mental Health Foundation 2018 Report, 2018).

Table 1: Main Themes and Subordinate Themes

Main Themes	Subordinate Themes
Category One: Provision link to mental health six standards	1.1 Work Plan (WP) 1.2 Mental Health Awareness (MHA) 1.3 Access to Service (AS) 1.4 Employee control and Purpose (ECaP) 1.5 Line Management Responsibilities (LM) 1.6 Monitoring of Wellbeing (MoW)
Category Two: Provision link to themes emerging from The Mental Health Foundation report, 2018 on Scottish context	2.1 Support/Help that Works Best 2.2 Inclusive Service Approach 2.3 Technological Aspect of Services 2.4 Support that Includes Strong Business Case 2.5 Need for Legislative Component 2.6 Sustainability Plan
Category Three: Evaluation Examples	3.1 In-house Evaluation 3.2 Role model SMEs

This research aimed to understand what the selected case organisations were doing to help SMEs to achieve the six standards. Furthermore, the aim was to understand case organisations' experiences regarding themes discussed in the Mental Health Foundation recent report.

4.2 Overview of Participants

In this study, the researcher used a purposeful sampling procedure and selected cases of organisations working to provide mental health services for the workplace. These cases were chosen by careful research on public service organisations operating in the workplace mental health area. Each of the cases stood on a spectrum, from information technology-based apps, through government-provided or brokered services to citizen-driven social innovation options.

Table 2: Case categories and Cases

Service Option	Cases (see Appendix 2 for case template)
AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Mental Health at Work; web; MIND curated · Woebot Health · CIPD
Government Brokered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · See Me · Healthy Working Lives Scotland · Salus
Citizen-driven Social Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · VOX Scotland · MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC · Remote Workmates

Three of the nine cases – Mental Health at Work, Woebot Health and CIPD – are AI organisations. See Me, Healthy Working Lives and Salus are government-brokered organisations, and another three – MHScot, VOX Scotland and Remote Workmates – are self-help options. At the beginning of the study, background information was gathered and the fundamental working process of these cases was ascertained. Following the service organisations' overview, the findings are presented and summarised using a case narrative process. The main focus of case narratives was on the further description of the six standards provision of organisations.

4.2.1 Case narrative of Mental Health at Work

Mental Health at Work (MHW), one of the case organisations, define itself as an online gateway to resources, training and information. MHW claims that it aims to provide the tools needed to make workplace mental wellbeing a priority in any firm, big or small, regardless of the industry or location. It also claims that resources are the heart of MHW, with organisations using the website as the first stop to find documents, guides, tips, videos, courses, podcasts, templates and information from key organisations across the UK. MWH states on their website that resources, views and examples on the website come from a wide range of organisations from across the UK, from business to charity to government. MHW is curated by Mind, a mental health charity. It is funded by the Royal Foundation

as part of their “Heads Together” campaign (MHW, 2020). In the section on ‘our partners’ on MHW’s website, it mentions Mind’s collaboration with 13 key partners from the world of business, industry, and mental health to develop MHW.

MHW suggests the site brings together resources, toolkits, blogs and case studies in one place. Its claim is- regardless of the sector or the organisation's size, people should find what they need at MHW. It mentions MHW has collected and organised many resources into toolkits designed to help, focused on Mental Health for Small Workplaces. On the website, these are its pre-packaged suggestions for sets of resources that go well together to help organisations focus on a particular area of workplace mental health. To help SME organisations, it provides a free short E-learning course and it claims that e-learning can build staff confidence in thinking and talk about mental health. According to the section on ‘Commitment’ on the MHW website:

Mental Health at work uses an MHW Commitment, a simple framework that builds on what is known. Their commitment is based on the Thriving at Work standards, pulling from the pledges and six standards that are there, evidenced by up-to-date research, from UK employers and mental health experts. MHW is a roadmap to achieving better mental health outcomes for employees, with actions that any organisation can follow to improve and support their people's mental health. Beyond that, it shows the organisation's values, declaring that mental health at work is a priority for them.

(MHW, 2020)

MHW promotes mental health wellbeing by providing Wellness Action Plans (WAPs) to managers and employees through its website. WAPs are defined as customised and practical tools that help employees in practical ways to support their own mental health at work. As the ‘resources’ section of the website puts it, “Managers and staffs can use WAPs to help them identify what keeps them well at work, what causes them to become unwell and the support they would like to receive from their employers to boost wellbeing or support them through recovery” (MHW, 2020). MHW also mentions that WAPs have been designed to help manage mental health by identifying mental health issues and making plans to tackle such situations.

MHW suggests in the resources section on the website that “managers can encourage a team to draw up a WAP that gives them ownership of the practical steps needed to help them stay well at work or manage a mental health problem in everyday work life” (MHW, 2020). MHW acknowledges the communication barriers between management and team and endorses WAPs as a dialogue opener between managers and employees to better understand their needs and conditions and therefore, better support their wellbeing. Furthermore, on the section of ‘Resources’ on the website, MHW states:

WAPs can lead to greater productivity, better performance, and increased job satisfaction. Employers who choose to introduce new starters to the WAP during the induction process can demonstrate their commitment to staff wellbeing from the very beginning, sending out a clear message that proactive management of the wellbeing of their workforce matters. WAPs are also particularly helpful during the return to work process when someone has been off work due to a mental health problem. WAPs helps with a structure for conversations around what support will help and what reasonable adjustments might be useful to consider.

(MHW, 2020)

Mind claims that it has worked with the Federation of Small Businesses (FSB) and people in smaller workplaces across the UK to create online training courses to build staff confidence in thinking and talking about mental health awareness. The primary aim is to help SME staff to begin a workplace conversation and hope that employees should find MHW training courses valuable. It further suggests that these courses are vital sources for SMEs. It advises employers to quickly and easily get the message across wherever they communicate with their staff – whether that is a poster on a wall, a message on the intranet or a section in a staff newsletter.

MHW believes that in its “Building Your Awareness” module, employees learn about the basics of some of the most common mental health problems and how they might feel in the workplace. It refers that staff can also get information regarding where to get support from and how to talk to their employer if they think they might have a mental health problem. It added resources to the module which focus on some of the common misconceptions around mental health and how staff can challenge the stigma surrounding it.

The core perception of MHW is- during or at the end of the online module or WAP, employees might identify mental ill-health signs in themselves or with a colleague and might appreciate some support. Especially for people who are already experiencing mental health issues, they might feel that they need extra help as sensitive conversations may remind them of unpleasant experiences. MHW suggests that organisations hold follow-up training sessions with their employees.

Self-care for mental health is mentioned in MHW's e-learning training. It has designed a module called “Looking After Yourself for Mental Health”. MHW suggests that this module is designed especially for SME Workplaces. As per MHW's perspectives, that module can teach staff about wellbeing and how it is related to mental health and how some of the challenges they face by working in a smaller

organisation can affect their wellbeing. It also implies that the module focuses on some techniques such as mindfulness and relaxation, which employees can use as a way to maintain good wellbeing.

MHW recommends that employers who affiliate with them will have to support their managers in applying six standards for their employees. MHW also claims it has provided sufficient resources for training and the tools for managers to implement each standard and drive change. A module called 'Supporting Each Other' is used for small organisations. It also confirms that with this module's help, the organisations can learn how to support a colleague who has a mental health problem and can help them return to work. According to the 'resources' section on the MHW website- "To effectively support staff to recover and return to work as quickly as possible, employers should take a person-centred approach and be sensitive to the individuals need" (Mental Health At Work, 2020).

MHW believes that its support is practical as it provides early intervention on mental health and manages initial mental health distress. It also declares through the website that MHW helps organisations to have a responsive environment in handling mental health by sharing resources. The focus is placed on the following six standards, established by Stevenson and farmer (2017): toolkits and e-learning modules. Its website mention that the organization is supported by groups such as CIPD, ACAS and the FSB. It also claims on the website that it is directly associated with the FSB; with its help and that of SMEs and charities across the UK, MHW has created well-researched resources and online training modules for small businesses.

MHW has free online courses available for stress management and mental health awareness. It also provides mental health support through an e-learning module, which is developed by Mind for employees. Mind has created some free, quick online training, especially for small organisations, to encourage staff to think about and discuss mental health. MHW hopes that employees will better understand mental health problems by the end of the online training course. It suggests that the Mental Health toolkit for small workplaces is well informative, structured, educational and instructive. It further advises that managers ask employees to participate in the training as all the topics can be completed and covered independently and also suggests that employees will feel confident and aware of their own and their peers' wellbeing after watching informative videos in those training modules.

MHW strongly believes that policies on stress and mental health include a strong business case. MHW also reports that a growing number of senior leaders now acknowledge that workplaces are only as powerful as their people. Organisations depend on having a healthy workforce.

MHW shares reports through their website. One of its reports, as reviewed by Stephenson and Farmer (2017), suggests that growing employer transparency presents prospects to enhance the scope of organisation action on wellbeing and this change can be felt throughout organisations through strong leadership. That report also claims that employers' action on wellbeing is almost always noticeable.

MHW offers entirely free services, led by sharing resources and online training. It implies that rather than being a commercial mental health service provider, MHW attempts to support workplaces through efficiently researched materials and toolkits. These toolkits are developed to focus on an earlier stage of strategy development. Its service is a continuous process of adding new resources and helping all kinds of organisations to achieve full knowledge regarding mental health support.

4.2.2 Case narrative of Woebot Health

Woebot was invented by Alison Darcy, a clinical psychologist at Stanford University. Woebot introduces itself as a mobile application or a chatbot which uses AI to help users by providing one-on-one therapy. Darcy created the tool based on CBT which, as explained in Section 2.9.3, treats depression by encouraging people to examine how they react to difficult situations. Woebot Health claims that Woebot App is not a direct substitute for a therapist, and it does not help the users to find one either. Instead, the tool uses a wide range of approaches to treat mental health, but it is very different from other forms of therapies. Darcy explained in the section on ‘About Us’ on the website that "The Woebot experience doesn't map onto what we know to be a human-to-computer relationship, and it doesn't map onto what we know to be a human-to-human relationship either" (Woebot Health, 2020).

Woebot intends to make mindfulness accessible to people anywhere in the world. An individual with a data plan and a smartphone, a Google Play or Apple App account can use the application. Developers of Woebot declare that they worked together with data scientists, storytellers, designers and engineers, and combined their passion for artificial intelligence to create a “friend” named Woebot. The developers of Woebot believe that the App can help people with their mental health through the application of CBT. They also suggest that users can treat Woebot as an online assistant.

The Woebot developers claim that Woebot is more committed, focused and devoted solely to participants’ feelings and App can stimulate users' emotions by reminding them to write in a gratitude journal. Woebot Health explains that it also provides users with essential mental health awareness information and helps them build a practice of meditation. Woebot Health states in the section on ‘Related Interface’ on the website:

Core to all our products is technology and content that can create and maintain a bond with people to engage them in their mental health. We use Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to understand and adapt to a person’s emotional state and cognitive ability, to motivate them to monitor their mood and to practice proven therapeutic techniques.

(Woebot Health, 2020)

According to the website, employers can include Woebot in their mental wellbeing plan and Woebot itself makes a plan while working with a user, and the plan provides everyday support to a user for at least the first two weeks. After completing the first two weeks, the Website suggests that it will automatically produce a report for the user, and that report will summarise the user's mental state and a user can also make his or her own plan with Woebot and continue to use it for the rest of the time.

Woebot explains on their website that any organisation can make the chatbot part of their workplace wellbeing plan, provide information about mental health and encourage employees to use Woebot to improve staff mental wellbeing. Organisations can develop a culture of positive mental wellbeing at work while offering initial technological support through Woebot. The App Woebot refers that it covers topics such as mental health, anxiety, depression, and it also tries to create awareness and educate its users about mental wellbeing through journals and informative videos.

Woebot health indicates, it encourages people to communicate their thoughts and then leads them by applying helpful techniques when they need it most. According to the website, it can make conversation at any hour of the day and reach people practically anywhere and it can encourage individuals to assist their own mental health. It also declares through the website that Woebot Labs Inc adheres to hospital-level security policies and procedures to protect sensitive user data. In this way, it claims that users can feel comfortable sharing their feelings without hesitation.

Woebot mentions it endorses self-care to its users through the daily conversation session. According to the website, it covers a self-care topic, which aims to help users understand the importance of self-care, make them more effective, energetic and confident, and take care of their own self, which is essential for achieving their goal. Woebot believes that for those who are interested in apps and technology, having an app for this is a cost-effective approach.

Woebot suggests it can support organisations by being part of their workplace wellbeing tools. It predicts managers know their workplace environment best; they can be responsible for its implementation in the workplace. Employers who take the Woebot commitment will help their managers implement standards for their employees to use the app as a daily logbook. It also expects that an employer can also focus on practical reports from Woebot, which will give employers a picture of the employee's state of mind. Employers can get that report from employees once they use Woebot for two weeks.

In explaining how Woebot works, the website suggests that after a brief introduction, the fully automated conversational agent, Woebot, asks the user's feelings and thoughts and then uses CBT to help reframe thought patterns and adjust negative sentiments. The intention is that by assessing the user's mental and behavioural health daily, Woebot helps generate more positive lifestyle behaviours.

Darcy, the founder of Woebot, hopes to make practical psychological tools radically reachable for people. She mentions in the section on 'About Us' on the website- " It means being able to access support, no matter the hour and whether you have a diagnosis or a prescription or not" (Woebot Health, 2020). She claims that Woebot helps individuals behave towards themselves and to empathise and modify the damaging narratives that continuously replicate their minds. She also claims that it attempts to alter the user's thinking by delivering views and growing awareness until the user has replaced unpleasant behaviours with healthier ones. The team Woebot thinks that it can act as a smartphone therapist, consulting with users onscreen then face-to-face complementing human healers' tasks. In this manner, Woebot claims it can make users more mindful and conscious of their feelings.

Woebot points out when accessing Woebot, if the bot detects crisis language from the user, it can confirm with the user, and then provide resources – explicitly directing them to one of the British Association for Counselling and Psychotherapy (BACP) certified and appointed counsellors and subsequently linking to all other services available from the mental wellbeing packages. In explaining its active client it states that Care First, a leading provider of workplace wellbeing and counselling to employees of public and private sector organisations, is the first in the UK to incorporate Woebot into its EAP programme, which currently consists of a telephone counselling helpline, face-to-face counselling and a range of other support services.

As an ibot technology, Woebot states it is always available and can offer a much higher frequency of therapeutic interactions than a human therapist. Woebot might support the moral case more than the business case. Normally for an organisation, the business case will get more priority as productivity is highly related to a staff member's mental wellness. Woebot believes that it has the potential to be a very positive, low-cost offering for businesses that want to help employees' mental health by comforting many people and inviting them to get real support. It can be an excellent foundation for any Wellbeing Policy.

It is unclear exactly how Woebot Health will be running the business in the coming years. Mental wellbeing AI chatbots and apps are still in their primary stages, requiring significant investment and research. However, Woebot points out it offers scalable solutions that can improve a team's behavioural health by providing something they want to use and engage with for a long time. The organisation believes that it will capture more organisations to make a scalable income. There is a segment on its website for in-house evaluation where users can share their valuable experiences with the organisation. When explaining its evaluation process on the website, Woebot states that routine security audits and risk assessments are conducted by third-party penetration testing services and internal reviews are done quarterly and annually.

4.2.3 Case narrative of CIPD

CIPD defines itself as an association for human resource management professionals. After forming the organisation in 1913, CIPD now has over 150,000 members globally. It mentions on the website that it works across private public and voluntary sectors. CIPD states its main goal is to create a better workplace, improve working lives, and help individuals, businesses and society. It also states that the organisation tries to bring change in the workplace by working with the government and employers. CIPD points out it mainly researches HR and learning and development issues. According to the website, HR professionals can obtain membership from CIPD by completing the qualifications offered by the organisation and CIPD offers different levels of HR best practice courses for all levels of HR professionals. According to the section on ‘Wellbeing at Work’ on the CIPD website:

Creating a positive, healthy environment at work is key to productivity and happiness. In addition to the practical professional support available to CIPD members via the online platform, CIPD provides members with access to a suite of products and services to support their mental health and wellbeing. The CIPD online service platform is a structured way to work through physical or mental health issues and any financial difficulty members may face.

(CIPD, 2020)

CIPD indicates that together with its workplace wellbeing provider, Health Assured, CIPD provides members with free help and support 24 hours a day, 7 days a week either by telephone or online (CIPD, 2020). It also declares it works closely with Health Assured, an organisation which offers online resources to support professionals' health and wellbeing. CIPD claims it plays an essential role by allowing its members to gain access to this wellbeing portal.

CIPD further claims it helps its members by sharing free access in the online portal and Health app and offering participants access to resources that encourage greater wellbeing and a healthy lifestyle. It seems like the organisation does not explicitly help employers with a mental health work plan, but it recommends Health Assured's four-week programmes to positively impact employees' mental health. The service provider proposes in the section on ‘Knowledge Hub’ on the website that “employees can choose an individual wellbeing area, set their targets, complete meaningful activities and track the progress, all from the comfort and convenience of their phone, whenever it suits them best” (CIPD, 2020).

CIPD promotes on the website mental health wellbeing and prevention strategies at work with the help of different trusted organisations. It suggests it facilitates the process by sharing links of various organisations' web pages. CIPD's online portal, powered by Health Assured, shares information about

stress, anxiety and depression in their wellbeing section. It recommends it directs its members to click on relevant resources linked from trusted mental wellbeing websites, provides information about mental health and encourages members to use free help and support from the online portal until they feel comfortable about addressing their mental wellbeing issues with professionals.

CIPD provides information on how it delivers knowledge about mental health and encourages members to use the online portal as first-hand support. It claims on its online portal, mental health is widely discussed. It also claims that CIPD members can access a wide range of services to support their mental health and the portal provides members with a structured way to manage health difficulties and offers 24/7/365 telephone or online emergency support.

CIPD indicates that Health Assured covers issues such as mindfulness in the emotional health section in the portal. It aims to help members understand the importance of mindfulness and how it can make people more effective, energetic and confident. Health Assured further suggests that practising mindfulness can improve focus and attention and create a sense of the present moment. It puts out that it discusses mindfulness techniques and states that anyone can learn and benefit from these techniques and control their sense of purpose through practice and patience.

In the work-life section of Health Assured's online portal, it discusses mental health management. Being aware and able to spot the symptoms of employees who could potentially suffer from mental health issues is a valuable ability to have as an employer or manager. It further states not only will it allow managers to offer help and care to their staff early on, but it will also potentially change and improve their lives. It is imperative to remember that everyone has a unique mental health experience, so symptoms can vary from person to person (CIPD, 2020).

Health Assured recommends that it is always worth talking to any staff members about whom the managers may have concerns. Managers can do so by educating themselves about the signs of mental illness. It also suggests that employers and managers arrange virtual workshops for employees and Health Assured can provide virtual training sessions on mental health, and it believes that this is a more cost-effective method than a traditional workshop session.

On the website, it is not mentioned anywhere that CIPD has strategies for checking workers' mental health and wellbeing from their side. However, the website says it does help members with information on the adoption of employee assistance programmes. According to the website, its online portal attempts to educate managers and supervisors about the potential signs and symptoms of poor mental health.

CIPD suggests that service-wise, Health Assured is well equipped to give CIPD members online support and wellbeing services. It is always essential to protect the sensitive information of clients. Health Assured claims that its consultancy call centre is run by professionals who value clients' privacy the

most. CIPD believes all the sections in the portal are relevant to the wellness of clients. Wellness can be supported by taking care of the mental, physical and financial health of the members. The service organisation covers all these areas, and its EAP helpline claims it is always ready to help members.

CIPD notifies, members can access Health Assured's online portal, which offers privileged access to mental wellbeing self-help programmes, videos, fact sheets, educational resources and interactive tools to support mental health issues. Moreover, it suggests Health Assured promotes mental health wellbeing and prevention strategies at work with the help of different trusted organisations. These are some of the UK's prominent organisations working towards the betterment of people's mental health. Health Assured shares web links to Mind, Samaritans, Money Advice Service, NHS UK, and other trusted organisations' to ensure mental health-related information availability.

Health Assured has online courses available for stress management and mental health awareness, and CIPD mentions these training courses are free of cost for CIPD members. It also provides permanent and useful technological mental health support solutions for members through the online wellbeing portal. CIPD claims it collaborated with Health Assured to give professional online EAP services to its members. It seems like the effectiveness of its support entirely relies on Health Assured's service quality and functionality: CIPD does not manage these online services by itself, but rather, they are supported and function by Health Assured. CIPD believes having entirely confidential support and understanding can give members confidence in carrying out their everyday activities. According to Health Assured, no one knows when members will be stuck with a situation that may not always be easy to speak about face-to-face, and Health Assured can “give that extra ear to confide in and rely on”.

CIPD argues that policies on supporting stress and mental health include a strong business case. The emotional, psychological and social wellbeing of employees is benefited when employers treat mental health issues seriously. It further illustrates employers achieve goodwill, and their organisations attract the best talent. Employees feel much more motivated, and the business benefits from this. Health Assured supports this and further states that looking after an employee's mental health can enhance the overall business value and reputation.

CIPD also claims it ensures that CIPD can help members by educating them regarding the legislative issues of mental health. It says it trains its members about sickness management, return to work policies, recruitment and reasonable adjustments and helps its customers throughout the journey using technology-friendly methods. Though it provides support through the online portal, it indicates that its focus is on ERP and CBT related solutions and continually tries to improve its service quality by using feedback from the customers.

CIPD has a segment on their website for in-house evaluation, where customers can share their valuable experience with the organisation. It indicates CIPD wants the participants of its courses to continue to

grow in confidence, knowledge and awareness and evaluate the long-term impact of courses, EAP solutions and workshops. It hopes that service users will help them do this. It adds it also cares about service users' input to establish what further learning they consider valuable and the key challenges in working around mental health and wellbeing.

4.2.4 Case narrative of See Me

See Me defines itself as Scotland's programme to tackle mental health stigma and discrimination and challenges stigma and discrimination at its roots. According to the organisation, it challenges discrimination and unfairness at work, education, home, and the community: wherever people experience it. It is funded by the Scottish Government and Comic Relief and managed by the Scottish Association for Mental Health (SAMH) and The Mental Health Foundation (See Me, 2020).

In explaining its working process, workplace officer Mairead Rowan states that one of their programmes is called the Workplace Programme, which is a four-step improvement course. See Me collects data from an organisation through a base survey and analyses these anonymous data in the first stage. She also informs that from See Me's baseline survey, it learned that 90% of employees think that organisations need to increase awareness regarding mental health. One of the questions in the See Me survey is "Would you like a better understanding of mental health?", and Mairead says usually employees answer four and above out of five on this question. She also suggests that employees are not sufficiently comfortable to share mental health situations with management. Probable reasons for this are the lack of social relations, inclusive culture and trust within the organisation.

Mairead suggests that in the second stage, See Me makes an improvement plan with the help of survey data and provides this to organisations. See Me, working as a free consultant, claims that it can give organisations a chance to make progress with an improvement plan. It shares survey information with the organisations as evidence of an employer's current stand on managing mental health. According to See Me website, its workplace action plan covers key areas, including awareness build-up, senior managers commitment, training line managers, and reasonable mental health adjustment.

Workplace officer Mairead indicates in the interview that in the third stage of the workplace programme, See Me suggests the organisation reviews the survey result and advises them to transform practice by putting the plan into action. She also says in this stage, See Me provides several resources and campaigns to assist organisations in achieving transformation. It further provides free e-learning facilities focused on mental health-related issues such as disclosing mental health problems in work, tackling mental health discrimination and reasonable adjustment. See Me claims that e-learning is open

to everyone, not just managers. Furthermore, there are dramatization opportunities in E-learning where people have the scope to share their experiences.

See Me points out it organises campaigns and activities that bring positive change in the workplace. It aims to create an environment where people can share their experiences and discuss mental health in a fun and easy manner. See Me workplace officer also points out the firm has a tool called “let's chat” that encourages managers to speak to their employees about mental health, particularly to the people showing signs of mental health problems. In that topic See Me mentions in the section on ‘Campaigns and Activities’:

“The Power of Okay” is a two-part campaign that focuses on improving the way people think about mental health at work. “Pass the Badge” is a simple way to start conversations on mental health. The idea is that a person wears a See Me badge for a day and then passes it onto someone else to wear for the next 24 hours. That individual then passes it on and so on. There is also a digital badge that can be posted on social media and passed on by tagging others.

(See Me, 2020)

However it is done, the message See Me indicates to convey is that everyone has mental health, and it is okay to talk about it.

After one year of the workplace programme, See Me suggests it helps organisations conduct a mental health check survey to identify improvements and progress in the fourth stage. Surveys conducted after the first year's improvement plan recommend that employees are marking the organisational environment negatively because they now have a better understanding of mental health-related rights and regulations. See Me informs it helps to empower staff with resources and enables them to act upon awareness information. It produces and shares a report of the findings and generates a new action plan for the organisation to improve different areas. Mairead in the interview states that this is See Me's cycle for improvement programme and its broader mental health strategy and workplace mental health framework. She also mentions that there is always scope for SMEs to benefit from this low-cost workplace mental health programme.

See Me points out, any organisation regardless of size in Scotland can be a part of See Me's workplace programme. In the interview, Mairead from See Me acknowledges that SMEs' challenges are greater than those of big organisations in tackling workplace mental health due to budget constraints. She also claims, See Me is aware that SMEs need to rely heavily on either government services or free services to make mental health provision better. See Me has nine SMEs engaged with the workplace programme, which is very small in number compared to SMEs in Scotland.

See Me claims it promotes Employee Distance Programme for mental health training, but it also believes that these training programmes are not suitable for SMEs due to the limited staff numbers. In this case, a digital platform can play a critical budget-friendly role in helping SMEs to develop acceptable mental health practices.

In the interview, Mairead mentions that See Me's sustainability is positively related to building capacity. It is attempting to build more capacity by not physically accessing organisations but sharing more online free resources through its website. She also mentions it provides a cost calculator to senior managers, and with this tool, managers can calculate the cost of someone being off sick or being unwell at work. However, its survey of organisations suggests that firms are reluctant to use digital support and resources. See Me thinks that SMEs' challenges are more than big organisations in tackling workplace mental health due to budget constraints. See Me is sharing free resources with organisations so that even with limited resources, staff can help themselves. Even though there are free services from the government, See Me believes the SMEs are not ready to utilise those services due to a lack of awareness.

See Me claims it works collaboratively with Healthy Working Lives (HWL), which runs a health and wellbeing award programme and through which See Me can gather wellbeing related data on a broader level. It states it is linked with certain membership bodies such as Business in the Community, CIPD and the Institution of Occupational Safety and Health. Moreover, it is managed by two central bodies, Mental Health Foundation and SAMH. Workplace officer Mairead from See Me indicates it has been trying to build a link with Scottish Trade Union Congress. See Me believes that extensive knowledge of this sector and a strong culture of knowledge sharing can be advantageous for the organization in creating a broader SME client base.

4.2.5 Case narrative of Healthy Working Lives

Healthy Working life (HWL) define itself as an organisation that offers workplace health, safety and wellness assistance, advice and information to employers in Scotland. In its own words from 'service updates' section on the website, it is a "free and confidential NHS service to help employers understand, protect, and improve their workforce's health and wellbeing" (HWL, 2020). NHS Health Scotland, along with Scotland's fourteen local NHS Boards, delivers HWL programmes and services.

HWL suggests that the Healthy Working Lives Award, which integrates Scotland's Health at Work programme, considers how health and well being can be actively promoted in the workplace, such as supporting mental wellbeing or healthy eating (HWL, 2020). The organisation also claims that it provides advice, educates people about workplace hazards and consults with employers about recruiting and creating opportunities for disabled communities and people with health problems. The Healthy Working Lives states that their award Programmes are structured to help employers and employees in a realistic, rational and beneficial manner to establish these workplace themes.

The organisation states in the section on ‘Award’ on the website that:

The Healthy Working Lives (HWL) award programme helps organisations identify issues and improve health, safety, and wellbeing in a productive and structured way. Organisations of any size can join the programme and HWL will support the organisation at each step to achieve the award. When they register for the award, the national award team will set up their online portfolio. Organisations who are new to the programme register their organisation for the Bronze award. Award will be valid for one year from the date organisations achieve it. During that year organisation will work on maintaining the award and, if they are ready, it will progress towards the Silver and the Gold awards.

(HWL, 2020)

HWL further explains on ‘Award’ section on the website how their programme works:

Once the organisation has joined the programme, it can start to gather a portfolio of evidence to show that the organisation meets the Bronze award criteria. The award will be valid for one year from the date they achieve it. To maintain it, they need to complete an annual online review. The review looks at how they have been working to identify issues and improve health, safety and wellbeing in their organisation for the last 12 months. It also asks them to say what they plan to work on for the next 12 months.

(HWL, 2020)

To work with HWL, it explains that organisations need to plan the health, safety and wellbeing of employees. During this process, HWL staff will contact the organisation to make an achievable plan. It claims its self-assessment process helps the organisation to identify strengths and weaknesses in essential health and safety. HWL then recommends areas of improvement for it to create its own health and safety action plan.

HWL indicates it arranges training sessions throughout Scotland, and they are also available online. It also indicates that the training sessions help to improve mental health awareness amongst employers and employees. According to the website, HWL also has a free online learning course to give everyone a basic idea about mental health at work. Employers should ensure that workers are aware of the employee assistance services available in times of bad mental health to benefit them. In these cases, it suggests signposting all the essential mental health-related information and resources. HWL recommends employers consult with employees in several ways; these include “holding formal consultations or meetings, having health and safety as a regular topic at departmental or management meetings sharing information on notice boards, through intranet and e-mail alerts adding information to payslips by printing messages on them or using inserts” (HWL, 2020).

HWL recommends the Living Life service, which offers support to Scotland through guided self-help and CBT. Staff can access the service by referring themselves for an assessment via the phone. According to the website, Living Life is a free phone service offering treatment for anyone in Scotland over 16 years of age with low mood, mild to moderate depression and anxiety. Users will be offered an initial appointment to ensure Living Life is best suited to their needs. If this is so, they then have a series of telephone support sessions with a guided self-help coach or therapist. If negative thoughts and feelings are affecting daily life, specialist help may aid the recovery. HWL recommends that Living Life uses a form of talking therapy to help users recognise unhelpful thought patterns and positive ways of coping. It suggests that the support sessions enable them to react more positively to challenging situations whilst improving their confidence and self-esteem.

Regarding self-care for the eLearning training module, HWL states it offers topics that aim to help participants understand the importance of self-care; make people more effective, energetic and confident; and show them that taking care of their own self is essential for achieving their goals. HWL suggests that involving employees in the decision-making processes will improve the processes themselves and help employees feel more valued, involved, and empowered to have their say.

To manage staff, the organisation says it needs to go through the process of surveys. Work Positive is a platform for stress-related risk control that assists employers in recognising and reducing the potential sources of occupational stress. The HSE Management Standards accepts and recommends this tool to assist work towards the standards. According to the website, 'The Work Positive' process involves interaction preparation and obtaining a questionnaire (to be provided to all workers to enable a thorough evaluation of the possible causes of tension at work), followed by consultation, action planning, monitoring and review.

The Employee Well-being survey is mandatory, with several questions designed to the organisation. HWL indicates it is created to meet the HWL award criteria in full. It believes this survey is a quick method of collecting health and wellbeing information from a large number of employees and can be sent to all or a sample of employees in the case of a larger organisation. Where a sample is preferred, the employees' sample must be random and representative of all grades and levels.

HWL also suggests that it has a one-day free training package on Mentally Healthy Workplaces for managers. It recommends organisations take the Thriving at Work review of mental health seriously, where the workplace's role was issued and acknowledged by the Government. It delivers awareness and information in ways that organizations can check and use to regularly assist their employees. It further states that:

Organisations of any size can join the programme and HWL will support them at each step to achieve the award. This support for the organisation is free and confidential. They will

offer the employer a health, safety and wellbeing programme to help the employer develops clear and robust policies and practices. Saving money and making employees feel supported and valued show that organisations have high health, safety, and well-being.

(HWL, 2020)

HWL believes the Scottish government strongly supports HWL's helping organisation through the award system approach. It claims that it is a proven way to boost employee morale and productivity.

HWL believes Government-funded HWL's approaches are inclusive of other occupational health programmes. It works with national mental health resource organisations such as Mind, Breathing Space, Samaritans and NHS Living Life Service. The organisation indicates it is trying to create awareness in organisations by sharing mental health resources from available trusted sources.

According to the 'Training' section on the website, HWL has online courses available for employees and managers regarding essential mental health awareness, and these training e-courses are free for organisations. However, it does not provide any permanent and useful technological mental health support solution like ibot or an online portal for workers.

The organisation firmly believes that policies on supporting stress and mental health should include a strong business case and that helping employees' mental health can result in less sick leave and ensure employee retention. It also claims it can improve productivity and engagement through a health and wellbeing programme which improve teamwork and can also ensure lower staff turnover and lower recruitment costs in the business. HWL suggests a number of simple, cost-effective ways to support and encourage a mentally healthy workplace. As a government-funded programme, HWL emphasises government legislation and suggests employers minimise the hazard of illness or harm to employees from their work. This includes situations that can influence an employee's mental wellbeing. This duty is part of the Health and Safety at Work Act 1974 and Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999. The Equality Act 2010 also involves employers to bring sufficient changes for employees with long term disabilities. Mental health conditions also fall under this definition (HWL, 2020).

HWL claims it runs for free, and the Scottish Government funds the program. It also claims that it is linked to many employers who come forward and ask for their help. It indicates it is currently attempting to cover the entire of Scotland and moving forward with the national capacity to support organisations. HWL suggests it is focusing on a Do It Yourself process whereby every organisation can feel confident to run their own health and wellness programme. The organisation says it wants to ensure that resources and support are there for employers in this journey.

According to the HWL website, it works closely with partners and customers to review and develop their training: Customer feedback suggests that customers love its training products and would recommend it to other customers. Furthermore, the customer survey input in 2018–2019 shows that 75% of people using courses would recommend them to others (HWL, 2020).

4.2.6 Case narrative of Salus

Salus Occupational Health, Safety, and Return to Work Services defines itself as an NHS-based provider who has been providing occupational health services to public and private sector organisations throughout Scotland and England for more than 20 years. Salus claims it is at the forefront of occupational health development and delivery in Scotland, working closely with the Scottish government to ensure the overall health, safety and well-being of Scotland's working-age population.

Salus states on 'About Us' section on the website that it has approximately 230 staff based over a variety of UK sites and operates in a similar way to a social enterprise model. Any surplus funds generated from providing services to employers are passed directly back to the NHS for the benefit of NHS service users. Salus indicates it applies the NHS's principles and values with a commercial focus to assist organisations in meeting their legislative requirements. Regarding its service provision, it mentions in the section on 'Occupational Health' on the website that:

Salus provides services to small and medium-sized organisations as well as large multi-national and public sector organisations where most benefits are delivered directly by Salus staff, but some are also provided locally by accessing a network of highly skilled service providers around the UK. Services recently developed and now in operation include an online referral and reporting system, access to rehabilitation support in the form of case management, physiotherapy and occupational therapy and the implementation of a telephone-based absence management system.

(Salus, 2020)

Salus thinks that to gain maximum productivity and ensure a happy and healthy workforce, a health and wellbeing strategy is integral to an organisation's business needs. It suggests it provides advice on a range of options available and tailors these to suit changing business needs. Salus also suggests that it plans with the organisation's teams to design and deliver organisational health promotion policies that maximise its health. It implies an organisation may require its services to help employees detect and adjust lifestyle factors that may be disadvantageous to their overall wellbeing. The employer can then make a health promotion plan for the organisation. In addition, it mentions on 'Range of Services' section on the website:

Salus plays a key role, nationally, in the UK wide Fit for Work Programme, by co-ordinating activity across all 14 health boards in Scotland. Salus Return to Work Services provides case management services to clients across the UK, to assist clients who are experiencing health and social barriers to remain in or return to work, training or further education.

(Salus, 2020)

In its planning process, Salus states it works with the organisation to identify its health promotion and education priorities. Salus run a health and wellbeing test conducted by experts, where it assesses employees' health and lifestyle issues by screening and producing a confidential online report.

Salus suggests it advises employers of group results and any required organisational changes. These changes include physical and wellbeing adjustment. The last step of the process is to arrange to follow up and recall the steps if required. It suggests it can only work as an outsider and show employers the current scenario and suggest them wellbeing adjustment. It also emphasises that employers must make their own decision to protect their employees' mental health through the work plan.

Salus argues that the workplace is an ideal location for health promotion and health education programmes to be carried out (Salus, 2020). It works with employees and provides targeted activities to recognise their wellbeing essentials and education priorities. To promote the good health of staff, Salus claims it participates in events in workplaces and also arranges educational displays for organisations. The firm also claims that it is available to discuss complex issues with employees. In explaining its working process Salus suggests an organisation can arrange an appointment in or near the place of work to get confidential support and advice. Salus can access specialist information with the informed consent of the employee. That can also help Salus to make appropriate and reasonable recommendations about individual cases. Salus suggests it can advise the organisation on practical action required to comply with disability legislation.

In pointing out its clinical, functional capacity based evaluation Salus suggest that the evaluation reviews the worker's ability to perform a certain task, whether they are currently absent or present at work. It can determine their suitability to perform their current role or a specific alternative role. The process addresses a range of factors that can interact to influence an employee's ability to work – independence in daily functioning, physical capacities and the psychosocial factors that can affect an employee's ability to manage their medical condition. Salus claims that the evaluation produces a report with conclusions and recommendations for actions to support the employees in the workplace.

Salus indicates that its Jobsite evaluation assesses the employees' work atmosphere to make suggestions to help them manage a current medical condition in the workplace. This involves a visit to the workplace

to record the characteristics of the job. It claims this process allows the job demands to be compared to their current abilities and recommendations for correct modifications or measures to be taken. The evaluation produces a report with recommendations for actions to support the employees in the workplace.

Although the main focus of the Occupational Therapy service for Salus is work, it addresses other life areas on the website, such as carrying out day-to-day activities within and out of the home. It suggests these issues can often impact an employee's ability to perform their work. Salus considers training to be an essential activity for all organisations and helps provide all levels of employees with the fundamental knowledge and skills to perform their roles. If organisations are looking for effective health and safety training for managers or staff, Salus claims it can also provide resources to the workplace to manage staff training. It highlights that it can facilitate a wide range of health and safety courses, including the Institution of Occupational Safety and Health (IOSH) training courses (Salus, 2020).

Salus highlights it offers training and awareness-raising sessions regarding mental wellbeing. Its wellbeing training and awareness sessions can be tailored to the needs of the organisation. It claims this training attempts to create awareness to managers by teaching them risk assessments and absence management techniques.

According to current evidence, Salus does not have strategies for checking workers' mental health and wellbeing from their side. However, it suggests it can help an organisation with the health assessment of its employees. Salus mentions it undertakes pre-placement health screening to ensure prospective new candidates (and existing ones, if there is a change in the post) are placed in positions compatible with their health needs whilst considering the post's functional requirements. A job description assists Salus in this process.

The organisation is aware that employers may require health and wellbeing checks or assistance for the organisation. To support this area, Salus suggests that it can organise assessment for individuals by a specialist who can offer an expert opinion, which will help managers or supervisors manage absence in the workplace.

At the moment, Salus considers focusing on giving occupational health services to employees who have developed a medical condition where the condition is affecting their work performance. It claims it evaluates an employee's performance by functional ability, job-site environment and activities of daily life. The evaluation produces a report with conclusions and recommendations for actions to support the employees in the workplace.

Salus declares it works with other organisations to form a service to meet absent management service. EASY (Early access to support for you) is the only "in-house" NHS absence management service in

the UK and has been formally evaluated by the University of Glasgow. EASY provides support and early intervention to staff from their first day of sickness absence to speed up recovery and assist an early return to work. Salus indicates it works with managers and the HR team. In explaining service process, Salus indicates that first, the employee or line manager calls a freephone telephone number, available 24/7, on the first day of absence. EASY staff then contact the employee, offering them an onward referral to specialist services and reminding them of key policies while ascertaining a potential RTW date (Salus, 2020). The team then notifies line managers of key absence details and outlines possible RTW dates and any necessary next steps which should be considered.

Salus indicates it offers a free and comprehensive range of RTW services across various sites throughout the UK. For example, Salus Case Management is a predominantly telephone-based service with an additional option for face-to-face service delivery if necessary, which is designed to assist clients in remaining in or returning to work (Salus,2020). With Working Health Services Scotland (WHSS), Salus says it offers confidential and free guidance and health assistance to the working individual employed by organisations with no more than 250 staff and WHSS help employees access confidential and free services without delay. Salus believes that its working process prevents employees from a further decline in health, and its case managers communicate with relevant professionals and GPs to ensure a suitable outcome.

Salus states it has signed up for the See Me mental health and wellbeing campaign, as well as the Healthy Working Lives Partnership Charter in Lanarkshire (Salus, 2020). The Faculty of Occupational Medicine (FOM) is an educational and professional body for occupational medicine and pursues maximum practice standards. It established the Safe Effective Quality Occupational Health Services (SEQOHS) standards to generate a standard quality for occupational health services. Salus mentions it is associated with FOM and has also been awarded the FOM's SEQOHS accreditation. Salus also mentions it is also associated with the British Standards Institution (BSI), the UK's first national standards body (NSB) who help enhance the safety and quality of services, product and structures by facilitating the establishment of standards and promoting their use. Salus works with BSI to help improve the standard of the organisation.

According to current evidence, Salus does not have any visible, permanent and convenient technological mental health support solution for the organisation. It mentions it works in a process whereby caseworkers will handle cases of employees who develop a medical condition. It also suggests it work with the government to establish a low-cost, high volume solution for occupational health. According to 'Return to Work Services' section on the website, "Services recently expanded and now in operation include an online referral and reporting system, access to rehabilitation support in the form of case management, physiotherapy and occupational therapy and the implementation of a telephone-based absence management system" (Salus, 2020).

Salus claims it can demonstrate significant savings leading to improved staff health & wellbeing impacting service delivery and productivity. It says it proactively works with the organisation to reduce absence rates within the first year of full implementation of EASY. It

further suggests that their absent management technique can help the organisation with financial savings and improvement in productivity. Salus considers prioritising the business case when it comes to managing occupational wellbeing. Business organisations are always more inclined to protect their financial savings and the productivity of the employees. It also argues that organisations who value and engage with their staff suffer less from sickness absence.

Salus ensures that any relevant legislation, e.g. The Equality Act 2010 is applied, particularly where the application of reasonable adjustments are required to ensure employers adequately support their staff in line with the appropriate legislation. Salus indicates it applies the NHS's principles and values with a commercial focus to assist organisations in meeting their legislative requirements and operates similarly to a social enterprise model where any surplus funds generated from providing services to employers are passed directly back to the NHS to benefit NHS service users.

Salus claims it has consistently evaluated the services given to clients frequently. This has allowed it to generate advanced solutions to help the workplace achieve good health at work and enhance sickness absence management. To protect services and customers, Salus suggests it operates within the quality systems of ISO9001:2015, a comprehensive quality management system, and SEQOHS, subject to rigorous internal and external audits to ensure it meets the required standards. In addition, it indicates it was one of the first organisations in the UK to achieve this accreditation.

Salus indicates it collects constructive criticism on service quality. These responses help it to improve the effectiveness of the support it provides to organisations. According to the website, it has also been awarded the Faculty of Occupational Medicine's Safe Effective Quality Occupational Health Services accreditation, (SEQOHS), the first NHS Scotland Occupational Health organisation to achieve this status. Salus mentions that the certification process, administered by the Royal College of Physicians of London, was recently established to support, raise and reward quality in OH services in the NHS and private sector.

Shaw Trust, one of the clients of Salus, helps disadvantaged and disabled individuals into independent living and employment. Their mainstream and specialist employment service helps individuals obtain skills, which allows them to get jobs in different sectors. Tony Urwin from Shaw Trust noted in the 'Evaluation' section on the website that "Salus provide highly professional, solution-focused interventions which have made a significant difference within the workless population in terms of support into work, the sustainment of employment and the increased wellbeing of the client" (Salus, 2020)

4.2.7 Case narrative of VOX Scotland

VOX Scotland claims that it is the only national mental health support provider in Scotland where service users run the organisation for other service users. It describes itself in ‘About VOX’ section of the website as “Scotland’s national voice on mental health, representing members’ views to Scotland’s politicians and health professionals to make sure Scotland’s laws and mental health services reflect service user needs and interests” (VOX Scotland, 2020).

VOX Scotland States that the main idea behind forming VOX was to ensure that the voices of people with lived experiences of mental illness should be heard. According to the section on ‘About VOX’ on the website: “VOX provides collective advocacy at the Scottish national level – representing groups and communities with a lived experience of mental illness – and VOX also supports individuals to form their own groups to express their experiences in their own words” (VOX Scotland, 2020). VOX claims it aims to enable people with direct experience of this illness to influence Scotland’s law and create a platform for them to promote awareness about mental illness in the community.

VOX suggests it functions as an intermediary between the people, Scotland’s Government and health and social care services. VOX aims to promote a good “fit” between mental health services and laws to ensure that everyone benefits and that public money is wisely spent (VOX Scotland, 2020).

The organisation states the following in the section on ‘About VOX’ on their website:

VOX doesn’t have a vested interest in service provision, and this enables them to represent members’ views without referring to financial considerations or a political agenda. VOX represents at the national level across all mental health issues and works in partnership with local/regional groups and thematic mental health organisations (e.g. Bipolar Scotland). They don’t compete with local groups and encourage all their members to join local groups and organisations.

(VOX Scotland, 2020).

VOX claims it represents its members’ understandings and opinions to the Government so that policymakers can shape their policies based on the views of people who have experienced mental illness. The organisation also points out it delivers its members’ personal experiences to NHS and the broader society. However, no evidence was found that says VOX helps organisations or employers with specialist mental health services, or it helps individuals with any kind of consultancy or therapy, but it does conduct research on mental health issues.

VOX Claims that VOX Capacity-Building takes two forms, and it claims to do everything it can to support its members to express their own views in their own words. It also suggests it supports members to attend training events which help them gain the awareness, knowledge and skills to express their

opinions in public (VOX Scotland, 2020). It points out VOX organises training events for its members, educates them on conducting research, helps them develop organisations, and teaches them about working in partnership. The members also get training on public speaking from VOX.

To develop a sense of community and belonging among its members, VOX suggests it publishes a regular newsletter called VOXBOX. The newsletter publishes ideas and views of the members and also works towards supporting the development of an informal network among Scottish mental health organisations. According to the website, The VOX Board considers membership applications at its regular monthly meetings. According to the organisation, it is “very welcoming and inclusive – individuals living with mental health issues are often ‘locked out’ of mainstream society, and VOX challenges this exclusion” (VOX Scotland, 2020).

Vox has suggested that the public create groups and join in their movement to promote a good “fit” between mental health services and laws to ensure that everyone benefits from it and that public money is spent wisely. VOX claims it supports individuals in forming their own groups to express their experiences in their own words, and managers and employers can create a group of their own to share their struggles, needs and experiences. However, no evidence was found which suggests VOX has any strategies to check directly workers’ mental health and wellbeing from their perspective as they do not have a vested interest in service provision.

VOX claims its partnership with a broad range of organisations. It says it is affiliated with organisations such as the Royal College of Psychiatrists, Healthcare Improvement Scotland (HIS) and the International Initiative for Mental Health Leadership (IIMHL). The IIMHL is a “virtual” agency that improves mental health services by supporting innovative leadership processes. With the help of IIMHL, VOX states It has created a bridge for its users to share their experiences and learn from other countries. It aims to continue to learn from others’ experiences and to help share its own learning (VOX Scotland, 2020).

VOX indicates an online newsletter is available for stress management and mental health awareness, but this service is exclusive for VOX members. It does not provide any permanent or convenient technological mental health support solution for workers. VOX also indicates it supports the moral case more than the business case. However, for a business organisation, a business case will get more priority as productivity is positively related to the mental wellness of staff.

According to the website, VOX is working on a mental health strategy in collaboration with the Mental Welfare Commission (MWC) and the Scottish Human Rights Commission (SHRC). It says it is continuously working to raise awareness about rights in relation to mental health. Finally, building capacity is one of the main missions of VOX, but it has to invest a significant amount of time for it.

4.2.8 Case narrative of MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC

MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC (MHScot) defines itself as a small disability-led social enterprise based in Edinburgh which supports the mental health and wellbeing of all Scotland's workforce in the private, public and third sector (MHScot, 2020). It suggests its main focus is on education, mental health literacy and culture, delivering courses, workshops, awareness-raising sessions, focus groups and more. It claims MHScot helps organisations to develop a positive, resilient and empowering work environment. MHScot believes that in creating a healthy workplace, a healthy mind is the most crucial factor. It claims that its focus on learning and development, education and supporting culture change regarding mental health in the workplace will help this to be achieved (MHScot, 2020).

MHScot states it arranges Scotland's Mental Health First Aid open course and an in-house course where organisational employees, volunteers and individuals can enrol. It also states it runs the Mental Health First Aid Course developed by NHS Scotland for adults who support young people between the age of 11 and 17 and arranges emotional culture workshops for organisations who want to create a more human and empathetic workplace and employee culture. In explaining the service process, It suggests that the client can work with MHScot to devise tailor-made workplace well-being solutions, bespoke to the organisation's needs and requirements.

Catherine Eadie, founder-director, began MHScot as she was a firm believer that prevention and early intervention were essential factors in making positive changes in mental health and wellbeing in the workplace. Experience of poor mental wellbeing and, more recently, a chronic health condition (fibromyalgia) has given her additional insight into the factors that require people to think differently about how they work and in what environment they work in (MHScot, 2020).

MHScot claims it promotes mental health wellbeing and prevention strategies at work through its organisation mental health first aid programme and facilitates the process whereby Mental Health First Aiders and Management come together to develop a framework for the practical implementation of providing Mental Health First Aid at work. It examines the organisation's resources, capacities and skills and how they could reasonably be utilised to put practical support structures in place. It further indicates it investigates how the service might operate in the workplace and tailors a solution to the organisation's specific needs and means, working with organisations to help them create a customised solution that fits their needs and requirements.

MHscot advises that organisations may feel ready to make a 'framework' for which it can support them in considering what a mental health programme might look like in an organisation as they know their workplace environment best. Materials were found suggesting on the 'Professional Expertise' section on the website that MHScot is responsible for the implementation of the framework.

MHScot claims it provides information about mental health and encourages organisations to create an environment in the workplace where mental health is being widely discussed; top-down to bottom-up. It also claims that it examines the practical steps that organisations can take to develop a culture of positive mental wellbeing at work while offering initial support and signposting to staff with poor mental health. To make real culture change and make mental wellbeing issues familiar, the organisation believes that everyone must be on board, but crucially those at the top level. On the website, MHScot covers topics such as attitudes, stigma and discrimination in its Pick & Match course programme.

In its training workshops, it suggests it covers topics such as listening skill development and suggests organisations provide an appropriate space within the workplace that is accessible and suitable for a private conversation. MHScot believes, its Emotional Culture Workshops are for organisations who want to create a more human and empathetic workplace and employee culture. Positive emotional culture, in its view, is linked to better performance, quality and customer service. From this perspective, it thinks that building a more human & compassionate workplace can give workers the freedom to talk about mental health. Creating human, face-to-face conversations about workplace culture, emotions and experiences is the main idea of the Emotional Culture Workshop. MHScot claims that it is an insanely simple card-based tool for structured face-to-face conversations about workplace culture, emotions and employee experience.

MHScot mentions self-care for mental health first aiders in its training topic. It also mentions on the 'Training' section on the website that the self-care topic "aims to help participants understand the importance of self-care, make people more effective, energetic and confident, and take care of their own self which is essential for achieving the goal" (MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC, 2020). It further adds it helps managers learn mental health management strategies and trains them to carry out employees' RTW processes.

MHScot believes that employers have a legal duty of care to their employees. It further advises running stress audits, which, if based on the HSE's Management Standards, pro-actively provide a preventative intervention level for the organisation (MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC, 2020).

The organisation indicates it does not have strategies for checking workers' mental health and wellbeing from their side, but it does help organisations to adopt and monitor EAP. It suggests MHScot runs surveys to learn about staff mental health and wellbeing at work by using bespoke questionnaires. It argues on the website that the MHFA programme support is effective because it addresses early mental health intervention and manages initial mental health distress, and helps people until other suitable and professional help can be found. On the 'Training' section of the MHScot website, it mentions that:

MHScot can provide the resources for conducting and assessing stress audits and stress risk assessments for organisations, producing both quantitative and qualitative data.

MHScot can advise how stress audits and assessments can become part of organisations' culture, policies and management processes. The data can assist with the development and implementation of appropriate action plans and change management.

(MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC, 2020).

MHScot suggests that Buy the Good Staff, Senscot, Alliance, and Social Firms Scotland are organisations who work along with MHScot and it is supported and assisted by these organisations. Its partnership with Apex City Hotel began at the beginning of 2018 when it began to deliver courses at their venue. Real Talk organises storytelling workshops and conducts intimate mental ill-health storytelling events. MHScot states that its partnership with Real Talk brings storytelling to the workplace, reducing stigma and encouraging open conversations, often at the heart of real culture change. It claims GTG Training, one of the skills development training organisations in business skill, health and safety and IT, was looking to add topics around mental health and wellbeing to their training programme and approached MHScot to form a partnership, and now they are part of their extensive programme.

According to the website, MHScot has online courses available for stress management and mental health awareness, but these training courses are not free. It does not provide any permanent or convenient technological mental health support solution for workers. MHScot strongly believes that policies on supporting stress and mental health include a strong business case and the impact of workplace mental health difficulties cost the UK economy considerably through lost working days, staff turnover and lower productivity. MHScot further states in the section on 'Professional Expertise' that:

Attentive and perceptive employers know the benefits of having a healthy and productive workforce. If employers manage and support their employees' mental wellbeing, they can ensure that their staff perform to potential, allowing them to achieve peak performance. In a period of accelerated change, training recognises the enormous improvements that can be made in staff wellbeing, leaving the organisation to concentrate on the business.

(MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC, 2020)

MHScot thinks that employers do not follow mental health policies because they do not have an appropriate policy regarding this. It claims that it can help the organisation improve, review and evaluate existing mental health policies regarding sickness management, recruitment, reasonable adjustment and RTW. It also claims that it can help organisations create and implement new policies involving mental health wellbeing and equality. MHScot explains that by conducting surveys on employees, it can assess the workplace's overall mental well-being and survey results can help them develop positive mental health policies, training and strategies to tackle the business areas that need consideration.

There is a section on the organisation's website for in-house evaluation where the customer can share their valuable experience with the organisation. MHScot indicates that lifelong learning and development in mental health and wellbeing is something MHScot is keen to encourage. It wants the participants of its courses to continue to grow in confidence, knowledge, and awareness and evaluate the long-term impact of courses and workshops and hope that service users will help them do this. It also indicates it appreciates service users' input regarding what further learning they would consider valuable and what the key challenges are in the place of work concerning mental health and wellbeing.

Since 2015, MHScot points out it has engaged with 1238 participants. Among these, 541 participants were from the voluntary sector, 332 and 119 from the private and public sectors. Accordingly, 41 were individuals and 175 participants attended events where MHScot gave presentations or offered a workshop at an event. After their two days of mental health first aid course, 32% said their knowledge had improved, 24% said their experience had been enhanced and 23% were confident of the improvement of their skills. It also indicates that when asked how the participants will use their learning from the course, 27% said by informing others and 24% said they would use it in their personal lives. According to MHScot's mental health at work evaluation, most participants agreed to have more knowledge about mental health at work, recognise early signs of mental health distress, and their confidence at approaching a colleague concerning their mental health and wellbeing grew.

4.2.9 Case narrative of Remote Workmates

Remote Workmates defines itself as a virtual community for new and existing workers who support each other on a daily basis. It claims that Remote Workmates help each other to adopt working remotely by sharing experience, advice, and tips. It also shares relevant resources with members. According to the organisation, people who meet on this platform are not colleagues, they are remote workmates. The organization reveals that its main goal is to make sure workmates are never lonely and no one feels isolated while working remotely.

Remote Workmates suggests its program as a global and diverse platform. Members and moderators of this organization refer that they organise different events such as Wellbeing Week which includes mindfulness, exercise sessions and virtual yoga to give all the members a comforting environment. Moderators are promoting through their website an exciting ongoing challenge called World 365 Loop, where participants have to exercise their way around the world twice collectively.

Remote Workmates was created during the Covid-19 pandemic to tackle the adverse effect of working in an isolated environment. The website declares that an experienced group of remote workers founded the organisation to help the new remote working population.

In explaining its working process Remote Workmates states that it uses the Slack App to host discussions and manage all of the wellbeing activities. An individual has to join the Slack community to become a remote workmate. New workers are facilitated by the buddy scheme to adopt remote working and then they participate in group activities and challenges and, as the organisation claims, be one of the people who turned a crisis into a movement. Remote Workmates' hope is for this to be a community of people who come together in a crisis but stay together for the longer-term enjoyment of remote work (Remote Workmates, 2020).

The organisation does not offer individual advocacy, and neither does it have the capacity or structure to provide specialist mental wellbeing services such as helping organisations with making work plan. The organization refers that workmates can share their thoughts and related resources on mental health wellbeing as this is a free and open platform. This platform's structure does not support the idea of helping with mental health at work plan at the organisational level.

Remote Workmates suggest that it supports members with free training to gain knowledge and develop skills to manifest their views in mental health. They provide information that in the past, moderators have supported members to participate in classes such as wellness sessions, calm and power workshops, and seminars involving self-image improving mindset tools and exercises to create awareness of mental wellbeing.

Remote Workmates states it welcomes individuals living in any corner of the world, with or without mental health and well-being issues, and focuses on the topics that are often avoided in mainstream society. It also states that the platform gives members the chance to talk about their situations.

The organisation promotes that it focuses on the importance of mindfulness, and how it can make people more energetic, effective and confident at work. If members want to change the results, then the firm emphasises that they should change the image through effective education of what is happening and a constant spaced repetition of the idea they want to implant. Remote Workmates arranges an informative, fun and practical webinar titled self-image which it claims improve mindset tools and exercises to teach members how to change their self-image permanently.

Remote Workmates suggests that it encourages the public to create groups and join in their movement to promote a good fit between mental and physical health practices. It further suggests that it supports working people to develop their channel through Slack to express their battles and experiences with other workmates. It does not have strategies for checking workers' mental health and wellbeing from their side as the platform's structure has been created only to encourage members to share their experiences on members' own terms.

4.10 Summary of findings

Each of the nine cases was evaluated in this chapter to assess the workplace mental health service condition of these organisations. This chapter began with an overview of the categories under which the cases were developed, which included factors related to mental health standards and service organisation's perspectives of workplace mental health. Following the service organisations' overview, the findings were presented and summarised using a case narrative process. The research has identified different perspectives by studying various cases. These perspectives have helped decide the outcome of the study.

Chapter 5: Analysis and Discussion

This chapter presents the analysis of this study. The finding chapter provided data enabling the options to be evaluated with respect to the six standards. Nine organisations have been explored as mental well-being service cases under three main options: an AI tool, government-brokered services and self-help, or citizen-driven options. All the options are evaluated with respect to the core standards for services. The analysis was done using a Likert scale (Figure 1), which emerges from a collective response to a set of items, and in the format, responses are scored along a scale (Likert, 1932) as 'best for', 'good for' and 'not good for'. Case options are considered below to identify the optimal approach to effective mental health services in SMEs.

Analysis on Likert Scale						
6 Standards for Mental Health in Workplaces						
Options	Work Plans (WP)	Mental Health Awareness (MHA)	Access to Service (AS)	Line Management Responsibilities (LM)	Monitoring of Wellbeing (MOW)	Employee Control and Purpose (ECaP)
AI						
Mental Health at Work	Good For	Best for	Good For	Good For	Not Good For	Good for
Woebot Health	Not Good For	Good For	Best For	Not Good For	Best for	Good For
CIPD	Not Good For	Good For	Good For	Not Good For	Not Good For	Not Good For
Government-Brokered						

See Me	Best for	Good For	Not Good For	Good For	Good For	Not Good For
Healthy Working Lives	Good For	Good For	Not Good For	Good For	Good For	Good For
Salus	Good For	Not Good For	Good For	Good For	Good For	Good For
Citizen-driven social innovation						
VoX Scotland	Not Good For	Not Good For	Not Good For	Not Good For	Not Good For	Good For
MHScot	Not Good For	Not Good For	Good For	Good For	Not Good For	Good For
Remote WorkMates	Not Good For	Not Good For	Good For	Not Good For	Not Good For	Good For

Figure 5.1 Allocation of Judgement on Likert Scale

5.1 What is Meant by a Mental Health at Work Plan

A mental health at work plan (WP) is a detailed and structured strategy to address mental health issues at work. It is developed to support everyone at work with or without mental health concerns. The WP should have details such as an organisation's strategy to deal with workers' mental health problems, how they promote well-being for the employees, and the process of monitoring the workforce's welfare (Mind, 2018). People can suffer from ill mental health by issues caused inside or outside of work, and a WP should have details of how the organisations support their employees experiencing poor mental health: "There should be a specific work plan on how organisations equip and support their line managers and supervisors, signpost to

relevant sources of information and support and establish clear objectives or targets shaped around the organisation's vision" (Mind, 2018).

In their report, Mind (2018) mentioned that it is crucial to develop a WP with input from employees across the organisation. Taking opinion from employees gives a clearer picture of what support people need and what the employer can do better. Organisations can draw on colleagues' knowledge and experience already interested in mental health, or mental health champions or trained mental health first aiders if the employer already has them in place (Mind, 2018). Good communication with people across the organisation is vital while creating an action plan. Mind (2018) suggests asking the employees what works best for them and adjusting support accordingly to help organisations create applicable WPs. As SMEs lack resources, they need assistance from mental health service providers to establish them.

5.1.1 The actions of AI organisations regarding mental health at work plans

This study concentrated on options such as AI or technology-based solutions to help SMEs with the WP. The findings of this research suggest that technology-based solutions have a mixed impact on developing and supporting WPs for SMEs. MHW is one of the case organisations under technology-based solutions in this study. MHW claims it promotes mental health well-being by providing a WAP guide to managers and employees.

MHW suggests that the WAPs are a customised and practical tool that managers and staff can use to identify what keeps them well at work, what causes them to become unwell and what kind of support they would like to receive from their employers to boost their well-being. In addition, it recommends, organisations should enable their employees to develop their own WAP, which gives them the ownership to manage their own mental health problems in their everyday work life. The WAP guide is available on MHW's website, and any SME organisation can download it and take support from the guide. The only issue is that MHW is a digital platform which can support organisations with its digital resources, cannot offer SMEs further evaluation on their work plan.

The other two AI-based case organisations Woebot Health and CIPD, suggest helping their members in terms of technological solutions by sharing free access to their online platform, giving members all-time access to tools that promote a healthy lifestyle and greater well-being. However, at the moment, they do not specifically help employers and employees with the WP.

5.1.2 The actions of government-brokered organisations regarding mental health at work plans

When it comes to supporting the SMEs by Government-brokered organisations, evidence suggests that service providers such as See Me, HWL and Salus collect available and significant information about the organisation and its staff to provide the most efficient mental health work plan. Research findings show that these government-brokered organisations work similarly. They plan with the organisation to design and deliver organisational health promotion policies to maximise the workforce's mental health. Once organisations join these programmes, they start to gather a portfolio through a baseline survey. These organisations claim that collecting baseline data also helps them know more about what policies are in place and what training organisations offer managers.

In the second stage of the service process, these government-brokered organisations analyse baseline data and help SMEs with an achievable annual mental health improvement work plan. In the health and safety action plan, they recommend areas of improvement for the organisation. In their planning process, they work with the organisation to identify their health promotion and education priorities. In addition, they point out that these service organisations advise employers of survey results and any required organisational changes. These changes include physical and well-being adjustment.

According to research, the last step of the process is to arrange to follow up and recall the steps if required. Government-brokered organisations claim they work as an assessor when it comes to evaluating organisations. In this manner, organisations become accountable to service providers, and they create an interplay relationship with them. Though these government-brokered organisations struggle to build capacity, their work process supports the criteria for developing a WP, supervision and evaluation.

5.1.3 Citizen-driven organisation' actions regarding mental health at work plans

Research data suggest that citizen-driven organisations do not support SMEs or any other industry with the WP. They do not facilitate any one-on-one sessions, and they do not provide specialist mental health services such as helping organisations with a WP. Instead, they try to convey their members' views and ideas to the Government and other authorities.

Research finds that a diverse and global gathering of people can share their valuable thoughts on the citizen-driven platform. A social platform such as Remote Workmates hosts group

discussions and events for members. Those platforms are used to share thoughts and awareness resources on mental health well-being by members. However, these platforms' structure does not support helping with the WP at the organisation level.

5.1.4 Best option for supporting mental health at work plans

See Me has done better in helping organisations with their WPS than any other case organisation. Establishing transparency with staff as part of a WP is very important. See Me communicates with staff and ask them what works better and adjust supports according to this while creating a WP. It says it can help SMEs through a systematic mental health baseline information collection to survey data analysis, work plan development and evaluation. This process of assisting organisations with the work plan is organised and systematic. Via this method, they can easily gain insights into the mental well-being situation of an organisation. They develop the WP based on the information collected directly from the staff. Most importantly, See Me claims it is always there to guide and evaluate organisations on their way to achieving one of the core standards.

Because of the limited budget and lack of time, SME employers are unwilling to engage in evaluation research. Newman et al. (2015) reported on a worksite wellness intervention targeting small businesses where they provided free, company-specific advice in design and execution, and only 21% responded to the follow-up survey. This is a sign that SME employers are not motivated to create a WP for their employees' mental health. See Me has confirmed that employees showed concern in their baseline survey that they do not feel comfortable talking to their managers or supervisors regarding mental health. A service organisation such as See Me can be of valuable help in collecting necessary mental health-related information from employees. Furthermore, SME employees can rely on a third-party organisation who can act neutrally to create a WP and supervise an annual mental health support review.

To qualify for the best option, case organisations need to fulfil maximum service characteristics of mental health WP standard. Research interview data and secondary data indicate that See Me fulfils almost every criteria to be the most satisfactory option for this standard. See Me is the only one who creates and provides organisations with a mental health improvement work plan and free online resources and online training from all the cases. Other cases standing at the 'Good For' position in the Likert Scale only help firms make work plans with available resources but do not create or provide organisations with bespoke improvement WP. 'Not Good

For' case organisations do not fulfil the characteristics of the Mental Health WP standard. This analysis strongly justifies that See Me is the best service organisation among all the cases regarding helping SMEs with mental health WP.

5.1.5 Blend of options for establishing mental health at work plans

Among the three options, the services of the government-brokered organisation and technology-based or AI organisations should be blended to enhance advantages in the service provision of SME mental health. Government-brokered organisations such as See Me and HWL create value by working as a moderator and evaluators of mental health services for large and small organisations. The literature mentions that only 33% of SME employees report to their employers for help. However, 38% of large organisations' employees reported their employer or management (Business in the Community, 2019). Furthermore, 88% did not disclose their concerns to their employers or line managers among the SME employees who experienced any mental health problems. This overall scenario indicates that SMEs are not effective in dealing with mental health at their workplace. In this case, if government-brokered organisations act as trustworthy administer and create trust, communication and a clear understanding between SME employers and employees, it can be less challenging for employers to deal with SMEs' mental health issues.

Government-brokered organisations always struggle with capacity building criteria. See Me mentioned in their interview that they are trying to build more service capacity through their online platform to share more workplaces resources. MHW's Wellness Action Plan can work as a free personalised and practical tool for SMEs. Managers can inspire the employees to create their own WAP, which will help them stay well at work. This process helps open up a dialogue between managers and team members to understand better their needs and experiences. Managers and staff can use it as the primary resource in making a WP. In this way, managers can establish a WP with online resources and get extra support from the government-brokered organisation to further evaluate their WP.

A blend of service options between AI and citizen-driven organisations can create disadvantages in SME mental health service requirements. Citizen-driven social innovation organisations do not support SMEs or any other industry with a WP. They do not offer individual supervision and deliver specialist mental health services such as helping

organisations with a WP. On the other hand, AI or technology-based options do not offer direct supervision. Instead, they provide online resources to support mental health work plans. However, the literature signifies that SMEs need direct supervision to establish a WP. Without the help of low cost or free services of government-brokered organisations, they might face challenges to develop such plans.

5.2 What is Meant by Mental Health Awareness at the Workplace

Every organisation should have an open and positive culture where people feel free to talk about their mental health (Mind,2018). The best way to make that happen is by developing mental health awareness (MHA) at the workplace: "Raising awareness of mental health is something that an organisation should build into its ongoing activities as a part of mental health at work plan" (Mind, 2018). Organisations can adopt different ways to raise mental health awareness in organisations. SMEs can be supported by gaining access to reliable information resources regarding mental well-being. The resources should be sufficiently informative so that employees can help themselves in need and also help other colleagues (Mind, 2018).

Help from external sources could be a part of broader mental health awareness activity. Making the most of internal communication through posters, noticeboards, staff newsletters, magazines, and intranet can help organisations get the message out: "Bringing people together with different perspectives and experiences is essential to challenge mental health stigma and open about the state of mind" (Mind, 2018). As people follow their leaders' behaviour, managers and supervisors can influence employees' attitude and enhance their understanding of mental health.

5.2.1 The actions of AI organisations in creating mental health awareness

Case organisations that use AI have the resources to boost the mental health knowledge of an organisation's employees. Organisations such as Mental Health at Work, CIPD and Woebot Health claim they can help people with their online resources. These resources are based on topics such as mental well-being, anxiety, depression. These digital platforms suggest creating awareness and educating users about mental well-being through journals and informative videos. These organisations also point out that any organisation can make these free of cost digital sources part of their workplace well-being plan, share information about mental health, and encourage employees to use them for the better mental well-being of staff.

Mental Health at Work and CIPD suggest they promote mental health well-being and prevention strategies at work with the help of different trusted organisations. They facilitate the process by sharing links of different organisations' web pages. In addition, CIPD's online portal shares information about wellness activities in their well-being section. According to the website, CIPD encourages members to use free help and support from the online portal until members feel comfortable dealing with their mental health issues with professionals.

Mental Health at Work has free courses available on its digital platform, which are vital for SMEs. They advise the employers to quickly and efficiently get the message to their staff about online training materials – whether this a poster on a wall, a message on the intranet or a section in a staff newsletter. Overall, research insists that through these digital platforms, a good volume of quality mental health awareness information can be shared free of cost. In addition, organisations can develop a positive mental well-being culture by offering initial online training support through these digital organisations.

5.2.2 The actions of government-brokered organisations in creating mental health awareness

As part of the baseline survey, government-brokered organisations suggest they ask employees whether they receive any training and support or know about the organisation's mental health policies. If the results show that people are not aware of mental health, they suggest that organisations take steps through the improvement plan. From their survey, SEE ME learned that almost 90% of the employees think that there should be more awareness about mental health within their workplace. According to research data, Government-brokered organisations have different campaigns and activities to promote mental health, and they share awareness resources through their online portal.

When it comes to supporting workers' well-being, government-brokered organisations suggest they have a crucial role to play irrespective of the problem or struggle to be personal or at work. They offer online and in-person training throughout Scotland. These organisations claim that short courses can help improve awareness about mental health. For example, to give a general introduction to mental health at work, HWL has a free online learning course. Though these online modules are not explicitly made for SME workplaces, government-brokered organisations offer sensible mental awareness-related resources for all kinds of organisations.

5.2.3 The actions of citizen-driven organisations in creating mental health awareness

According to research data, citizen-driven organisations help members to convey their own opinions on an open platform. In addition, these organisations suggest they organise free training events for the employees to enable them to gain awareness, knowledge and skills and these skills will make them more confident in speaking publicly. According to websites, these platforms have supported members to participate in classes such as wellness sessions, calm and power workshops, and seminars. These seminars and workshops are not related to workplaces but are concerned with general mental well-being.

VOX Scotland and Remote Workmates claim they try to support their members in expressing their views in their own words. They help members attend training events to acquire awareness, knowledge and skills that will assist them to express their opinions in public. MHScot, meanwhile suggests, the organisation examines the practical steps that organisations can take to develop a positive mental well-being culture while offering initial support and signposting to staff with poor mental health. It points out it covers topics such as attitudes, stigma and discrimination in its Pick & Match course programme. This topic aims to help participants understand the role that stigma and discrimination play in mental health and be aware of the environment that can foster or reduce stigma in the workplace (MHscot, 2020). According to the website, MHScot provides mental health awareness courses for employees, but these are not free of cost, and many SMEs might not be interested in expensive programmes.

5.2.4 Best option in terms of mental health awareness

To help employees build confidence in expressing their opinion about mental health, Mind collaborated with the FSB and developed online awareness training courses. It believes this is a great way to start the workplace conversation and claims that the employees should find their training courses valuable. Findings have suggested that most SME owners struggle to find spare time to spend with employees and have necessary conversations, or even struggle to find time to organise training sessions because of their busy daily schedule (Panagiotakopoulos, 2011). MHW addresses the fact that smaller businesses face unique challenges and get exceptional opportunities. With their unique challenges, SME employees can invest their time to gather awareness from the MHW platform, which gathers vast resources from different examined sources.

In the 'Building your awareness' module, employees get to learn about the basics of some of the most common mental health problems and how they might feel in the workplace. Staff can also get information regarding where to get support from and how to talk to their employer if they think they might have a mental health problem. The module also focuses on some common misconceptions around mental health and how staff can challenge stigma. Most importantly, MHW has created a training module specially for SMEs, and their website offers significant information regarding SME mental health at the workplace. Martin et al. (2020) highlighted that the unavailability of adequate mental health support in SMEs incurs additional organisational costs. Free resources and specialised training material from MHW can therefore help SMEs build a primary mental health awareness level.

To be eligible for the best option in this research, case organisations need to satisfy maximum service characteristics of MHA standard. Research interview data and secondary data reveal that MHW fulfils the maximum criteria to be the most satisfactory option for this standard. Moreover, MHW is the only one who claims that it provides SME specific awareness resources and training through its digital platform. Working for a small business can give staff unique experience to job functions and work environments because workers tend to play several job roles in SMEs (Martin et al., 2009). In this case, it can be essential to treat SME staff with unique mental health awareness training and resources. Other cases, standing at the 'Good For' position in the Likert Scale only help firms with available generic resources, not exclusive for SME setup. 'Not Good For' case organisations do not fulfil the characteristics of the MHA standard. This analysis strongly justifies that MHW is the best service organisation among all the cases when it comes to helping SMEs with MHA.

5.2.5 Blend of options to create mental health awareness

Among the three options, the blend of services of the technology-based or AI organisations and government-brokered organisations can make a difference in creating mental health awareness at SME workplaces. There is a need for the curation and interpretation of OH research and resources for SMEs, and practical experience and input of small organisations with these resources can produce tangible benefits for SMEs (Nielsen & Noblet, 2018). Mind has partnered with FSB and small SMEs and created online resources. These resources help the workforce to build confidence to open up about their mental health. MHW has all these resources available for SMEs in their digital platform.

Government-brokered organisation See Me creates awareness about mental health stigma and its effect in the workplace. Two years after the See Me campaign, surveys were conducted, and the results were positive. There was a 17% drop in the perception that mentally ill people are dangerous and the number of people who believed that the public should be better protected from people with mental illness dropped by 11% (Dunion & Gordon, 2005). See Me is attempting to change the culture of discrimination that causes mentally ill people to suffer from more physical health conditions compared to their healthier counterparts. The organisation is also working to make a better workplace environment where employees can share their mental health problems with the employers without any concerns.

A review by Hanisch et al. (2016) illustrates that workplace anti-stigma interventions may help change employees' knowledge, behaviour and attitudes towards people with mental health issues. An organisation such as See Me can create awareness by educating employees and employers about mental health stigma. By doing so, they may help change employee's attitude, knowledge and behaviour towards mental health at the workplace. A digital platform such as MHW and government-brokered organisations like See Me and Healthy working life can create value in the awareness development of the SME workforce.

VOX Scotland and Remote Workmates try to support their members by helping them to attend training events to acquire awareness, knowledge and skills that will assist them in expressing their opinions in public. Meanwhile, MHScot offers support through MHFA courses. Hadlaczst et al. (2014) found that MHFA ultimately increases the general population's mental health literacy by improving self-recognition, increasing the insight into one's own and others' emotional well-being, and enhancing mental health-related vocabulary. However, SMEs need cost-effective solutions, and MHFA is not the best way to create mental health awareness cost-effectively (Narayanasamy et al., 2018). SMEs might face disadvantages if they blend social innovation service options with government-brokered options as they do not provide services that create SME-specific mental health awareness.

5.3 What is Meant by Access to Mental Health Services

Organisations should ensure open conversations about mental health, and in their journey with the organisation, employees should get support from their employers at every stage (Mind, 2018). Mind (2018) suggests that "One of the essential steps to dealing with mental health

problems is to encourage employees to open up in the first place. Once problems are out in the open, employer and employee can begin to work together to find the right solution". Workers should have access to areas where they can start honest discussions about mental health. Employers need to ensure support for people during the recruitment process and also monitor them throughout their employment (Mind, 2018).

Supporting staff can be started from the start of the recruitment process, and it is the organisation's responsibility to make staff feel comfortable about the company culture. Organisations should have a culture where, if any employee shows signs of mental health problems or discloses mental illness at any stage in their career, they should have an early conversation about their needs.

5.3.1 The actions of AI organisations regarding access to mental health services

MHW suggests that an employee finishing the online module or dealing with WAP employees might help identify mental ill-health signs in themselves or in a colleague, following which they might try to seek some support. Sometimes this can mean that individuals currently undergoing mental health problems may need some urgent support as sensitive conversations may bring up complex topics: "MHW encourages small organisations to think about the support and help that is already available within the organisation, and in the area to highlight follow-up training to their employees" (MHW, 2020). However, MHW points out that it can only help organisations and staff with e-learning modules and online links of other service organisations who can help them. Other than that, they are not capable of giving mental help services physically.

Similar to MHW, CIPD suggests it provides information about mental health and encourages members to use the online portal as first-hand support. In their online portal, mental health is widely discussed. CIPD mentions on the website that its members are offered access to multiple products and services to support their mental well-being. It also mentions it provides members with a structured step to work through physical or mental health issues and any financial difficulties they may face. Together with the workplace well-being provider, Health Assured, they provide CIPD members with free help and emergency support 24/7/365 via telephone or online (CIPD, 2020). Here, CIPD members are the beneficial group who can use emergency telephone support for mental health issues.

Woebot Health claims it welcomes people to share their thoughts and then guides them through applying effective techniques in moments when they need it the most. It also claims it can reach people almost anywhere in the world and chat to them at any hour of the day or night, as well as encouraging individuals to assist themselves. Woebot Labs Inc claims it adheres to hospital-level security policies and procedures to protect sensitive user data. In this manner, users can feel comfortable sharing their feelings without hesitation. Woebot can be an initial mental health consultant, advisor and cognitive behaviour therapist.

5.3.2 The actions of government-brokered organisations regarding access to service

See Me mentions on the website that it has a tool called "let's chat" that encourages managers to talk to their employees about mental health, particularly to the people who are showing signs of mental health problems. It is a part of See Me's action plan and a pivotal resource for engaging managers with staff. See Me suggests it aims to ensure that the organisations, the managers and the employees know mental health policies through regular communication and supervision.

Next, HWL recommends organisations use the Living Life service, which offers support to people in Scotland through guided self-help and CBT. Staff can access the service by referring themselves for an assessment via phone. It also suggests that Living Life is a free phone service offering therapy for anyone in Scotland over 16 years of age with low mood, mild to moderate depression and anxiety (HWL, 2020). They use a type of conversion therapy to help users recognise unhelpful thought patterns and positive coping methods.

Meanwhile, Salus claims it provides employers and employees with confidential support and advice concerning work or non-work-related issues (Salus, 2020). It assesses specialist information with the informed consent of the employee and advises an organisation on the practical action required to comply with disability legislation. Most importantly, Salus suggests it is available to discuss complex issues with employees. However, Salus in general, deals with health and safety and well-being. This means that addressing well-being-related issues is part of Salus's overall OH services; hence their focus on mental health services is not particularly remarkable.

5.3.3 The actions of citizen-driven organisations regarding access to service

According to VOX, "The VOX Board considers membership applications at its regular monthly meetings and is very welcoming and inclusive. Individuals living with mental health

issues are often 'locked out' of mainstream society, and VOX challenges this exclusion" (VOX Scotland, 2020). In this manner, VOX suggests it can give people support when they know they need it and consider themselves locked out. Remote Workmates mentions it also welcomes individuals living any corner of the world to join, especially those with mental health wellness issues that mainstream society often ignores. It suggests its digital platform gives members the chance to talk about their situations. However, these two platforms do not have access to the professional mental health services required in SME mental health cases.

Finally, MHScot recommends it covers topics such as listening skill development in their training workshop and suggests that organisations provide an appropriate space within the workplace that is accessible and suitable for private conversations. Its Emotional Culture Workshops are for organisations who want to create a more human and empathetic workplace and employee culture. They consider that positive emotional culture is linked to better performance, quality and customer service also suggests that building a more human and empathetic workplace can give workers the freedom to talk about mental health.

Having face-to-face conversations about workplace culture, emotions and experiences is the main idea behind the Emotional Culture Workshop. MHScot claims it is an "insanely simple" card-based tool for structured face-to-face conversations about workplace culture, emotions and employee experience. It also suggests that emotional culture workshops can build confidence in staff, but these workshops are not free of cost, and SMEs need to take the initiative to arrange these workshops for the staff.

5.3.4 Best Option for Access to Service

Employees can have open conversations about mental health with AI App Woebot Health, and it claims to offer support at any time and stage of a person's journey with their organisation. One of the essential steps to dealing with mental health problems is to encourage employees to open up in the first place. One survey uncovered that out of 1645 employees, 27% feared the negative consequences on their career, 20% of the respondents were worried about the confidentiality of their mental health issues, and 17% were not interested in discussing those issues with anyone at their workplace (Business in the Community, 2019). This indicates a lack of trust, communication and a clear understanding between SME employers and employees, making it extremely challenging to deal with SMEs' mental health issues

Woebot health has the potential to be a platform where staff know that they will not be judged at any level. Once problems are out in the open with the help of Woebot and the permission of the employee, then both employer and employee can begin to work together to find the right solution. One survey revealed that out of more than 12,000 employees, 68% preferred to talk to a chatbot over their supervisor about anxiety and stress at workplace (Oracle and Workplace Intelligence, 2020). Furthermore, the findings of a community mental health survey revealed that mental health services must be convenient for those with any kind of mental health problems, whereby the use of technology was found to be most useful to improve the services' convenience (NICE, 2020). This suggests that staff should have access to a 24/7 accessible platform such as Woebot Health, where they can start open conversations about mental health.

To be qualified for the best option in this research, case organisations need to satisfy maximum service characteristics of the Access to Services (AS) standard. Research interview data and secondary data reveal that Woebot app satisfies the maximum criteria to be the most satisfactory option for this standard. Moreover, Woebot stands out among other cases because the organisation claims it can support employees 24/7 with an accessible digital platform. In that way, there would be support available when employees are struggling at regular intervals throughout employment. Other cases, standing at the 'Good For' position in the Likert Scale only help firms with available digital resources, which do not ensure 24/7 one to one mental health support. 'Not Good For' case organisations do not fulfil the characteristics of the AS standard. This analysis strongly justifies that Woebot can be the best service organisation among all the cases when it comes to helping SMEs with AS standard.

5.3.5 Blend of options to support access to services

Among three options, the blend of services of AI organisations and government-brokered organisations can positively change access to mental health services at SME workplaces. AI options such as Woebot Health can help solve employees' issues with trust and communication. Recent research suggests that employees prefer to talk to a robot over their manager concerning mental health issues at work. Furthermore, studies have demonstrated that when CBT is used with RTW interventions at the individual level, it gives a better result, which includes enhanced work satisfaction, less psychological distress and depression (Corbière et al., 2009). CBT can accelerate the process of RTW by an average of 2 weeks (Bruinevls et al., 2007). Woebot Health is a CBT-based AI option that can also accelerate an earlier RTW.

Currently, government-based organisations are not directly providing any mental health intervention services. However, the Scottish Government (2020) has decided to introduce a new CBT platform. This computerised CBT platform will increase the number of treatment options from one to twelve. The Scottish Government will also implement the most comprehensive workforce specialist service in the UK, which will be able to deliver specialist support in complex cases while maintaining confidentiality (The Scottish Government, 2020). With their current supervisory activities, government-brokered organisations can create advantages by tagging with services such as the Workforce Specialist Service and supplying AI-based CBT services to help SMEs.

Blending the citizen-driven social innovation option with other alternatives will not make improvements in SME mental health service access because these platforms do not have access to the professional mental health services required in SME mental health cases.

5.4 What is Meant by Line Management Responsibilities

Line managers and supervisors play a crucial part in organisations' mental well-being. Good health, well-being and improved performance are linked continuously with supportive line management. Meanwhile, weak leadership has been associated with burnout, stress and depression. Good employee management is not always complicated: "At its heart, it is about considering all employees, not resources or a set of performance statistics. Developing a management style that is open, approachable and self-aware goes a long way to improving team members' well-being and performance" (Mind, 2018).

The way organisations support and manage employees undergoing mental health issues can be crucial in influencing how they deal with their problems and improve the situation: "Organisations should provide managers training on mental health and stress management, including spotting the signs and having supportive conversations" (Mind, 2018). Workplaces should have detailed guidelines for supervisors and line managers on supporting employees with mental well-being issues. An organisation should always encourage and enable positive line manager behaviours regarding staff mental well-being.

An organisation should also have a culture where employees can speak to their line manager regarding mental health problems. The line manager should have knowledge about the best help that staff can get personally and professionally to improve their mental health situation:

"Line managers should have access to training which has a significant effect on how they consider the impact of mental health" (Mind, 2018). Training should be handled in a relevant, sensitive and engaging manner and have a positive impact on participants (Mind, 2018). Frequently, the most challenging role for managers is opening a dialogue about the problem related to mental health. Support from case organisations in arranging free training sessions for line managers can significantly benefit small organisations as they lack financial resources.

5.4.1 The actions of AI organisations regarding line management responsibilities

According to MHW website, employers who sign the MHW commitment can facilitate their managers in implementing six standards for their staff. Along with each standard, there are ideas to get managers thinking and tools to get them started, making it easier for big and small organisations to implement each standard and lead change. The firm has a module called "Supporting Each Other" for a small organisation, where the organisation claims SMEs will learn how to assist a co-worker who has mental well-being issues and how to support RTW.

As Mind stresses, "To effectively support staff to recover and return to work as quickly as possible, employers should take a person-centred approach and be sensitive to the individuals need" (Mind, 2018). It suggests it focuses on talking to peers and creating a network with other SME organisations to share ideas and experiences from their workplace regarding employee well-being. Though it supports SME managers through its online module, its mental health services are limited to online resources.

Next, Woebot Health claims it can support organisations by being part of one of the workplace well-being tools. Managers know their workplace environment best; they can be responsible for its implementation in the workplace. Woebot suggests employers who take the Woebot commitment will help their managers implement standards for their employees through their use of the app as a daily logbook. It also suggests that the employer can also focus on practical reports from Woebot, which will give employers a picture of their employees' state of mind. Employers can get that report from employees once they use Woebot for two weeks.

In the work-life section of CIPD's online portal, it discusses the management of mental health: "Being aware and able to spot the symptoms of employees who could potentially suffer from mental health issues is a valuable ability to have as an employer or manager. Not only will it allow managers to offer help and care to their staff early on, but it will also potentially change their life and make a positive impact" (CIPD, 2020). CIPD mentions it attempts to educate

managers about some common signs of mental illness; it suggests it is always worth communicating with any staff members whose managers are alarmed. Managers can educate themselves about the signs of mental illness. CIPD also suggests that employers and managers arrange a virtual workshop for employees. Health Assured can provide a virtual training session on mental health, and it believes that this is a cost-effective manner rather than the alternative, a traditional workshop session. However, its services are limited to CIPD Members, and it is not the most low-cost mental health service for SMEs.

5.4.2 The actions of government-brokered organisations regarding line management responsibilities

See Me suggests it does not provide any manager training, but it does have E-modules focused on stigma and discrimination which are not only for managers but are open for everyone. There are dramatisation opportunities in the E-learning section where people can share their experiences too. After doing the online module, it claims that people become more confident about mental health and open up more about their mental issues.

The organisation further notes that it will "get anonymous data back from the survey, analyse it and provide the concerned organisation with a report. This also includes what training might be useful and what order, to maximise behaviour change and secure sustainability. The initial plan lasts for one year" (See Me, 2020). It also suggests that the employer build a training programme to ensure managers can assist staff in undergoing mental well-being problems. See Me indirectly motivate managers through the action plan and e-module to take care of staff mental well-being

To get support from HWL, the organisation must go through the process of Surveys: "Work Positive is a stress risk management resource that supports employers in identifying and reducing the potential causes of stress in the workplace. The process is aligned with the HSE Management Standards and recognised by HSE as a recommended tool to help work towards the Standards. The Work Positive process involves planning and securing commitment, a questionnaire (to distribute to all staff to allow a comprehensive assessment of the potential causes of stress at work), followed by consultation, action planning, monitoring and review" (HWL, 2020).

HWL suggests that the HWL well-being survey is mandatory, with several questions tailored to the organisation. It is designed to meet the HWL award criteria in full. It also recommends

managers to supervise the whole process of collecting information about staff's health and safety and well-being. HWL provides short courses to managers and supervisors regarding well-being to achieve the confidence to deal with employees. However, they usually consider the health, safety and well-being of an organisation as a whole, which has the potential to undermine the importance of supporting the organisation's mental health.

Finally, Salus believes that training is an essential activity for all organisations and helps provide all levels of employees with fundamental knowledge and skills to perform their roles. Suppose organisations are looking for effective health and safety training for managers or staff. In that case, Salus claims it can facilitate a wide range of health and safety courses, including the IOSH Training Courses. However, their health and safety services may pose a risk of undermining the service significance of mental well-being since Salus's primary focus is on the overall health and safety of organisations.

5.4.3 The actions of citizen-driven organisations regarding line management responsibilities

Vox suggests that the public create a group and join in its movement, which aims to promote a good "fit" between mental health services and laws to ensure that everyone benefit from it and public money is spent wisely: "VOX support individuals to form their own groups to express their experiences in their own words" (VOX Scotland, 2020). In addition, both managers and employers can create a group of their own to share their struggles, needs and experiences. Other than motivating them to join groups, VOX does not provide any type of mental health services to managers and supervisors.

Next, MHScot suggests that managers create a "framework" whereby it can support them to consider what a mental health programme might look like in their organisation – as managers know their workplace environment best, they are responsible for its implementation. They advise management on how to conduct the RTW procedure and provide them with training on reasonable adjustments. MHScot provides support for managers and employees to help colleagues currently suffering from mental illness and enables the affected colleagues to stay at work where it is right to do so. They advise organisations to encourage the workforce to be proactive about the disclosure of mental health issues in the workplace. MHScot has strongly suggested that employers should be aware of their legal responsibilities to care for their employees. They have also advised organisations to conduct regular stress audits. By following the HSE's Management Standards, stress audits can be very effective at providing a preventive

intervention level for the organisations. The only issue is that their service is not free of cost, and SME organisations need a budget for themselves to get any support from MHScot.

Finally, Remote Workmates encourages the public to create groups and join in their movement to promote a good fit between mental and physical health practices. It claims it supports individuals in forming their own channel to convey their struggles, needs and experiences in their own words with other workmates. However, it specifically does not provide any workplace well-being training or services to managers and supervisors.

5.4.4 Best option for supporting line management responsibilities

Government-brokered organisations do help SMEs with the action plan and short e-learning courses. However, it is essential to have a management style that is open, approachable and self-aware, and government organisations must on that part. This plays a significant role in improving team members' well-being and performance. Research shows it can be a real barrier for employees to speak to their managers. The survey results conducted by See Me reveal that employees are not comfortable to talk to their managers; in many cases, the managers are very unapproachable. This indicates that managers need training on how they can build and improve comfortable staff-manager relationships.

Government-brokered organisations should ensure that line managers can access specific training, which has a significant effect on employees' mental health. Training should be conducted in a sensitive, relevant and engaging manner and positively impact managers and supervisors. Lloyd et al. (2017) found that stress, anxiety, depression and emotional exhaustion can be decreased with the help of stress management training programmes. Employers can get stress management training in person from HWL. Organisations that use a coaching setup for a mental health management programme get the best results, followed by classroom training; online and train-the-trainer setups were least effective (Vanhove et al., 2015). In this case, government-brokered organisations such as HWL are better positioned to train managers and supervisors in a physical environment.

To be eligible for the best option in this research, case organisations need to satisfy maximum service characteristics of the Line Manager Responsibilities (AS) standard. Research interview and secondary data revealed that none of the case organisations satisfies the maximum criteria to be the most satisfactory option for this standard. None of the service organisations provides or shares exceptional information regarding LMR standards. Research suggests that to be best

in this option, service organisations need to provide extensive training to line managers so that they can spot the early sign of mental health problems in staff and initiate supportive conversation. Other cases, standing at the 'Good For' position in the Likert Scale only help firms with available digital training resources or stress management courses. 'Not Good For' case organisations do not fulfil the characteristics of the LMR standard. This analysis weekly justifies that Government-brokered organisations or MHW can be effective to achieve the LMR standard.

5.4.5 Blend of options to support line managers in fulfilling mental health responsibilities

Martin et al. (2020) argued that in-person training and resilience training interventions might produce better results than online training. Online interventions are growing rapidly nowadays, which is why more focus should be given to the influence of interpersonal factors while implementing interventions at the workplace (Martin et al., 2020).

Though evidence suggests that classroom training is more effective, the focus should also be placed on online training. It has been noted that most of the SME managers find it difficult to have an effective conversation with their staff because of their busy work patterns and they lack time to give mental health training to colleagues (Panagiotakopoulos, 2011). Therefore, managers can access those short online courses and update themselves with different mental health interventions.

Citizen-driven social innovation organisations do not provide any specific workplace well-being training or services to managers and supervisors. If technology-based or government-brokered organisations blend their line manager training services with social innovation options, then this is unlikely to result in any remarkable improvement.

5.5 What is Meant by Monitoring of Well-being

An organisation should scrutinise their mental health operations to understand how much mental help support employees are getting from them and what factors affect employees' mental well-being (Mind, 2018). Through this process, the employers can get a better idea about their approach and can achieve a better understanding of what is working and where they need more improvement: "Staff survey can be a great tool to capture information about well-being. It will ask the staff about their workload, leadership and management, personal

development opportunities, and internal communication" (Mind, 2018). It is essential for managers to regularly take stock of their staff's mental health, the types of pressure they are under, and how to alleviate these (Mind, 2018). Conducting a regular audit of staff mental health, where they can share their challenges, is one practical solution to this.

Managers can gain a good insight into how their employees are doing by arranging regular one-to-one meetings. Managers can build trust in the staff by conducting routine inspections. This will give the colleagues a chance to raise problems early in their struggle period. Employees can also request a meeting outside the routine plan if they want to discuss anything serious. If the organisation organises a staff survey, which asks about employee experience, organisational culture, and mental health, this can help gather information about the team's well-being (Mind, 2018). SMEs are drivers of innovation, and they usually allocate their time in revenue-building activities. Mental health service providers should help SMEs regularly monitor the well-being of staff

5.5.1 The actions of AI regarding monitoring of well-being

According to research data, service providers such as MHW and CIPD do not have strategies to check on workers' mental health and well-being from their side. However, they help members with information on the adoption of employee wellness action plan programmes. CIPD claims that the online portal of CIPD attempts to train and educate managers and supervisors about the potential signs and symptoms of poor mental health. MHW believes that with the help of a WAP, managers can regularly look out for signs in staff and offer any necessary support. By allowing work teams to draw up a WAP, managers will be able to plan and understand what works and what does not work for the staff.

Mind has explained the importance of a WAP: "A WAP can help employees to develop approaches to support their mental well-being, leading to a reduced likelihood of problems such as work-related stress. If a team member does experience a mental health problem, manager and employee will then both have an idea of the tailored support that could help, or at the least a tool to start that conversation" (Mind, 2018). The manager should regularly review the agreed steps in the WAP with their employees. By doing this, the manager then can help the colleagues to become familiarised with the WAP to reflect their experiences or try new approaches that they might find useful. The colleagues will feel more in control if the manager

allows them to take ownership of the process. MHW provides the WAP form to organisations, but it does not evaluate the process of a regular mental health check by themselves.

Next, Woebot Health claims it helps its users in terms of regular mental health checks. After a brief introduction, the fully automated conversational agent, named Woebot, checks in to ask the user's mood and thoughts and then employs CBT to help reframe thought patterns to improve negative emotions. Woebot also believes it can help SME managers implement standards for their employees using the app as a daily logbook. The employer can also focus on practical reports from Woebot, which will give employers a picture of their employees' state of mind. The organisation suggests that employers can get this report from employees once they have used Woebot for two weeks.

5.5.2 The actions of government-brokered organisations regarding monitoring of well-being

According to research data, SEE ME and Healthy Working Lives encourage organisations to conduct regular checks on their employees. They also encourage managers to have good relationships with their staff so that employees can open up to them. Instead of focusing on the performance issue, they should also try to determine what lies underneath the individual. The organisations also encourage support and supervision. HWL claims it has a free one-day training course for managers on Mentally Healthy Workplaces. It also claims that HWL provides information and examples of the many ways in which workplaces can check and regularly support their staff.

According to research data, Salus does not check workers' mental health and well-being regularly. However, it suggests it helps the organisation with the health assessment of employees. It undertakes pre-placement health screening to ensure prospective new candidates are placed in posts that are compatible with their health needs whilst considering the post's functional requirements. A job description assists them in this process. It believes it is aware that employers may need health assessments or support for organisations, managers and employees.

From the analysis, it can be said that these types of government-brokered organisations cannot perform a regular check on employees because of their capacity limit. Instead, they help organisations with a baseline survey. They review the organisation's mental well-being situation annually. However, SME managers still need regular supervision regarding the well-being monitoring of staff.

5.5.3 The actions of citizen-driven organisations regarding monitoring of well-being

According to research data, Citizen-driven service organisations do not have strategies for checking on workers' mental health and well-being from their side as they do not have a vested interest in service provision. The platform's structure was created so that it can only encourage members to share their experiences in their own words. However, MHScot suggests it does help firms with information on the adoption and monitoring of employee assistance programmes. Using bespoke questionnaires, the companies can undertake confidential staff surveys to assess the overall mental health and well-being of staff in the workplace. However, its services are not free of cost and are thus not entirely suitable for SMEs.

5.5.4 Best option for the monitoring of well-being

The aim of Woebot is that by checking in on mental and behavioural health daily, it can help its clients open up on mental health-related issues. Though it is a virtual assistant, it is programmed to identify clients' state of mind by chatting with them, and it can provide CBT support. AI Options such as Woebot can be beneficial to staff for the regular monitoring of well-being. Low-cost mental health services are most appropriate for SMEs as they will reassure employers to take initiatives within budget (Deloitte, 2017). For example, Woebot Health suggests that it can offer scalable solutions that can improve the team's behavioural health. It believes that it can help more organisations to make a scalable income, which will create opportunities for organisations to experience the services of Woebot at a low cost.

With the escalating scalability, sophistication and efficiency of technology-based platforms for depression, recognising and treating individuals' mental health problems in the digital spaces has become more manageable (Eichstaedt et al., 2018). To ensure speedy and effective treatment, the early intervention of mental health problems is mandatory. Traditional mental health practices depend heavily on professionals and individuals to examine and report symptomatic changes. AI options such as Woebot Health can notice related signs and act as a mechanism of early detection.

To be qualified for the best option in this research, case organisations need to satisfy maximum service characteristics of the Monitoring of Wellbeing (MOW) standard. Research interview data and secondary data reveal that Woebot app satisfies the maximum criteria to be the most satisfactory option for this standard. Woebot stands out among other cases because the organisation claims it can monitor employees 24/7 with an accessible digital platform.

Moreover, Woebot also believes it can help SME managers with its daily logbook system and mental health report generation approach. Other cases, standing at the 'Good For' position in the Likert Scale only help firms with the annual organisation mental health report, which do not ensure one to one mental health monitoring support. 'Not Good For' case organisations do not fulfil the characteristics of the MOW standard. This analysis strongly justifies that Woebot can be the best service organisation among all the cases when it comes to supporting SMEs with MOW standard.

5.5.5 Blend of Options for the Monitoring of Well-being

Among the three options, the blend of services of AI organisations and government-brokered organisations can positively change the monitoring of well-being at SME workplaces. Detecting patients at an initial phase in their mental problems through an appropriate means of detection creates chances for patients to be more immediately provided with the right care resources (Eichstaedt et al., 2018). With the growing integration of digital platforms and the algorithmic analysis of phone sensors, unique opportunities are becoming available to detect mental health issues (Saeb et al., 2015). Woebot health uses NLP and AI techniques to identify and adjust to a person's emotional condition and cognitive power, encouraging them to observe their mood and exercise established treatments. Woebot can also help SME managers monitor the well-being of employees using the app as a daily journal. Woebot can generate a practical mental health report, which will give employers a picture of their employees' state of mind.

The pattern government-brokered organisations follow to monitor the organisation's mental welling can also be blended with AI options. They recruit data directly from employees and adjust WPs for the organisation. Newman et al. (2015) reported a worksite wellness intervention targeting small businesses where they provided free, company-specific advice in design and execution, and 21% responded to the follow-up survey. Multiple approaches to engagement to well-being improvement programmes are required to track the employees' well-being state. See Me has a tool called 'let's chat' that encourages managers to regularly talk to their employees about mental health, particularly to those showing signs of mental health problems.

Citizen-driven social innovation organisations do not provide any specific workplace wellness monitoring services to managers and supervisors. Therefore, if technology-based or

government-brokered organisations blend their monitoring strategies with social innovation options, it is unlikely to result in remarkable improvements to SME employees' mental health.

5.6 What is Meant by Employee Control and Purpose

It is essential for some people to feel that other workmates value their relationship and support them to remain cheerful after a difficult workday: "Right working conditions inspire loyalty and high performance from staff. Plus, it can prevent people from developing new mental health problems and support those living with them to thrive" (Mind, 2018). The managers' duty is to check-in frequently with workmates to establish their mental state and control what triggers stress in work-life: "If communication is clear, open, effective, manageable, and responsive, the staff will be able to access all the information they need to do their job while avoiding overload" (Mind, 2018). Mind also notes that staff need to believe that they are supported and valued and that their job plays a significant role in the workplace. Service organisations do not have direct control over staff well-being, but they can train managers to value their employees.

5.6.1 The actions of AI organisations regarding supporting employees with control and purpose

Self-care for mental health is mentioned in MHW's e-learning training. There is a module called "Looking After Yourself for Mental Health". This module is designed especially for SME Workplaces. In it, staff can learn about well-being and how it is related to mental health, and how some of the challenges they face by working in a smaller organisation can affect their well-being. MHW suggest that it also focuses on certain techniques such as mindfulness and relaxation, which employees can use to maintain good well-being.

Woebot mentions self-care to its users through the daily conversation session. It suggests it covers the self-care topic, which aims to help users recognise the significance of self-care and how it can make them more active, enthusiastic and optimistic about life. For those who are interested in technology, having an app that teaches self-care is a cost-effective method

CIPD mentions about self-care for mental well-being in their well-being portal. It covers topics like mindfulness in their emotional health section in the portal. CIPD suggests that mindfulness is the practice of purposely focusing attention and sense on the present moment and accepting

it without judgment. It discusses mindfulness techniques and also mentions that anyone can learn and benefit from these techniques through practice and patience and can control their sense of purpose.

5.6.2 The actions of government-brokered organisations to support employees with control and Purpose

See Me suggests it does not have a direct role in this; it is more of an organisation's internal concern. See Me says it encourages an organisation to maintain an organisational culture where employees can open up. However, HWL mentions self-care in the eLearning training module. It suggests that involving employees in the decision-making processes will improve the processes and help employees feel more valued, involved and empowered.

Next, Salus's clinical, functional capacity-based evaluation assesses the employee's potential to perform a specific job, whether currently in work or absent. It claims it can determine their suitability to perform their current role or a detailed alternative role. The process addresses a range of factors that can interact to influence an employee's ability to work independently in daily functioning, physical capacities, the psychosocial factors that can affect an employee's ability to manage their medical condition. Finally, the evaluation produces a report with conclusions and recommendations for actions to support the employees in the workplace.

Salus claims its job-site evaluation assesses the employees' work environment to make recommendations to help them manage an existing medical condition in the workplace. This involves a visit to the workplace to record the characteristics of the job. This allows the job demands to be compared to their current abilities and for recommendations to be made for appropriate modifications or actions to be taken. Even though Salus mostly deals with the health and safety section, its service process is a good fit for analysing employees' sense and control over their work lives.

5.6.3 The actions of citizen-driven organisations to support employees with control and purpose

MHScot mentions self-care in their training topic several times. It indicates it covers a self-care topic which aims to help participants realise the significance of self-care, make people more efficient, enthusiastic and confident, and take care of their own self, which is essential for achieving their goals. The only issue is many SMEs might not be interested in taking part in training that is not funded.

Meanwhile, VOX indicates it produces a regular members' newsletter (VOXBOX) to foster a sense of community among VOX members, share views on mental health and support the development of an informal network among Scottish mental health organisations (VOX Scotland). People with mental health issues are always welcome to the VOX network as it was created by people who themselves are suffering from mental difficulties. VOX aims to build confidence in members so that they can feel appreciated by their surroundings.

Finally, Remote Workmates mentions their self-image improving seminar for mental well-being. If members want to change the results, they need to change the image through effective education of what is happening and constant spaced repetition of the idea they want to implant. Remote workmates claims it arranges an informative, fun and practical webinar titled "Self-image improving mindset tools and exercises" to teach members how to change their self-image permanently.

5.6.4 Best option for supporting employees with control and purpose

None of the case organisation stands out in terms of helping SMEs to manage employees in a manner that makes them feel supported and valued. AI-based organisations are there to educate employees with their resources. Those resources will give employees the confidence to better deal with mental health issues, but it is the organisation's duty to make employees feel valued at the workplace. It is the managers' duty to check-in regularly with staff to see how they are doing and determine what is causing them stress.

Government-brokered organisations are there to support both employees and employers, but this mostly depends on the organisation's culture and communication: "If communication is transparent, open, effective, manageable, and responsive, the staff will be able to access all the information they need to do their job while avoiding overload" (Mind, 2018). Citizen-driven organisations help employees feel valued, but employees will feel supported if their work is meaningful. A positive culture that values all staff and invests in their skills and development is required, building the trust and integrity essential to maintaining commitment and productivity.

To be eligible for the best option in this research, case organisations need to satisfy maximum service characteristics of the Employee Control and Purpose (ECaP) standard. Research interview and secondary data revealed that none of the case organisations satisfies the maximum criteria to be the most suitable option for this standard. None of the case organisation

stands out in terms of assisting SMEs to manage employees in a manner that it makes them feel supported and valued. Research suggests that to be best in this option, service organisations need to provide extensive training to line managers to help staff maintain work-life balance. Other cases, standing at the 'Good For' position in the Likert Scale only help firms with available training resources to understand self-worth. 'Not Good For' case organisations do not fulfil the characteristics of the ECaP standard. This analysis weekly justifies that case organisations in the position of 'good for' can be effective to achieve ECaP standard.

5.6.5 Blend of options to ensure employee control and purpose

The approach and behaviour of senior managers and employers regarding managing mental health can be upsetting and in some cases unacceptable. However, a complex mix of legal constraints and interventions might be able to change this behaviour (Cerna, 2013). An administrative body such as See Me, HWL or Salus can help and manage the organisation to regularly meet healthy workplace criteria. Organisations can also add AI services in their mental health plan. In a global survey, 68% of the 12,347 respondents responded that they would prefer to talk to a robot over their manager about stress and anxiety at work, and 75% thought AI could improve their mental health and well-being (Oracle and Workplace Intelligence, 2020). In recent years, people have grown more confident that technology innovations can help them in exciting new ways.

Some scholars have preferred to concentrate on social connectivity because feelings of interpersonal connectedness are important for psychological encouragement and have been considered one of the primary characteristics of well-being (Ryff & Singer, 1998). A large body of research has supported this concept that feelings of social connection and related concepts are critical to psychological health and well-being (Pinquart & Sörensen, 2000). Organisations can add citizen-driven social innovation options in their mental health services along with AI-based and government-based interventions. However, Kaplan et al. (2014) examined the efficiency level of social connectedness intervention activity and came to the conclusion that the practice had very little influence on any of the well-being outcomes.

5.7 Integration of Options to Achieve the Six Standards

More inclusive or multi characteristic interventions can produce a more significant impact. Anger et al. (2015) suggest that interventions impact mental health more if the interventions

are more diverse. Managers and staff should therefore tackle organisational, material and working environment-related requirements simultaneously with the help of AI-based and government-brokered organisations. Furthermore, the OH literature has found that intervention users' engagement with and commitment to the process is an essential factor. Müller et al. (2015) suggested that potential research should involve approaches for managers' active engagement of reflection, motivation and behaviour change. Government-brokered organisations provide managers with training regarding behavioural change, which is essential to understand and know more about their staff's mental health.

Stigma reduction interventions provided by government-brokered organisations are efficient in developing supportive behaviour, understanding and knowledge for employees with mental health issues. Furthermore, research has suggested that free face-to-face resilience training intervention and coaching by government-brokered options may have a greater impact than digital training and online courses. Vanhove et al. (2015) observed that training using face-to-face setups is better to train the trainer than online systems. In addition, the strength of the intervention's impacts increases with the number of phases (Theeboom et al., 2014). In that manner, a CBT-based AI intervention programme, such as Woebot Health, can be a useful programme for employees who require constant support for their mental health.

Reviews have suggested that system-wide multicomponent workplace approaches are impactful for organisations' well-being (Martin et al., 2019). An "integrated approach" to employee well-being means that employee mental health interventions should protect the workplace from harm, create awareness, support the positives and react to well-being issues as they are evidenced through work (LaMontagne et al. 2014). Interventions advantageous to reach the six standards are also required to support employees' mental health at the workplace. AI-based and government-based mental health service options fulfil the different supporting workplace benchmarks to establish these standards. Therefore, the integration of these service options can facilitate low cost or free, achievable, multicomponent interventions.

5.8 Costs and Benefits of Different Mental Health Stakeholders

In this research, the practical context is SME mental health service provision, for which there are significant theory and political aspects associated with the spectrum of options. These three

options reflect the different paradigms and perspectives on SME mental health. All the options have their costs and benefits in terms of addressing the mental health of SMEs.

5.8.1 Costs and benefits of AI or technology-based stakeholders

The development of and preference for AI and chatbots (Diamandis & Kotler, 2020) represents a paradigm of mental health as a biologically grounded phenomenon. This views mental health as a brain disease that can be fixed with science and professional solutions. Technologies managed by large global organisations (Medical Futurist, 2019), whether pharmaceutical or information technology organisations, are the main agents shaping solutions for people. In effect, AI captures and replicates professional expertise without human (professional) mediation.

Purposefully checking and communicating with employees regularly with each of the direct issues is considered more critical than ever. In one study, nearly 40% of global employees said they were deprived of their employers' emotional support (Greenwood & Krol, 2020). The same study showed that personnel who felt their supervisors were not good at emotional interaction were 23% more likely than others to experience mental health decline. However, another study revealed that 82% of participants said they would get better support from a chatbot than humans, and rather than consulting their manager about stress and anxiety, 68% would prefer to talk to a robot (Oracle and Workplace Intelligence, 2020). It, therefore, appears that increasing numbers of employees are turning towards AI or digital-based services to support their mental health.

A survey of 2,000 UK employees showed that most of the respondents mentioned that technologies in different forms help them manage their mental health and well-being (Muller-Heyndyk, 2018). Different AI and digital case organisations help the workplace in distinctive ways. For example, MHW works with the FSB and small businesses, charities and other organisations across the UK to ensure that their resources work for small organisations. It suggests that each topic in its platform regarding SMEs can be covered and completed independently and it includes a range of facts and short informative videos and links to valuable resources and support. Meanwhile, Woebot Health uses a CBT chatbot to change the user's mind by providing perspective and cultivating attention until they have replaced bad habits with better ones. Furthermore, CIPD provides members with free help and support 24/7 via telephone or online platform. Easy access and availability could therefore be the main reason behind employees' favourable reviews of AI or digital-based mental health services.

The modern generation is used to a fast-paced lifestyle and mostly prefer online services for everything. Many specialists think that this modern age group will be able to relate to CBT through apps like Woebot quite easily. Woebot is an affordable software that provides private sessions and does not need to be pre-booked. Sometimes, people find it difficult or feel embarrassed to share their difficult experiences with another human. In contrast, consumers feel more comfortable sharing their experiences with simulated online assistants because they feel less judged.

In terms of the cost of using AI-based services, Stephenson and Farmer (2017) suggested that increasing employer transparency presents the most significant prospect to encourage superior scope and depth of employer action on mental health. SME employers and managers need to be transparent in their activities while using AI-based services as there is no direct third party supervision for employees. Mental health chatbots and therapy apps are still in their very early stages, requiring extensive research and restructuring to ensure patients' proper treatment. There is, therefore, potential risk of oversimplifying the conditions and mental health recommendations through such services. AI and digital-based service organisations can offer scalable solutions that can improve the team's behavioural health by providing something SMEs want to engage with and use. However, organisations' action should be transparent, and they should be careful about using premature AI-based options.

5.8.2 Costs and benefits of social innovation-based stakeholders

In this research spectrum, the paradigm of labelling people with defined mental health problems as different and deviant and stigmatising them is itself unhealthy and part of the problem. There is a long-standing movement to relabel mental health issues in less stigmatising ways. How people behave is less a sign of disease and more a form of reaction to troubling environments. Such behaviours may be alarming in a crisis but are not in themselves to be judged adversely or as a sign of a problem that needs to be eliminated. Preferably, "solutions" may be possible through refreshed positive relationships, compassion, care and love (Hunter 2018). Approaches involving close engagement with other people and healing communities among those with shared similar experiences are therefore beneficial options (Icarus 2019).

In one study, Greenfield et al. (2008) found that individuals who were supported in a peer-run mental health centre during the crisis had enhanced progress in distress and improved mental health service satisfaction. Support from like-minded people or peers help individuals across

mental health diagnostic categories to feel more confident, efficient and empowered (Davidson et al., 2017). Furthermore, Longden et al. (2018) suggested that offering a safe, collective environment in which individuals gather to share coping tactics, exchange perception and understandings and support one another's experiences can encourage greater tolerance for a stigmatised mental health condition. Many people think that where medical treatment is insufficient to treat their emotional side, a health-related support group can fill that void (Pomery et al., 2016). These studies have suggested that humans need to be engaged with and involved in solving their own problems.

Considerable research suggests that feelings of belongingness and being a part of a social association can be crucial for mental health and well-being (Pinquart & Sörensen, 2000). In this study, case organisations' service provisions were analysed and the results indicate that none of the organisations can support SME workplaces exclusively to provide mental health service. VOX supports individuals and groups and works with members to ensure that their views are listened by the Scottish Government. VOX Scotland and Remote Workmates ensure that they supplement individual members' views by representing the broader range of opinions gathered by their platforms.

The findings of this research indicate that social innovation-based or self-directed networks do not provide mental health services that ensure all six standards are met. These organisations mostly do not offer individual advocacy; they do not provide specialist mental health services such as helping organisations make mental health work plans, monitoring employees' well-being, or providing access to services. At best, they represent members' views to government, parliament, the NHS and the wider society and support and enable members to express their views in their own words. The only way in which they can help organisations is to offer a safe, cooperative environment in which peers can gather to support one another's experiences and feel more confident, efficient and empowered. This way, these organisations can help employees provide strong control and purpose at the workplace and help SMEs establish at least one of the six standards.

5.8.3 Cost and benefits of government-based stakeholders

In this study, there is a third paradigm and perspective in between AI-based and social innovation-based options; social agents, especially involving government control of health

care, can and need to use resources responsibly to provide or broker services for mental health. They work with other public and third sector agencies (charities) to establish a low cost and high volume solutions. McDaid (2017) recommended that the government provide mental health services collaboration with healthcare professionals and other charity organisations to increase NHS and public health organisations' capacity to deal with mental health issues increase effectively.

In terms of the benefits of government-based stakeholders, Stephenson and Farmer (2017) suggested that it is possible to measure the mental health actions of an employer. Enhanced transparency will therefore help develop a measurement culture that will create voluntary rating systems to help drive accountability and further progress. Ingrained this in the process, government-brokered organisations such as See Me, HWL and Salus are trying to give mental health support to organisations by making mental health work plans, providing training to line managers and annually monitoring and reviewing services in the workplace.

See Me promotes employee distance programmes for mental health, but it believes that it is not feasible for SMEs to join them. Moreover, researchers have found that classroom mental health training was less effective than programmes using a coaching format. (Vanhove et al., 2015). Martin et al. (2019) indicated that online training might not be as prolific as face-to-face coaching and resilience training interventions. The interview with See Me in this study revealed that face-to-face training and conversation significantly changes the staff's attitude toward mental health. Researchers have also emphasised that having personal interactions with employees and establishing a good relationship is crucial for workplace well-being training (Martin et al., 2019).

Government-brokered organisations provide different products and services to help the organisation supporting mental health. See Me hears from many employers that the business cases are more influential when it comes to managing workplace mental health. The senior manager can see the pound-to-pound impact that this can have in terms of sickness absence or cost of recruitment with the help of a cost calculator provided by See Me. Meanwhile, HWL and Salus provide on-site health and well-being assessment and generate reports for employees to rectify concerns. Government-brokered organisations also work closely and collaboratively with each other. For example, See Me compared some of its survey questions with HWL's

survey to avoid duplication. This was a significant piece of work for them to collaborate on the survey questionnaires of two different programmes. After the collaboration, they were able to examine the data on a broader level. As government-brokered organisations always struggle in capacity building, these organisations are attempting to move forward to influence rather than deliver services.

Government brokered organisations are in a position where they also feel the need to incline towards digital facilities to build service capacity. In a conversation with See Me, they mentioned that their sustainability is positively related to building capacity by sharing online resources. In the same way, Salus recently developed an online referral and reporting system. This online referral reporting system is already in operation. The Scottish Government (2020) has also decided to introduce a new cCBT platform. They suggest that this computerised CBT platform will increase the mental health treatment options from one to twelve. The Scottish Government also mentioned in their plan that they would implement a comprehensive Workforce Specialist Service in the UK, which will be able to deliver specialist support in complex cases and will maintain confidentiality (The Scottish Government, 2020). There is a drive from the government towards digitalising services to increase capacity to serve workforces. Integration of AI or digital-based and government-based options can help create more capacity to manage mental health six standards of SME workplaces effectively.

5.9 Summary of Analysis and Discussion Chapter

This chapter identified the best possible approaches to effective mental health services in SMEs. Public sources on the cases available online and in other publications were used to analyse the services offered to determine the optimum model. In this case, a combination and blend of approaches were found to be appropriate. The analysis provides a perspective on the drive to provide technological support to SMEs to create low cost, scalable constant interventions in the workplaces. However, some services are better provided by a human. This chapter also discusses the costs and benefits of service organisations and how all the options have their own advantages and disadvantages.

Chapter 6:

Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter aims to present the conclusions drawn from the result of the analysis of the secondary data and interview and then make recommendations for further research.

6.1 Conclusions

This study aimed to establish a comparative analysis of how innovations may provide low cost or free mental health services options to SMEs. An initial review of the literature showed how mental health services provisions in SME workforces benefit from a wide range of options. This addressed both workplace effectiveness and broader social concerns about health and equalities in organisations. Six standards for mental health services were considered as the prime scope and focus for improving mental health services to SMEs. Reaching workforces and implementing these standards in SMEs is driving innovation. However, these innovations must be low cost or no cost to SME workplace. To describe and compare options, this study aimed to access examples of service provision in Scotland. A spectrum of service option innovations, from AI and digital-based through to government-based and social innovation-based service organisations, were identified to map these options.

Cases of each option were articulated with the collection of policy documentation on service performance. Public sources such as online web pages and other publications that show the services offered were described and analysed through cross-case synthesis. This provided data enabling the options to be evaluated with respect to the workplace six standards on a scale as 'best for', 'good for' and 'not good for' concerning the standards. After the analysis stage, it was concluded that no one type of case from the three options perfectly fulfils the criteria to achieve mental health six standards for SMEs.

In terms of the findings, this study acknowledged that AI or chatbots treat mental health as a brain disease that can be fixed with science or professional solutions. However, as social

beings, people have the urge for emotional support from another human. It is only natural for a human being to be more open and have better conversations with another human than AI. Indeed, recent studies show that nearly 40% of employees globally think that they do not get any emotional support from their employers (Greenwood & Krol, 2020). Surprisingly, other studies have shown that rapidly increasing number of employees nowadays think robots can better support their mental health than humans. Employees now prefer to communicate with AI or robots more than their managers about stress and anxiety at work. In this vein, this research has determined that different AI and digital-based mental health service organisations can be used as a practical solution in achieving some of the six standards. AI-based organisations perform better than two other options – government-based and citizen-driven organisations – in terms of creating employee awareness, ensuring easy access to their clients and monitoring, and achieving the six standards.

In contrast to AI and Chatbot's perception of mental health, there is a long-standing movement to relabel mental health issues. People's ill behaviour reflects their surroundings, environment and backgrounds rather than mental disease. In recent studies, researchers have found that peer-run mental health centres have benefited individuals during a crisis. Like-minded peers help individuals with mental health issues feel more confident and empowered (Davidson et al., 2012). However, in this research, the analysis showed that these citizen-driven organisations do not ensure the promotion of the six mental health standards at the workplace. They do not provide services such as WPS, nor do they monitor employees' wellbeing or provide access to services. The only way social innovation-based organisations help their clients is by offering a safe, cooperative environment in which peers can gather to support each other and feel more confident, efficient and empowered. In this manner, the self-directed networks can only ensure one of the six standards, the one which provides employees with strong control and purpose at their workplaces.

Finally, government-based organisations collaborate with other public and third sector agencies (charities) to provide low cost and high-volume mental health solutions to employers. Government-brokered organisations are trying to give mental health support to SME workplaces by making WPs, providing training to line managers and annually monitoring and reviewing workplace services. In addition to these services, organisations such as See Me also offer advanced solutions such as a cost calculator. This calculator helps employers to understand the impact of sickness absence or cost of recruitment and focuses on how

employees' mental health can benefit employers in the long run. Capacity building has always been a struggle for government-brokered organisations, so they are focusing more on influencing rather than delivering services.

Overall, this study's significance was to identify the optimal low-cost approach to effective mental health services in SMEs. Recent systematic evidence reviews regarding effective workplace interventions suggest that system-wide multicomponent workplace approaches are impactful for organisations' wellbeing (Martin et al., 2019). Integrated approaches to employee wellbeing are considered to protect the workplace from harm, create awareness, support the positive and react to wellbeing issues as they evince through work (LaMontagne et al. 2014). This study indicates that a combination and blend of low-cost, easy access approaches is appropriate for SMEs to achieve all six mental health standards. Therefore, this research provides a valuable perspective on the drive to provide technological or AI-based support to SMEs to create low-cost scalable interventions in the workplaces with the help of the direct supervision of government-brokered options.

6.2 Limitations of the Study

It should be borne in mind that the study has several limitations. Most of these limitations occurred because of the COVID-19 pandemic:

- Employee perspectives on the three options – the AI tool, the government-brokered services, and the self-help options – were not collected.
- It was not possible to conduct interviews with representatives of the three main options listed above. See Me was the only interviewee, and the researcher managed to collect primary data from them.
- The possibility of bias exists as only one organisation was interviewed. However, the collection of secondary data has been discussed in a transparent manner throughout this study.
- In the early stage of the research design, it was decided to collect primary data through interviews to gather a retrospective view of case organisations. Hence, only

one set of interview data and mostly secondary data from public sources was used, i.e. online web pages and other publications.

6.3 Recommendations

This research proposes several recommendations:

- The findings of this study reveal that the practice of AI-based services for mental health is increasing nowadays; service organisations think they can improve service capacity through AI facilities. This research further indicates that it can be possible to achieve some of the six standards through AI platforms. Further research should be done to ascertain if SME organisations should make AI or digital-based mental health support services mandatory for their workplace mental health programme.
- The research also suggests that employees need emotional support at the workplace, but they do not open up to their employers or managers because of mental health stigma. In most cases, it is challenging to eliminate the stigma in the workplace because of the long-standing culture. There are opportunities for further research to establish if employees are more comfortable using AI platforms to share their stress, anxiety and stigma at workplaces.
- SME organisations are not taking advantage of the available free and low-cost mental health services to the fullest. Mental health service organisations should make strategies to attract SME organisations to use their easy access, low-cost and free service options. More research is therefore required to determine the factors that would attract SMEs to use low-cost mental health services.
- There is a risk of oversimplifying the conditions and mental health recommendations through AI-based mental health services. AI-based services are still in the early development stage. There should be further research on the control and supervision of AI-based services.
- Citizen-driven or social innovation service organisations are formed to provide peer support, boost individuals' confidence and empower them. Further research is required to establish if these organisations can help employees achieve mental health standards in the workplace.

- There is usually a long interval between evaluations for the government-brokered organisations' review processes. Research could help determine if organisations can collaborate with AI organisations to review on a monthly or quarterly basis.
- There is scope for further research on how employer and employees react to different mental health service options under SME setups.
- Current service options for mental health provisions are not able to fulfil all six standards individually. Studies have indicated that a multicomponent intervention could be a solution for addressing the mental health crisis at the workplace. A combination and blend of approaches from AI-based, government-brokered and citizen-driven organisations could be a solution. More research is needed on this.
- If SMEs can access all kinds of low-cost support under one platform, they will be motivated to use the services more frequently. There will be less pressure on one type of service organisation to deliver the standards. Service organisations may achieve and retain more clients, and they may be able to offer scalable solutions which will improve their sustainability. Further research could establish if this is correct.
- Mental health charities and support organisations such as Mind emphasise using AI-based and government-brokered or citizen-driven services together to tackle workplace mental health six standards through their research and reports. Government should patronise these organisations so that more evaluation on integration can be done to come to a concrete solution.
- Further research should be conducted to establish if the findings of this study differ significantly between small enterprises and medium enterprises. There is a large range between all the firms in “SMEs” and so further research could be welcome here.
- There is a need for broader integration of mental health services options and perhaps there is a role for an external regulator such as HSE in creating an enhanced institutional foundation. External regulators can help SMEs develop positive mental health policies, training and strategies by monitoring the areas that need consideration.

6.4 Final Words

This study significantly identified the optimal approach to effective mental health services in SMEs. The study indicates that to practically achieve mental health six standards, integration and blend of low-cost approaches are appropriate for SME workforces. The study also offers a perspective on the drive to provide technological support to SMEs to create scalable

interventions in the workplace with government-brokered and self-help mental health service organisations. My own view, today, is that integration of different mental health service options can make a beneficial impact in protecting SME mental health in Scotland.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Case Template and Initial Interview Questions

Overview; What The Organization Does and their Motivation

Section 1; What they do with respect to the six standards?

- Make a mental health at work plan and tell workers about it.
- Make sure that workers know about mental health.
- When workers find things hard, give them the chance to talk about mental health and the help and support they can get.
- Make sure workers have control and a sense of purpose about their work. Working should make people feel good.
- Make sure that managers and supervisors manage people properly.
- Make regular checks on workers' mental health and their wellbeing.

Section 2; What they say or think about their approach

- What works; show which help/support works best,
- Is their approach inclusive of trades unions, industry groups and other professional bodies?
- How significant is a Technological aspect/solution to this? Employers using computer programs and websites
- Is there a Business Case; policies on stress and mental health are not only moral but include a strong business case
- Do they think there is a need for further policy/legislation? Employers do not always follow their own policies (espouse but not practice) - possibly, a legislative component is needed
- What range/focus of the organisation matters most? What is challenging about the sustainability of a plan for these?

Section 3; Further Data?

- Any in-house evaluations of services?
- Any positive and role model individual or SME company cases?

Appendix II: Information Sheet for Participants and Consent Form

Information Sheet for Participant

An Invitation to Participate in research on Mental Health Services for SME workplaces; Options for Scotland

My name is Sanjana Sanom, and I am a doctoral student from the School of Business and Creative Industries at the University of West of Scotland. As part of my degree, I am undertaking a research project. The title of my project is:

Mental Health Services for SME Workplaces: Options for Scotland

This study will interview people who work in organisations working towards creating mentally healthy workplaces, specifically for SMEs in Scotland.

Interviews will aim to establish what is done by your organisation with respect to SMEs and (Stevenson and Farmer Review 2017) and also aim to explore what experiences are in your organisation with respect to themes emerging from The Mental Health Foundation recent report on the Scottish context (Mental Health Foundation 2018 Report).

I am looking for volunteers to participate in the project. There are no criteria (e.g. gender, age, or health) for being included or excluded – everyone is welcome to take part.

I am not aware of any risks associated with this project. The entire process should take no longer than 30 minutes. You will be free to withdraw from the interview at any stage; you would not have to give an explanation.

All data will be anonymised as much as possible, but you may be identifiable from tape recordings of your voice. Your name will be replaced with a participant number or a pseudonym, and it will not be possible for you to be identified in any reporting of the data gathered. All data collected will be kept in a secure safe cabinet in a locked room on a pc which

is password protected, to which only I have access. These will be held till the end of the examination process, following which all data that could identify you will be destroyed.

If you are able to help in this way, I will be able to provide you with my analysis and findings prior to any official publication of the study. The results may be published in a journal or presented at a conference.

If you have read and understood this information sheet, any questions you had have been answered, and you would like to be a participant in the study, please feel free to contact me or my supervisor, Dr Stephen Gibb.

<p>Sanjana Sanom</p> <p>Doctoral Student, University of West of Scotland</p> <p>Email: [REDACTED]</p>
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<p>Dr Stephen Gibb FCIPD</p> <p>Senior Lecturer, School of Business and Creative Industries, UWS</p>

Consent Form

The University of West of Scotland requires that all persons who participate in research studies give their written consent to do so. Please read the following and sign it if you agree with what it says.

1. I voluntarily and freely consent to be a participant in the research project on the topic of Mental Health Services for SME Workplaces conducted by Sanjana Sanom, a doctoral student at the University of West of Scotland.
2. The broad goal of this research study is to explore the experiences of organisations working towards creating mentally healthy workplaces, specifically for SMEs in Scotland. Specifically, I have been asked to take part in the procedure, which should take no longer than 30 minutes to complete.

3. I have been told that my name will not be disclosed and will not be linked with the research materials. I have also been advised that my responses will be anonymised and I will not be identifiable in any report produced by the researcher.
4. I also understand that if I feel unable or unwilling to continue during the interview, I am free to leave. My participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and I may withdraw from it without negative consequences.
5. In addition, I can decline to answer any particular question or questions if I don't feel comfortable to answer.
6. I have been allowed to ask questions regarding the interview, and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
7. I have read and understood the above and consent to participate in this study. My signature is not a waiver of any legal rights. Furthermore, I know that I will be able to keep a copy of the informed consent form for my records.

Participant's Signature

Date

I have explained and defined in detail the research procedure in which the respondent has consented to participate. Furthermore, I will retain one copy of the informed consent form for my records.

Researcher's Signature

Date

Appendix III: Template Analysis Checklist

Serial		Complete	Date	Remarks
1	The primary analysis of Secondary data and Interview Data			
2	Data Coding			
3	Composition of Themes and Association			
4	Import Data to Case Template			
5	Revision of Data			
6	Findings			

Appendix IV: Secondary Data Sources

Types of Sources	Topic	Details & Link
Website	Healthy Working Lives	https://www.healthyworkinglives.scot/Pages/default.aspx
Government Publication Report	Health and work strategy: review report	<p>Review considers mental health emergent risks and the approach that needs to be taken to health and work in Scotland. In doing so it sets out four policy themes underpinned by a series of health and work principles and discusses about Healthy Working Lives services.</p> <p>https://www.gov.scot/publications/fair-healthy-work-review-scottish-governments/pages/1/</p>
Government Publication Report	Health Works A review of the Scottish Government's Healthy Working Lives Strategy A report on implementation May 2013	<p>In 2009 the Scottish Government undertook a review of its health and work strategy and published Health Works, which outlined a range of actions for improvement. This report details the progress and outcomes of these actions three years on.</p> <p>https://www.gov.scot/publications/health-works-review-scottish-governments-healthy-working-lives-strategy-report-implementation-2013/pages/6/</p>
Government Publication Report	Health Works: A Review of the Scottish Government's Healthy Working Lives Strategy , 2009	<p>Health Works is a review of the Scottish Government's Healthy Working Lives Strategy.</p> <p>https://www.webarchive.org.uk/wayback/archive/20170401173616/http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2009/12/11095000/18</p>
Public Health Scotland Publication Report	Evaluation of the SCHWL support to employers and Healthy Working Lives Award Programme: Telephone Survey Report	<p>The purpose of this evaluation is to test the contribution to employers made by the Scottish Centre for Healthy Working Lives (SCHWL) through two key areas of its activity. The first is its services to employers, the second is the HWL Award Programme.</p> <p>http://www.healthscotland.com/documents/5784.aspx</p>

<p>NHS Health Scotland Project Report</p>	<p>Evaluation of the Scottish Centre for Healthy Working Lives Services to Support Employers and Healthy Working Lives Award Programme: Final Report</p>	<p>The evaluation report seeks to assess the impact of services that are provided to support employers and the Healthy Working Lives (HWL) award programme by identifying changes in their policies, procedures, behaviours and organisational performance. http://eprints.gla.ac.uk/87025/</p>
<p>Public Health Scotland Publication Report</p>	<p>Evaluation of the Scottish Centre for Healthy Working Lives Workplace Services and Award Programme - A Theory of Change Approach Initial Report</p>	<p>The focus of this 3-year evaluation is the Workplace Services and Award Programme offered by the Scottish Centre for Healthy Working Lives (SCHWL), a subset of its wide-ranging activities that seek to create a healthier and more motivated workforce across Scotland. https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Evaluation-of-the-Scottish-Centre-for-Healthy-Lives-Glass-MacKenzie/a2b1135c31f65a22c9a227767508565ec55487e8</p>
<p>Research Report by Pauline Cameron Consultancy & School of Business and Management, University of Glasgow</p>	<p>Effective diffusion and adoption of healthy working practices : a feasibility study</p>	<p>Report of a feasibility study which aimed to establish the parameters of a potential healthy working practices demonstration and research project and ensure that the research focused on answering the right questions. https://lx.iriss.org.uk/sites/default/files/resources/GCPHreportEffectiveDiffusionandAdoptionofHealthyWorkingPracticesFINALREPORT_FINAL.pdf</p>

Scholarly Journal	Healthy Working Lives: the Scottish Strategy for Improving Health in the Workplace	<p>many of the changes in the delivery of occupational safety and health in Scotland have originated in the public sector, through the Scottish health department, and indeed these developments have often influenced the UK agenda. This chapter describes the Scottish situation and its response to UK legislation, with emphasis on Scottish developments and innovation</p> <p>https://www.proquest.com/openview/855b669a5971d4a0eb143d3b358d1fd9/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=1226336</p>
Strategic Report	Strategic Plan for Health, Safety and Care	<p>The purpose of this strategic document is to set out what Falkirk Council aims to achieve in terms of Health, Safety & Care throughout 2007-2010 and healthy working lives is a part of the plan.</p> <p>https://www.falkirk.gov.uk/employees/policies/docs/health-safety-care/Strategic%20plan%20for%20health%2C%20safety%20and%20care.pdf?v=201906271131</p>
Strategy Report	Your Health: Staff Health Strategy 2011-2014 NHS Greater Glasgow & Clyde and Glasgow City Council	<p>The aim of this Staff Health Strategy is to improve the health and wellbeing of our staff. It will do this by improving working conditions, increasing the availability of healthy lifestyle choices, and building capacity for health improvement. This strategy aims to fulfil the aspirations of both organisations to be exemplar public sector employers. Healthy Working lives is part of the health strategy.</p> <p>https://glasgow.gov.uk/CHttpHandler.ashx?id=11222&p=0</p>
Website	See Me Scotland	https://www.seemescotland.org/
Research Report	See Me Evaluation Report 2020/21: Outcomes Focused Evaluation	<p>This summative report is an overview of the final year of Phase 2 of the See Me Scotland programme (April 2020 – March 2021)</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/See%20Me%20Evaluation%20Report%202020-21_FINAL.pdf</p>
Research Report	See Me evaluation and Learning: What Helps to tackle Stigma and Discrimination on Phase 2	<p>This paper presents an overview of what works to tackle stigma and discrimination (the mechanisms of change) drawing on learning from across Phase 2 of the programme. The evidence for each mechanism of change is based on the evaluation of a number of projects and initiatives across programmatic areas.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/See%20Me%20What%20Works%20paper%202020-21%20FINAL.pdf</p>

<p>Evaluation Report by Mental Health Foundation</p>	<p>See Me Scotland: building on what works to tackle mental health stigma and discrimination</p>	<p>This summary briefing paper provides insights from the See Me Phase 2 evaluation (2016-2019) into a fresh perspective on what we know works to tackle mental health stigma and discrimination. It builds on existing evidence in the form of the mechanisms for change that work to support successful anti stigma and discrimination initiatives and that contribute to the efforts to challenge stigma and discrimination when and where it is identified.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/What%20Works%20Briefing%20Paper%202020_0.pdf</p>
<p>See Me Workplace Programme Evaluation Report</p>	<p>SEE ME WORKPLACE: THREE YEAR PROGRAMME EVALUATION NOVEMBER 2016 - OCTOBER 2019</p>	<p>A mixed methods was applied to the evaluation of the See Me in Work programme. Both qualitative and quantitative data were gathered to assess whether the medium-term outcomes relevant to the See Me in Work programme are being met.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/Three%20Year%20Phase%20%20Evaluation%20Reports_See%20Me%20-%20Workplace%20-%20Final%20Version.pdf</p>
<p>See Me communication Programme Evaluation Report</p>	<p>SEE ME - THREE YEAR COMMUNICATIONS EVALUATION REPORT NOVEMBER 2016 - OCTOBER 2019</p>	<p>A mixed methods Research approach was applied to the evaluation of the See Me Communications. Qualitative, quantitative and secondary data were gathered to evaluate the role of communications within See Me.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/Three%20Year%20Phase%20%20Evaluation%20Reports_See%20Me%20-%20Communications%20-%20Final%20Version.pdf</p>
<p>Evaluation Report</p>	<p>SEE ME CROSS CUTTING THEMES THREE YEAR PROGRAMME EVALUATION NOVEMBER 2016 - OCTOBER 2019</p>	<p>This report presents the cross-cutting themes and issues that have emerged over the past three years. It is part of a suite of six aligned reports, with the remaining five reports providing insight into successes and learning from the See Me programmatic areas: Social movement, Workplace, Education and Young People, Health and Social Care, and Communications.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/Three%20Year%20Phase%20%20Evaluation%20Reports_See%20Me%20-%20Cross%20Cutting%20Themes%20-%20Final%20Version.pdf</p>

<p>Evaluation Report</p>	<p>Evaluation briefing paper: Summary of the See Me Phase Two Evaluation (2016-2019)</p>	<p>The summary Report highlights the findings of the evaluation of Phase 2 of the See Me programme (2016-2019). The evaluation was carried out by the Mental Health Foundation in Scotland to critically evaluate the programme and provide insights into achievements and areas for growth. This summary is organised by the five See Me programme areas: Education and Young People, Social Movement, Health and Social Care, Workplace and Communications; followed by crossprogrammatic findings and recommendations.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/Phase%20%20Evaluation%20Summary_0.pdf</p>
<p>Evaluation Report</p>	<p>See Me Evaluation of Process and Impact: Phase 2 Year 2 2018</p>	<p>This report provides a summary of the findings from the See Me anti-stigma and discrimination programme in Scotland, from November 2017 until October 2018.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/MHF%20See%20Me%20Report%20Year%20%20FINAL_0.pdf</p>
<p>Evaluation Report</p>	<p>See Me Evaluation of Process and Impact: Phase 2 Year 1 2017</p>	<p>This report provides an overview of the impact of See Me Scotland’s national anti-stigma and discrimination programme from Year 1 of Phase 2 which covers the period November 2016 until October 2017.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/sites/default/files/MHF%20See%20Me%20Report%20Year%201%20Amends%20August%202019%20FINAL_0.pdf</p>
<p>Evaluation Report</p>	<p>Anti Stigma Summer Session Evaluation See Me 2020</p>	<p>The purpose of this evaluation was to explore the process and impact of the ASSS 2020. People who engaged with the online events and activities delivered between July and September 2020 were signposted to an evaluation survey. Survey respondents were given the opportunity to leave their contact details for follow up telephone interviews with a researcher from the Mental Health Foundation Scotland (MHF), to talk about their experiences in more depth.</p> <p>https://seemescotland.org/media/10297/report-stigma.pdf</p>
<p>Review Report</p>	<p>see me so far: A review of the first 4 years of the Scottish anti-stigma campaign 2002- 2005</p>	<p>This review of the first four years of ‘see me’ has been compiled in this Report.</p> <p>http://www.docs.csg.ed.ac.uk/EqualityDiversity/see_me_so_far.pdf</p>

Journal Article	Intervening within and across levels: A multilevel approach to stigma and public health	<p>This article uses a multilevel approach to review the literature on interventions with promise to reduce social stigma and its consequences for population health. Three levels of an ecological system are discussed. Scotland’s “see me” campaign is mentioned as it monitored and corrected misleading portrayals of mental illness and used a media campaign to personalize and normalize mental illness.</p> <p>http://www.columbia.edu/cu/psychology/vpvaughns/assets/pdfs/Intervening%20Across%20Levels%20(2014).pdf</p>
Salus Website	Salus Occupational Health , Safety and Return to Work Services	<p>http://www.salus.co.uk/Pages/default.html</p>
Service Review Portal	Salus Occupational Health & Safety Review	<p>https://nicelocal.co.uk/scotland/medical/salus_occupational_health_safety/</p>
Research Paper	A novel approach to early sickness absence management: The EASY (Early Access to Support for You) way 2015, Research conducted by HWL and Salus	<p>To describe and examine the components of a novel sickness absence management service Early Access to Support for You (EASY) and discuss their potential influence on the intervention. This paper describes an innovative occupational health intervention to sickness absence management based on the bio-psychosocial model to provide early intervention, and discusses the pros and cons of applying cognitive behavioural principles at an early stage in sickness-absence events, in order to improve return-to-work outcomes.</p> <p>https://content.iospress.com/download/work/wor2137?id=work/wor2137</p>
Review Article	Managing quality- A review article on Salus	<p>This article, based on a presentation delivered to the Scottish RCN OH Nurses Forum Conference in April, describes how Salus Occupational Health & Safety implemented a quality management system.</p> <p>https://www.personneltoday.com/hr/managing-quality/</p>

<p>Project Report</p>	<p>The Role of Case Management in the Management of Sickness Absence Social Work Department - North Lanarkshire Council & Salus Occupational Health & Safety 2006</p>	<p>Following discussions between the Director of Salus and the Senior Personnel Manager in the Social Work Department, a 3-month pilot was agreed to assess the value of the use of a Case Management approach to Management of Sickness Absence. This pilot project introduced a collaborative case management / multidisciplinary model to work in conjunction with the Social Work Department's Human Resources Team Aim are- to address management concerns about the level of 'long term' and to assess the effectiveness of the Case Management model in absences as defined by Council assisting the Council to manage sickness absence.</p> <p>https://mars.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/egenda/images/att79490.pdf</p>
<p>Annual Report</p>	<p>SALUS OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE (OHS) STATE HOSPITAL CARSTAIRS 2019-2020</p>	<p>The current provision covers OH Advisor, OH Nurse, Consultant OH Physician, Health and Safety, Physiotherapy, the EASY service and access to Mental Health Case Management. Additionally this arrangement allows access to the Clinical Governance structure and processes in place within Salus together with the Standard Operating Procedures and processes developed in line with our BSI Quality Standard and Safe and Effective Quality Occupational Health Service Accreditation.</p> <p>https://www.tsh.scot.nhs.uk/Board/Docs/Annual%20Reports/OHS%20Annual%20Report%202019-20.pdf</p>
<p>Journal Report</p>	<p>Working Health Services Scotland: a 4-year evaluation 2018</p>	<p>The WHSS evaluation findings indicate that participation was associated with positive changes to health and return-to-work. This study aimed to investigate the health and work/functional outcomes of WHSS clients referred between 2010 and 2014 and understand the factors associated with programme completion and RTW.</p> <p>https://academic.oup.com/occmed/article/68/1/38/4830142</p>
<p>Government Publication Report</p>	<p>Health and work strategy: review report</p>	<p>This Review considers emergent risks and the approach that needs to be taken to health and work in Scotland. In doing so it sets out four policy themes underpinned by a series of health and work principles. The benefits realised from a positive relationship between health and work will be felt by government, employers and individuals alike, and its achievement will require the commitment and concerted efforts of all three sets of stakeholders. Services of Salus were discussed in this report</p> <p>https://www.gov.scot/publications/fair-healthy-work-review-scottish-governments/pages/1/</p>

Report	Moving and Handling Training in South Lanarkshire Social Services	<p>The purpose of the report is to outline a proposal to transition to the Passport model of Moving and Handling training for social services staff in South Lanarkshire Council SALUS MH Passport training is delivered by Health and Care Professions Council (HCPC) registered nursing and allied health professional staff trained in moving and handling. Training staff provide onsite advice and consultancy which ensures timely and relevant professional guidance and support is provided for partners, carers and the cared for.</p> <p>https://southlanarkshire.cmis.uk.com/southlanarkshire/Document.ashx</p>
Website	VOX Scotland	https://voxscotland.org.uk/
Report	Development Plan for Voices of Experience (VOX) 2020 to 2027	<p>Report aims to represent a broad range of development plan to tackle mental ill health, to address injustice, build capacity within membership, work with marginalised communities to ensure they have a voice, influence change and create a vision for the future in mental health.</p> <p>https://voxscotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Scotland-Development-Plan-2020-2027.pdf</p>
Business plan Report	VOX Business Plan 2010-2012	<p>This report include plan to promote, establish, operate and /or support mental health related projects and programmes which are in furtherance of VOX’s charitable purposes, to advance the health and to relieve the needs of people who have, or have had, mental health problems by providing, or encouraging the provision of, services which will improve their conditions of life and also facilitate their full integration into society, to advance education in relation to mental health issues.</p> <p>https://voxscotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Business-plan-2011-2012.pdf</p>
Annual Report	Voice of Experiences (VOX) ANNUAL Report UPDATE 2021	<p>Report aims to suggest that VOX has future opportunities to get involved in the coming months, including the VOX priorities and engagement session, the film launch, and new work which VOXs growing staff team will be taking forward. This new work will include the development of a “snapshot consultation” system, more events and activities to engage with members and reach new members, and opportunities for volunteers.</p> <p>https://voxscotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Scotland-Newsletter-July-21.pdf</p>
Consultation Report	VOX SCOTLAND consultation response to; Increasing the Employment of Disabled People in the Public Sector - Consultation.	<p>Report suggests that meaningful employment for people with lived experience of mental ill health can be very rewarding and beneficial. It can address issues such as, financial insecurity, loneliness and can be central to improving the quality of life for people, reducing the likelihood of developing mental health problems, and supporting recovery.</p> <p>https://voxscotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-SCOTLAND-consultation-response-to-Public-Sector-Employment..pdf</p>

<p>Research Report</p>	<p>Untapped Potential: A research study in Scotland, June 2018, VOX</p>	<p>Report discusses how people with lived experience of mental health issues engage in civic and public life. This report outlines the results of a participative research project funded under the first round of DRILL grants in Scotland and carried out during 2017/18. The grant was awarded under the theme of 'participating in civic and public life'.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/14183-Mental-Health-DRLL-Report-A4-Rev7.pdf</p>
<p>Consultation document</p>	<p>VOX SCOTLAND consultation response to; A Connected Scotland: Tackling social isolation and loneliness and building stronger social connections.</p>	<p>This report talks about building social connections and addressing loneliness and how these are central to improving the quality of life for all, reducing the likelihood of developing mental ill health, and supporting recovery. VOX believes we must address the loneliness epidemic, and that society and services must see building social connections, reaching out to people, and supporting those most at risk as a key aspect of improving mental health.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wpcontent/uploads/2015/01/VOX-SCOTLAND-consultation-response-to-social-isolation-3final.pdf</p>
<p>Research Report</p>	<p>VOX Scotland: Real People, Real Cut 2016-2017</p>	<p>This report is the 3rd of its kind following the experience that people with mental health issues have had in Scotland over the last 6 years if budget cuts and welfare reform. The 1st two reports were entitled Real People Real Cuts and this 3rd report Real People Deeper Cuts, reflects the increasing negative trend that people have experienced over the years.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/Real-People-deeper-cuts.pdf</p>
<p>Report</p>	<p>VOX GOOD PRACTICE IN SERVICE USER INVOLVEMENT - MAY 2007</p>	<p>This document is to be seen as a collection of the views of many Scottish mental health service users and people with a lived experience of mental health problems. VOX have developed this document to illustrate some of the considerations and requirements which should be taken into account if effective service user involvement is both to become more widespread, and if it is to achieve the desired outcomes for all those invited to participate.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/Good-Practice-in-Service-User-Involvement-2007.pdf</p>
<p>Report</p>	<p>VOX Response to Mental Health Act Review 2009</p>	<p>This report shows VOX's response to the consultation on the Limited Review of the Mental Health (Care and Treatment) (Scotland) Act 2003. VOX aim to drive policy and practice, facilitate partnership working and strengthen the voice of people who have or have had a mental health problem. VOX aim to do this by using a range of innovative and accessible consultation methods to involve members. VOX asked its membership about its views on the Mental Health Act Limited Review to understand what parts of the act are working well and what areas our members felt could be improved on.</p>

		https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Response-to-Mental-Health-Act-Review-2009.pdf
Report	VOX response to the outline draft mental health strategy 2016	<p>This report shows VOX’s response to the the outline draft mental health strategy. VOX aim to drive policy and practice, facilitate partnership working and strengthen the voice of people who have or have had a mental health problem. VOX aim to do this by using a range of innovative and accessible consultation methods to involve members.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Response-to-Mental-Health-Act-Review-2009.pdf</p>
Consultation Report	VOX Consultation on Psychological Therapies	<p>VOX members were asked to respond to a questionnaire which explained the development of psychological therapies in Scotland and asked if people could suggest three improvements to the provision of psychological therapies that they believed would make a difference.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Consultation-on-Psychological-Therapies.pdf</p>
Report	VOX’s response to the DWP’s “No-one written off: Reforming Welfare to Reward Responsibility” Public Consultation	<p>There has been a great deal of concern over the last few months about the proposed changes within welfare reform, and the implications this will have for those with mental health problems. For this reason we felt it was important to obtain some meaningful qualitative information on the concerns that those who have or have had mental health problems have in relation to these proposed changes.</p> <p>https://voxsotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/VOX-Response-to-DWP-Consultation.pdf</p>
Website	Remote Workmates	http://remoteworkmates.com/
Website	Woebot Health	https://woebothealth.com/
Journal Article	Delivering Cognitive Behavior Therapy to Young Adults With Symptoms of Depression and Anxiety Using a Fully Automated Conversational Agent (Woebot):	<p>The objective of the study was to determine the feasibility, acceptability, and preliminary efficacy of a fully automated conversational agent to deliver a self-help program for college students who self-identify as having symptoms of anxiety and depression.</p> <p>https://mental.jmir.org/2017/2/e19/</p>

	A Randomized Controlled Trial	
Newspaper Article	Something Bothering You? Tell It to Woebot.	This newspaper article try to discuss-Can therapy by bot make people understand themselves better? Can it change long-held patterns of behavior through a series of probing questions and reflective exercises? Or is human connection essential to that endeavor? https://www.nytimes.com/2021/06/01/health/artificial-intelligence-therapy-woebot.html
Newspaper Article	Digital therapist' Woebot perks up with \$90M for AI- powered mental health platform	This article suggests that in an examination of Woebot’s conversations with more than 36,000 users, researchers found that, powered by natural language processing and other AI algorithms, the chatbot was able to build a genuine rapport with patients within just three to five days. The study also found that in some cases, Woebot was able to build a therapeutic bond faster and longer-lasting than those created between human therapists and their patients.
Journal Article	Evidence of Human- Level Bonds Established With a Digital Conversational Agent: Cross- sectional, Retrospective Observational Study 2021	This study aimed to investigate whether users of a cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT)–based conversational agent would report therapeutic bond levels that are similar to those in literature about other CBT modalities, including face-to-face therapy, group CBT, and other digital interventions that do not use a conversational agent. https://formative.jmir.org/2021/5/e27868/
Journal Article	Acceptability of postnatal mood management through a smartphone- based automated conversational agent	Automated conversational agents (chatbots) that provide cognitive behavioral therapy content through real time text message interfaces have been found to reduce depression and anxiety symptoms in select populations. This study sought to evaluate patient satisfaction with and the acceptability of a chatbot as a postpartum mood management tool. Woebot was used in this study. https://www.ajog.org/article/S0002-9378(19)31460-7/fulltext#relatedArticles

<p>Research Letter and viewpoint</p>	<p>Conversational Agents in Health Care</p>	<p>Executive leadership from Woebot wrote a letter to the editor of JAMA in response to an opinion piece calling for independent and additional regulation of conversational agents in health care. The letter argues that conversational agents do not need a separate regulatory mechanism because they should be considered in the context of their intended use, for which adequate regulatory mechanisms exist.</p> <p>https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/2774042?resultClick=1</p>
<p>Report</p>	<p>Woebot Health Research Publications and works in progress</p>	<p>This paper talks about all the research publications and work in progress by Woebot</p> <p>https://woebohealth.com/img/2021/05/Woebot-Health-Research-Bibliography_May-2021-1-1.pdf</p>
<p>Book</p>	<p>Deep Medicine: How Artificial Intelligence Can Make Medicine Human Again</p>	<p>A thoughtful and deep description from leading physician Eric Topol on the ways AI can truly unlock the potential of medicine – from deep learning techniques to identifying previously undiscovered tumor features to reinstating a meaningful patient-doctor relationship – to help make medicine better for all humans. Woebot was featured in this Book.</p> <p>https://www.basicbooks.com/titles/eric-topol-md/deep-medicine/9781541644649/#:~:text=In%20Deep%20Medicine%2C%20leading%20physician,medicine%20and%20reducing%20human%20mortality.</p>
<p>Journal Article</p>	<p>Psychological, Relational, and Emotional Effects of Self-Disclosure After Conversations With a Chatbot</p>	<p>This study advances current understanding of disclosure and whether its impact is altered by technology, providing support for media equivalency as a primary mechanism for the consequences of disclosing to a chatbot.</p> <p>https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6074615/</p>
<p>Website</p>	<p>MHScot Workplace Wellbeing</p>	<p>https://www.mentalhealthscot.land/</p>
<p>Website Article</p>	<p>Catherine and MHScot</p>	<p>In this article MHScot Catherine talked about how MHScot operates across Scotland and works with businesses and enterprises within the private, third and public sectors. Most of their activity has a focus on training and education and they design and deliver training programmes and workshops for teams of staff.</p> <p>https://www.communitycatalysts.co.uk/story/catherine-and-mhscot/</p>

Website News	Apex Hotels opens out mental health training series	<p>The news is about the collaboration between Apex Hotels, who will provide training facilities at its Apex City of Edinburgh Hotel and MHScot, who will deliver the courses through trained instructors, came out of the hotel group’s drive to provide training and support to its own employees.</p> <p>https://www.conference-news.co.uk/news/apex-hotels-opens-out-mental-health-training-series</p>
Company Report	Community Interest Company Report MHScot	<p>This report illustrates what the Regulator of Community Interest Companies considers to be best practice for completing a simplified community interest company report.</p> <p>https://www.mentalhealthscot.land/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/MHScot-CIC-Report-2019-20.pdf</p>
Government Website	Shades of Blue Campaign MHScot	<p>In this news article the Parliament congratulates MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC (MHScot), which it understands is Scotland’s first social enterprise, on the launch of its Shades of Blue emoji-like stickers to raise awareness of stress prevention and early mental health intervention in the workplace.</p> <p>https://www.parliament.scot/chamber-and-committees/votes-and-motions/votes-and-motions-search/S5M-03491</p>
Media Release	MHScot launches ‘shades of blue’ emojis to raise awareness of mental health in the workplace	<p>‘Shades of blue’ is being led by well-known social enterprise, MHScot Workplace Wellbeing CIC (MHScot) – aimed at stress prevention and early mental health intervention. The campaign wants to see ‘mental health First Aid training’ as a mandatory part of workplace health and safety.</p> <p>http://www.allmediascotland.com/media-releases/121030/media-release-mhscot-launches-shades-of-blue-emojis-to-raise-awareness-of-mental-health-in-the-workplace/</p>
Website	CIPD	<p>https://www.cipd.co.uk/</p>
Article	Mobilising wellbeing initiatives through technology, CIPD	<p>This article, CIPD shares two case studies of how people professionals in Ireland and the UK have used technology to mobilise initiatives that address several domains of wellbeing CIPD then provide a framework with examples to help you identify opportunities where technology can enhance your initiatives.</p> <p>https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/work/technology/digital-transformation-insights/mobilising-wellbeing-initiatives</p>
Review Report	Financial Wellbeing: An Evidence Review	<p>Evidence-based insight and practical recommendations for addressing employee financial wellbeing in the workplace.</p> <p>https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/evidence-financial-wellbeing</p>
Review Report	Mental wellbeing and digital work: an evidence review CIPD	<p>This review summarises the best available research on workplace mental wellbeing, including whether digital work harms mental wellbeing.</p> <p>https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/evidence-mental-wellbeing</p>

Report	Health and wellbeing at work, CIPD	It provides a wealth of benchmarking data on key areas like absence management, wellbeing benefits and mental health. The report includes forewords from the CIPD and Simplyhealth, detailed analyses and sector-based summaries, case studies from two organisations, and a concise guide outlining the steps you can take to support your employees' wellbeing.
Review Report	Employee resilience: an evidence review CIPD	This evidence review, based on a rapid evidence assessment (REA), finds several key factors that protect or reinforce resilience. https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/evidence-resilience
Review Report	Growing the health and well-being agenda CIPD	This report reviews the extent to which well-being considerations are integrated into UK organisations and highlights future priorities for the HR profession. It looks at how the changing nature of work, the workforce and the workplace is making a focus on individual well-being even more critical to broader organisational health and well-being. https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/health-agenda-report
Review Report	Preventing stress: positive manager behaviour	Reports on the final phase of research, funded by the HSE, CIPD and Investors in People, into management competencies for minimising workplace stress. This report, which builds on research carried out in 2009, looks at how managers used the interventions materials and how they implemented the work in practice. https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/preventing-stress-report
Guide	A guide to becoming a carer-friendly workplace	this guide discusses what we mean by a 'working carer' in the first place, considers the business, legal and moral reasons for care-friendly workplaces. https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/carer-friendly-workplace
Factsheet	Stress in the workplace CIPD Factsheet	This factsheet defines stress and draws the distinction between stress and pressure. It offers information on UK employers' duties under health and safety law and concludes with guidance on how to deal with stress at work, providing information on prevention, early intervention and stress policies. https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/stress-factsheet
Podcast	Pulling the plug on digital fatigue CIPD	Digital communication tools have been a necessary lifeline this past year, helping homeworkers stay engaged and connected. This podcast considers how we can foster a healthy relationship with these tools, avoid digital fatigue and harness the benefits. https://www.cipd.co.uk/podcasts/pull-plug-on-digital-fatigue
Website	Mental Health at Work (MHW)	https://www.mentalhealthatwork.org.uk/
Guide Report	Guide for line managers: Wellness	This guide is designed to be a helpful starting point in your journey as a line manager towards supporting your team members with their mental health at work.

	Action Plans (WAPs) MHW	https://www.mind.org.uk/media-a/5761/mind-guide-for-line-managers-wellness-action-plans_final.pdf
Guide Report	Guide for employees: Wellness Action Plans (WAPs) MHW	<p>This guide is designed for anyone in employment or a voluntary role who would like to learn more about how to use Wellness Action Plans (WAPs) to support and promote their mental health and wellbeing at work.</p> <p>https://mind.org.uk/media-a/5760/mind-guide-for-employees-wellness-action-plans_final.pdf</p>
Mind Website	Mental Health at Work Website Evaluation	<p>Mind in its website stated that the site brings together resources, toolkits, blogs and case studies into one place. Regardless of the sector you work in, the size of your organisation or the location you're based, you'll find what you need at Mental Health at Work.</p> <p>https://www.mind.org.uk/workplace/mental-health-at-work-website/</p>
Guide	A guide to compassionate bereavement support	<p>This guide aims to help employers and managers properly support grieving employees by providing compassionate and flexible responses in the immediate aftermath of bereavement and in the longer term. The guide will look at the law relating to bereavement, developing a supportive culture and policy, and the training and support that should be offered to line managers and employees</p> <p>https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/culture/well-being/bereavement-support</p>
Report	Better for Business: a report into the wellbeing of small business owners	<p>From financial worries and stress, to isolation and sleep problems – it's vital that small business owners receive the support they need and deserve. That's why – in addition to shining a light on the emerging wellbeing crisis among this audience – Simply Business partnered with a range of experts to offer free tips and resources tailored to the self-employed. MHW is sharing this report in their Small business toolkit.</p> <p>https://www.simplybusiness.co.uk/downloads/better-for-business-wellbeing-report.pdf</p>
Guide Article	Let's talk mental health	<p>We all have mental health, in the same way that we all have physical health too. Our mental health affects the way we think, feel and behave, which is why it's so important that we take the time to look after our mental health and wellbeing and look out for one another. This is a guide to talk to each other at work about mental health. MHW is sharing this guide in their small business tool kit.</p> <p>https://cdn.mentalhealthatwork.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/02152903/Lets-Talk-Mental-health.pdf</p>

Appendix V: Excel File for Data Coding and Case Mapping

https://studentmailuwsac-my.sharepoint.com/:x:/g/personal/b00334605_studentmail_uws_ac_uk/EW2KJnDdjWVHn-Vjl6oERggBhTjUzwiZp2g4PrUpCVTCAQ?rtime=67PRz-uu2Ug